

AI TRANSFORMER- BASED MODELS:

Comparative Study and Proposals in the Field
of Neurodivergence, Specifically for Dyslexia
and ADHD

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UNIVERSITY

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DECLARATION

Statement of Original Authorship

I hereby certify that the work presented in this thesis is the result of my own independent research and writing. Except where specific assistance is acknowledged, it has been composed entirely by me without the use of generative AI for substantive writing or analysis. Any AI tools mentioned within the text were used solely as objects of study or for experimental purposes, not as authorship aids.

This thesis has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification. All sources of information and ideas, including AI-generated material where relevant, have been clearly acknowledged.

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Date: 31 August 2025

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ABSTRACT

This thesis investigates the potential of Transformer-Based Models (TBMs) to support text accessibility, interdisciplinary translation, and educational inclusivity, with a focus on neurodiverse learners, particularly those with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. The research spans three key strands: linguistic simplification and transformation, domain mapping across academic disciplines, and the development of assistive educational technology. Central to the thesis is the use of TBMs (including ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, DeepSeek, and finetuned T5 models) to translate and simplify content between domains such as music, neuroscience, Arabic, and education. A novel approach referred to as YAM (Yet Another Metaphor) was developed to evaluate the ability of TBMs to reformulate content from one discipline or linguistic context into another. Besides transforming scientific concepts, it also includes mapping music theory elements onto psychological or cognitive frameworks. To support neurodivergent readers, the study also explores both rule-based and model-based simplification techniques aimed at reducing phonetic and structural complexity in English. A pilot empirical study involving Key Stage 1 and 2 pupils with Dyslexia and/or ADHD demonstrated a near-significant improvement in comprehension ($p = 0.0625$) under a simplified text condition, with no significant change in reading time ($p = 0.4961$), suggesting that the intervention enhanced understanding without increasing cognitive load. This result was discussed with the wider view of developing this model into a more advanced TBM, which, when enriched with insights from child psychologists and SEN (Special Educational Needs) specialists, could evolve into powerful, adaptive AI tools capable of delivering personalised, cognitively informed text simplification at scale. In response to the need for learner-specific flexibility, the thesis introduces a prototype mobile application designed to deliver real-time, customisable text simplification. This app, rooted in principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL), supports phonetic adaptations, multilingual content, and age-appropriate readability controls. Together, the app, empirical findings, and TBM comparisons provide a blueprint for lightweight, scalable solutions to educational accessibility. Ultimately, this work contributes to interdisciplinary AI research, music cognition, Arabic NLP, and inclusive pedagogy. It demonstrates that TBMs, when evaluated critically and applied creatively, offer significant promise for transforming how learners engage with complex or unfamiliar content across

languages, disciplines, and cognitive profiles. The development of the YAM framework, alongside the exploration of Arabic as a non-Latin script within this context, constitutes a novel contribution to interdisciplinary AI research. Unlike most evaluations of TBMs, which remain within monolingual or monodisciplinary boundaries, this work introduces a deliberately metaphor-driven approach to domain transformation. This approach challenges the assumptions of semantic neutrality in cross-domain translation. Additionally, by highlighting the severe limitations of existing TBMs when applied to Arabic, particularly in educational accessibility and neurodivergent contexts, this thesis exposes a critical research gap. These contributions, metaphor as a transformation strategy, and Arabic-language processing as a neglected axis of accessibility, are not only original but also open pathways for expanding the cognitive and linguistic inclusivity of AI models in real-world settings.

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INTRODUCTION

The research presented in this thesis explores how Transformer-Based Models (TBMs) can be evaluated and adapted to aid reading and comprehension across disciplinary boundaries, with a specific focus on individuals with neurodivergent profiles, particularly Dyslexia and Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). The central aim is to assess how effectively TBMs can transform specialist texts from one discipline into another, while also developing strategies to simplify complex language for greater accessibility. This goal emerged from early experiments in cross-disciplinary translation using Artificial Intelligence (AI), and from a broader interest in the potential of TBMs to support inclusive education and research.

My engagement with AI dates back to my time at UMIST (now part of the University of Manchester, UK), where I worked as a Senior Research Assistant on the algebraic object-oriented language, OBJ, a programming tool for modelling AI systems. I developed the compiler for a version of OBJ, later published in *The Computer Journal* (Gallimore, et al., 1989). This foundational experience informed my long-standing interest in AI, particularly in how object-oriented principles, now central to frameworks like TensorFlow (Abadi, et al., 2016), and PyTorch (Paszke, et al., 2019) underpin the design of neural networks used in Natural Language Processing (NLP).

The idea for this research originated from an informal but revealing experiment. A chapter from Dr Micka Clayton's interdisciplinary doctoral thesis (Clayton, 2023) combining musicology and neuroscience, was processed using ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2025). The goal was to prompt the model to rewrite the chapter for two distinct audiences: one in music education, and the other in neuroscience. Remarkably, the AI-generated outputs, evaluated by Dr Clayton, preserved semantic accuracy across both transformations. This prompted a broader investigation of TBMs' reliability in supporting interdisciplinary communication by transforming technical language across fields. More ambitiously, to ascertain if these models can be repurposed to support those who struggle with conventional academic text from other specialisations, and more specifically neurodivergent individuals with conditions such as Dyslexia or ADHD.

Transformer-Based Models as introduced in Vaswani, et al. (2017), have become central to modern NLP. They support tasks like text generation, summarisation, and machine translation. While much progress has been made, challenges remain, particularly in simplifying complex academic or technical texts without losing precision. This research aims to bridge that gap through three main threads:

- evaluating TBMs' ability to perform domain-domain transformations.
- identifying which TBMs are most effective for such tasks.
- investigating how these models might be adapted to improve access for neurodivergent readers.

Given the research's emphasis on accessibility, it is essential to understand the challenges presented by Dyslexia and ADHD. Dyslexia is a neurological learning difficulty that affects reading, writing, and decoding language despite average or above-average intelligence. Its key characteristics include poor phonological processing, slow reading, and difficulty with spelling. ADHD, a neurodevelopmental condition, impairs attention regulation and impulse control and often co-occurs with Dyslexia. While ADHD does not directly affect language processing, individuals often struggle with lengthy or complex texts due to inattention or cognitive overload.

These challenges are not yet adequately addressed by current AI tools. While TBMs have been applied to text simplification tasks, few have been designed specifically for neurodivergent users. This thesis proposes a structured evaluation of current TBMs, followed by a targeted experiment involving domain-domain transformation and text adaptation. The ultimate goal is to inform the development of a refined TBM-based system that enhances text accessibility for individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. The results may also contribute to broader NLP applications in education, publishing, and interdisciplinary research.

As will be seen later, identifying particular language difficulties in individuals with ADHD is not an easy task, and therefore not many solutions exist amongst TBMs or any other forms of AI models to address this. Apart from simplifications and restructuring texts, nothing significant has been done thus far to aid readability and comprehension for individuals with ADHD. One way to converge on a potential aid is

to combine simplification with other attention-focusing textual techniques, as this research will propose later by employing various TBMs in devising a strategy, and an AI model that can be further finetuned and developed in the future.

As a starting point, the ability of various TBMs to perform the task of domain-domain transformation needs to be examined. This will help to identify the most efficient TBM for the task and subsequently inform the design of a model, or the basis of one, that can provide targeted solutions for the specific needs of Dyslexia and ADHD. This process, consisting of several trials and subsequent evaluations, will pave the way to furthering the application of such models to aid Dyslexia and ADHD readability, and thus comprehension where possible. The findings of these trials may also benefit academia, industry, and accessibility-focused NLP applications, as well as suggesting alternative approaches for designing other experiments, which may lead to further improvements in the future design of TBMs.

In this thesis, Chapter 1 provides a general background of the history and development of TBMs before moving to a survey of the available relevant literature. The focus is on the role of TBMs in aid of neurodivergence, especially Dyslexia and ADHD, as these conditions have a prominent place in this study. A consideration of the methodology, and methods used in this research follows, including model selection, data collection, and evaluation techniques. In addition, a comprehensive search through the most well-known platforms for any models and datasets that can benefit individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD, such as Hugging Face (Hugging Face Diffusers, n.d.) and GitHub (GitHub, n.d.), amongst others, is included.

Chapter 2 covers the research design, methodology, and the methods followed in this study in more detail, while Chapter 3 deals with the hypotheses and plans of the research. This sets a road map for larger experiments with TBMs, planning the route and stages for larger trials and sets the scene of what is expected to be accomplished on a larger scale.

The selection of TBMs, their comparison, and the protocol and results of conducting various trials with the selected models, are reported in Chapter 4. In Chapter 5, a report on the role of TBMs in the field of neurodivergence delves deeper into investigating the role and ability of these TBMs when dealing with

Dyslexia and ADHD. In addition, it explores Bionic Reading© (Casutt, n.d.), a non-AI system with a potentially beneficial role to play, especially in assisting with ADHD readability, as intended by its inventor.

In Chapter 6, a pilot system of a dataset and rule-based AI model is created as proof of concept of the capability of TBMs in generating aids to Dyslexia and ADHD. An app is visualised using concepts developed in the rule-based model. In addition, a model to aid individuals with Dyslexia reading musical notation is developed based on real-time work.

Following on from the theoretical concepts, a real-life Dyslexia/ADHD readability experiment was conducted with primary school children. The design, execution, and implications, as well as the statistical analysis of the results are reported in Chapter 7.

The research concludes in Chapter 8 with various findings drawn from the preceding trials, as well as a host of propositions to expand the theme of this research, getting the most out of TBMs for the public good, in the near future.

To aid visual clarity, a colouring convention was followed throughout this thesis as below:

Python code & extracts	Response from TBMs
Inference result	Golden standard
Input text	Scoring
Prompt	Game dialogue

CHAPTER 1: BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE SURVEY

1.1 TRANSFORMER-BASED MODELS (TBMs)

As mentioned in the Introduction to this thesis, AI models with the capability to summarise, simplify, and explain documents and speech, are termed Transformer-Based Models (TBMs), and was first introduced in a paper by Vaswani, et al. (2017).

Their main function and influence on NLP are in enabling state-of-the-art performance in tasks, including text generation, summarisation, and translation. This section gives a brief description of the general architecture of a TBM. Since the publication of the above paper, there has been a substantial amount of academic work carried out in order to improve the criteria and design purpose of TBMs. Still, in general, most TBMs share the same fundamental basic architecture, with two key parts: The Encoder, which is responsible for processing the input sequence, by converting it into a numerical sequence of digits, and the Decoder, which generates the output sequence according to the specific function of the model, whether it is summarisation, simplification, or translation. Figure 1 below illustrates the basic architecture of a transformer.

FIGURE 1: TRANSFORMER ARCHITECTURE (THEAVERAGEGAL, 2021)

1.1.1 TBM PRINCIPLES AND TRAINING

There are two principles that enable TBMs to perform their intended tasks in a parallel rather than sequential fashion, making them more efficient than traditional NLP models. The latter performs sequential analysis of an input sequence, such as in older machine translation models translating only one word at a time, usually resulting in a poor output.

The first of these principles is a self-attention mechanism. This is a core mechanism allowing the model to weigh the importance of different words in a sentence when processing each word, normally referred to as a ‘token’ in the literature. This gives a TBM awareness of the context without relying on the recurrences of a token, which helps the model focus on important words in the sentence. For instance, in the sentence “the monkey ate an apple because it is delicious”, based on the semantic similarity between the token “apple” and the token “it”, the transformer would relate the two tokens rather than assuming that “it” refers to “monkey”.

The other principle is positional encoding, which is a way for TBMs to understand the position of a word in a sentence. Without positional encoding, a sentence like “I eat apples” would appear exactly the same to a TBM as “eat I apples”, since the first input has exactly the same words as the second.

For TBMs to perform effectively, they are trained extensively and finetuned using massive datasets purposed for this task. These datasets are collections of structured data designed solely for this purpose. TBMs usually go through iterations where output is evaluated for key features such as accuracy, robustness, and efficiency, and subsequently refined or finetuned accordingly. There are multiple ways finetuning can be achieved, depending on the ultimate goal or function of a TBM. Some of these approaches are:

- Altering the parameters up or down
- Retrain on specialised datasets
- Optimisation according to human interface

To illustrate some of these concepts, the following model has been developed.

1.1.2 ILLUSTRATION MODEL

The following example of a minute model provides an abstracted perspective of how transformers operate on vectorised textual input. By manually simulating input features, it illustrates the notion of mapping language to numerical vectors, a process central to transformer-based NLP systems (Vaswani, et al., 2017). With only ten parameters, it will be a pedagogical linear-transformer model.

In this example, the model's task is to determine whether an input sentence is a simple or a complex one. Initially, ten simple features that describe the sentence are defined. Each feature has a value between 0 and 1. These features are:

1. Sentence length
2. Average word length
3. Number of difficult words (based on a simple word list)
4. Number of syllables per word (average)
5. Passive voice usage (yes = 1, no = 0)
6. Number of commas
7. Number of abstract nouns
8. Percentage of function words (the, is, and, etc.)
9. Percentage of content words (nouns, verbs, adjectives)
10. Number of rare words (not in top 1000 words)

Each sentence gets turned into a 10-dimensional vector e.g.

$$x = [0.3, 0.4, 0.1, 0.5, 0, 0.2, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4, 0.1]$$

The model is just a weighted sum of those features (like a simplified neural network):

$$y = w_1 * x_1 + w_2 * x_2 + \dots + w_{10} * x_{10} + b$$

In this example, the model's parameters were given the following weights:

$$w = [1.2, 0.8, 2.0, 1.5, 1.0, 0.5, 1.3, -0.6, -0.3, 1.8]$$

$$b = -2.0$$

Where "w" is a weight. Weights in this model are specified explicitly but in large TBMs, they would be learned by training, hence they are referred to as "learned parameters".

The "b" parameter is the bias term which is essential in various ways:

- The bias acts like a starting point, or an offset without which the output of the model would always be anchored to zero, unless the weighted inputs force it elsewhere.
- It also helps the model learn better. Even if the input is zero, the model is still expected to predict something like “Simple”. Without a bias, “y” above would be zero, but with it, the model would have learnt that even without the existence of strong features, it should incline toward a prediction.

The next step in the model’s function is computing the “y” value by multiplying the weight by the value of each feature:

$$y = (1.2)(0.3) + (0.8)(0.4) + (2.0)(0.1) + \dots + (1.8)(0.1) - 2.0$$

Then, to apply a decision rule:

- If $y > 0$, the sentence is complex
- If $y \leq 0$, the sentence is simple

TBMs rely on the optimisation of a vast number of learned parameters (millions or even billions). These parameters are learned during the training process to capture complex linguistic patterns and contextual relationships within the data.

Below is the above model in Python, with an input sentence and feature values:

```
# Simple Classifier Model
import numpy as np
# Get sentence from user
sentence = input("Enter a sentence: ")
# Ask user to enter 10 numerical features (simulated)
print("Enter 10 feature values between 0 and 1, separated by
spaces:")
features_input = input("Features: ")
# Convert input to numpy array
x = np.array([float(val) for val in features_input.strip().split()])
if len(x) != 10:
    print("Error: Please enter exactly 10 feature values.")
else:
    # Model weights and bias
    weights = np.array([1.2, 0.8, 2.0, 1.5, 1.0, 0.5, 1.3, -0.6, -
0.3, 1.8])
    bias = -2.0
```

```

# Compute score
y = np.dot(weights, x) + bias
# Make prediction
prediction = "complex" if y > 0 else "simple"
# Output
print(f"\nSentence: {sentence}")
print(f"Score: {y:.2f}")
print(f"Prediction: {prediction}")

```

First Result:

```

Enter a sentence: I am happy.
Enter 10 feature values between 0 and 1, separated by spaces:
Features: 0.24 0.33 0.9 0.01 0.22 0.001 0.7 0 1 0.1
Sentence: I am happy.
Score: 1.38
Prediction: complex
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 %

```

Second Result:

```

Enter a sentence: I am happy.
Enter 10 feature values between 0 and 1, separated by spaces:
Features: 0.1 0.1 0.2 0.01 0.001 0.1 0.1 0.001 0 0
Sentence: I am happy.
Score: -1.20
Prediction: simple
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 %

```

This miniscule model illustrates the core functionality and structure of a TBM in a very simplified form as it converts an input sentence to a numerical vector of features, using the parameters to subsequently compute a prediction. In larger TBMs, there are far more complex processes and layers, but the concept remains the same.

In this example model, a linear transformation is performed adding bias, as happens in the first layer of a TBM. It also performs a decision-making step analogous to how a TBM employs deeper, more complex layers to classify input or predict the next token in a sequence. Unlike larger models, this model neither has self-attention to relate words to each other in the input sentence, nor does it have

multilayered architecture. Its weights are fixed, while in larger TBMs these can be adjusted as models learn through training.

There are other complex characteristics of large TBMs that make them smarter which is lacking in this model, although it makes for a conceptual stepping stone in the world of TBMs. To further illustrate how input features affect the behaviour of the model during inference, consider the first result from this simple model and compare it to the second. Intuitively, it is evident that the input sentence, which is the same in both inferences, is a “simple” one. However, the supplied values in the first case were inaccurately describing these features, and needed to be modified for this set of parameters to obtain the correct result.

Should the model deliver unexpected and illogical result after describing the features accurately, then it is logical to conclude that the weights or the bias in the model must be poorly defined and in need of finetuning, and/or modify its parameters (weights and/or bias).

The two contrasting results above illustrate one approach to verify the strength or otherwise of the parameters chosen, and the start of finetuning and training of the model. An analogy of this would be the building of a musical instrument (model) by an expert performer of the same instrument (correct input features), yet if the sound is dissonant, then the performer must conclude that the instrument needs tuning (adjusting the parameters).

With an understanding of the basic structure and function of TBMs, it is possible to explore in greater depth the uses and functions they perform. This literature survey will focus on their role in domain-domain transformation in general, and in particular, the area of Dyslexia and ADHD.

1.2 THE LITERATURE

Despite the great number of peer-reviewed papers and books written on the subject of TBMs, the majority deal only with their most well-known functions, such as

- Machine translation, summarisation and paraphrasing (sequence-sequence transformation)
- Similarity and semantic search (understanding)
- Text generation

- Domain specific (such as legal)
- Corrections (spelling and grammar)
- Knowledge (queries answering and recognition)

Exploring the existing literature provides several papers that focus on individual models and how they perform in the area of domain-domain transformation, for example from the legal to medical disciplines. These are usually evaluated on individual bases. However, there does not appear to be a specific comparative study that directly contrasts the performance of various TBMs such as T5, BART, GPT-4, UL2, and others, with regard to their performance in transforming texts from one domain to another.

Researchers have carried out a lot of work evaluating TBMs on very large volumes of text such as the whole collection of articles on Wikipedia, or vast amounts of books, and with massive datasets to perform different tasks. The results of such evaluations help researchers improve the models, making them even smarter and more useful. These comparisons are usually concerned with the architecture, size, and efficiency, or to evaluate specific applications of some of these models.

1.2.1 TBM COMPARISON AND DOMAIN-DOMAIN TRANSFORMATION

There have been a number of comparative studies of large models from the point of view of their efficiency in a specific field. These comparisons were merely concerned with more tangible purposes such as medical applications. A study by Boscolo-Rizzo, et al. (2025) involving 16 head and neck surgeons who assessed the TBMs' answers using the Quality Assessment of Medical Artificial Intelligence (QAMAI) tool, illustrated that both ChatGPT and Claude excelled at medical decision cases, outperforming other AI models involved in that study.

Another comparative study by Kung, et al. (2023) benchmarked ChatGPT's performance against contemporary United States Medical Licensing Examination (USMLE) datasets and found its abilities as potentially suitable for medical education and practice, although the evaluation in this study was a purely qualitative one carried out by two expert surgeons.

In the literature survey preceding this research, no published work was found considering any TBM's ability to explain one specific discipline in terms of another, let alone one whose main function is to transform any user-specified discipline into another. The same was found for TBMs that are concerned with the needs of individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. However, there are efforts to improve the functionality of TBMs to achieve better tailored explanations and to sense who the models are talking to so it can adjust its explanation accordingly. If one thinks about it in terms of explaining a medical condition to a 10-year-old child as opposed to informing another doctor, it clearly becomes necessary to enable TBMs to recognise the user.

Ultimately, the hope is for TBMs to be trained to bridge the gap between various disciplines by generating creative explanations using metaphors and analogies leading to personalised learning experiences. For instance, a TBM could explain how brain waves work to a musician by using harmonies as a metaphor for the same. Hence the challenge of comparing several TBMs on domain-domain transformation was selected as the first step in identifying the most suitable TBM for attempting to propose a model to assist individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD.

The research aim is to present, on a modest scale, given time and resource constraints, a model of such comparison and invite other research groups to extend this to cover a wider scope of models and disciplines.

1.2.2 TBM SURVEY

In this section, only a small number of seminal papers on TBMs are covered. These are the most relevant papers on TBMs for this research, although many more are referenced throughout this thesis. Additionally, the background and origin of the TBMs involved in this work will be covered, as well as a host of datasets and models on various research platforms, that are relevant to the ultimate focus of this research, i.e. Dyslexia and ADHD.

The survey is centred on the concept of TBMs as discussed by Vaswani, et al. (2017). In this paper, the team introduced a new architecture for NLP which they called a Transformer, since its main purpose was transforming text from one source into another. Without using recurrence (RNN), which is processing sequences of data one step at a time while maintaining a memory of previous steps, or by

convolutions (CNN), which applies filters in the form of small matrices that slide over the input to capture local patterns, a transformer would pay attention to every word in a sentence in relation to others in the same sentence.

Transformers use self-attention, letting every word see every other word at once, thus processing the text in a parallel fashion, speeding the process of transformation and giving the whole operation more credence.

The new architecture of a transformer typically comprises of an encoder and a decoder, with layers of multi-headed attention to consider not one word at a time, but every word in the sentence in a parallel fashion. It also has a feedforward network, which looks around and ahead for the meaning, without relying on recurrence or applying convolution. In this way, transformers outperform previous models on machine translation tasks and can be trained much faster by virtue of parallel computation.

The Transformer became the foundation for powerful models like BERT, GPT, and T5, which will be discussed below. This paper is considered one of the most influential papers in AI and NLP history, if not the most impactful development thus far.

BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representation Transformer) was subsequently introduced by Devlin, et al. (2018), and designed to read text in both directions at once, to help it understand context more deeply than older models. In this way, the model understands that the meaning of a word can change, depending on what comes both before and after it.

BERT can be finetuned easily to generate other models for a wide range of applications, such as a model for answering queries. It is a very powerful model, as demonstrated in the above paper, by applying it to 11 NLP tasks and achieving positive results.

GPT (Generative Pretrained Transformer) was introduced by Radford, et al. (2018) in the paper entitled “Improving Language Understanding by Generative Pre-Training”. It was the first large-scale TBM that was pretrained on a large body of text (datasets) and then finetuned for specific tasks. Unlike BERT before it, GPT is based solely on the decoder part of the original transformer architecture. It is designed this

way since, being a of the generative kind, it does not need to encode a whole input but only needs to see the previous word in order to predict the next one.

Since GPT is pretrained on such massive datasets and then finetuned to solve complex NLP tasks, it is much more advantageous than training models from zero for each task. GPT's impact on the world of AI has since been significant and led to creating GPT-2 and eventually (at the time of writing) ChatGPT-4.

T5 (Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer) was introduced by Raffel, et al. (2019). Its main objective is to consider every NLP activity as a text-to-text issue that needs to be treated as such, i.e. both input and output are plain texts regardless of whether it's translation, summarisation, question answering, classification, or others. T5 tends to simplify texts, e.g. transforming "The plane speed is supersonic" to "The plane is very fast".

T5 was pretrained on a significant dataset created by the authors, which is a refined version of the Colossal Clean Crawled Corpus (Dodge, et al., 2021), referred to simply as C4, with a size of over 750GB, and generated in various sizes – T5-Base, T5-Large, and T5-11B, with 11 billion parameters. The bigger the model, the better the performance, as will be practically demonstrated later in this thesis. T5 was benchmarked on many platforms and achieved state-of-the-art results across many tasks.

In 2023, Google DeepMind introduced **Gemini** (Google DeepMind, 2023). This report introduced a new family of multimodal (combining vision and language) models, named Gemini, that exhibits the ability to understand multimedia input from image, audio, video, and text. As with its predecessor T5 and GPT, the Gemini family consists of different sizes suitable for applications ranging from complex reasoning tasks to ones that run on devices with limited memory.

Gemini was measured on a broad range of benchmarks showing the larger member of this family's remarkable result. The above paper states claims about it "notably being the first model to achieve human-expert performance on the well-studied exam benchmark MMLU and improving the state of the art in every one of the 20 multimodal benchmarks we examined" (p.1).

Like GPT, Gemini models are built upon a decoder-only transformer architecture, optimised for efficiency. This design enables the models to handle

diverse input modalities seamlessly, allowing for compound processing of text, images, audio, and video within the same context window.

Claude, another decoder-only transformer, was introduced by Bai, et al. (2022) as Constitutional AI, with the principle of aligning AI systems with human values by minimising harmful outputs without extensive human intervention. This approach comprises two main phases:

- Supervised learning, where it generates responses to prompts, then evaluates its own response against a set of ethical guidelines, called ‘Constitution’.
- Reinforcement Learning from AI Feedback (RLAIF), where the model compares various responses to ensure alignment with the Constitution.

The Constitution includes principles derived from documents like the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights, a novel approach to designing AI models.

Meta-AI is a deep learning model that generates object proposals to identify and segment potential objects in an image, without relying on traditional hand-crafted features like edges.

The developers propose a convolutional neural network (CNN) that learns to predict a segmentation mask for an object in an image patch. The same network also outputs an object-related score of how likely it is that the patch contains a full object. Once trained, the network is applied densely across an image, scanning many locations and scales, and then generates a set of object segmentation masks, each scored for likelihood of being a real object.

In benchmark, Meta-AI produced high-quality object proposals that improved performance in downstream tasks like object detection. This was one of the earliest deep learning-based approaches to the object proposal generation, laying the groundwork for modern object detection frameworks.

Without delving deeper, it is interesting that this model is based on image segmentation when dealing with NLP issues, because at first glance, image segmentation seems purely visual and unrelated to NLP. There is however a deeper connection, especially as AI systems get more multimodal. Briefly, image segmentation helps NLP by giving it precise, structured visual information, enabling language models to refer to, reason about, and describe objects in images or video. This is the principal *modus operandi* of a modern multimodal AI.

The next model trialled in this research is Microsoft Bing Chat, known as **Copilot** (Microsoft, 2025). This is among the earliest comprehensive academic studies focused on Microsoft Bing Chat. The study empirically examines how users engage with Bing Chat to perform knowledge-intensive tasks such as writing, coding, and data analysis. It highlights that users utilise Bing Chat for tasks that are more cognitively demanding compared to traditional search engines, indicating a shift towards more sophisticated usage. The findings suggest that generative search engines like Bing Chat are increasingly being integrated into professional workflows, and assisting users in complex problem-solving and decision-making processes. As such, this paper serves as a foundational analysis of how generative AI tools like Microsoft Copilot are transforming knowledge, work, and complex tasks.

A late appearance on the scene of publicly accessible AI models is **DeepSeek** (Chen, et al., 2024). This foundational paper introduces DeepSeek as an open-source Large Language Model (LLM), developed by the Chinese AI startup DeepSeek. The research focuses on scaling laws and efficient pretraining strategies for LLMs, emphasising long-term sustainability and cost-effectiveness.

It uses a high-quality dataset comprising two trillion tokens for pretraining, covering diverse domains to enhance model generalisation. The paper also discusses the development of DeepSeek Chat, a finetuned version of the LLM optimised for conversational tasks.

1.2.3 USING YAM FOR COMPARISON

In addition to discussing all the TBMs this research will be using, or refers to as a main source of knowledge, the origin of this thesis intended comparing these models for ability and functionality in the area of domain-domain transformation using a YAM approach. To that end, it is essential to consider any research that conducted such a comparative study, despite possibly using a different approach and topic for comparison. For this purpose, the work of Uppalapati & Nag (2024) in comparing AI models' (ChatGPT, Claude AI, Bard, and Perplexity) performance in complex medical decision-making scenarios will be explored.

The models were assessed across 4 key metrics: accuracy, relevance, clarity, and completeness. Claude AI emerged as the top performer, achieving an average score of 3.64 for relevance and 3.43 for completeness. ChatGPT consistently

performed well, while Google Bard exhibited significant variability in clarity, leading to inconsistent responses. Perplexity AI (Perplexity AI, Inc., n.d.) demonstrated moderate performance across the evaluated metrics. However, the evaluation metrics for this study was based on relatively subjective features:

- Accuracy – how correct and scientifically sound the information was
- Relevance – how well the response aligned with the medical scenario
- Clarity – how clearly the information was presented
- Completeness – how comprehensive the model's response was in addressing all aspects of the query

It was hoped that the comparison's metric would be of a more a quantitative one to inform this research, but evidently the above criteria were of a qualitative nature, relying on experts to score the importance of each of these criteria above. That is not to say that no other comparative studies using quantitative tools exist, but there is a definite lack of comparative studies in this relatively young world of TBMs.

One more example of a comparative study between ChatGPT and Bard (Ahmed, et al., 2023) delves deep into the architecture, training methodologies, performance evaluations, and limitations across various domains. However, the study does not present a direct comparison but more of an assessment of the impact and efficacy of each of these two models in various domains, and no metric evaluation was conducted.

1.2.4 ECONOMIC IMPACT OF TBMs

Having covered some of the existing literature, there is an important discussion to be touched upon before concluding this section, namely the economic aspect of AI large models' development.

In recent years, the development of large-scale AI models such as GPT-based transformers has emerged as a significant economic force, driven by both technological innovation and the pursuit of strategic market advantages. These models function as foundational digital infrastructure across sectors, enabling new forms of automation, personalisation, and knowledge work augmentation. Their economic impetus is rooted in economies of scale where the marginal cost of

deployment diminishes after training, and in their ability to confer competitive advantages in areas such as search, advertising, and customer interaction.

However, the impact is unevenly distributed. While they stimulate productivity and innovation, particularly through an open Application Programming Interface (API) and downstream applications, their development is largely monopolised by a few resource-rich entities, due to the immense computational and financial costs involved. This concentration raises concerns about equitable access, global AI leadership, and socioeconomic disparities. At the same time, these models enable broad innovation spillovers, empowering smaller firms, educational institutions, and researchers to build on the capabilities of pretrained systems. As such, LLMs represent both a transformative economic opportunity and a structural shift in the distribution of technological power.

In a later section of this thesis, this phenomenon will be explored further as demonstrated by the introduction of DeepSeek due to its unique development methodology which is distinct by its economic drive. However, apart from such economic influences, these models also have the potential to be of substantial benefit to education, especially in areas that have traditionally faced challenges, such as for students with diverse needs. Two such cases will be considered here, being Dyslexia and ADHD.

1.2.5 DYSLEXIA AND ADHD SURVEY

Transformation of text from any domain into one that is specifically adapted for neurodivergence, specifically Dyslexia and/or ADHD, has not been addressed by any of the above TBMs. It also does not appear in any of the AI literature (and specifically TBM literature), with one exception, which will be discussed later in this section.

BIONIC READING©

Surprisingly, the dominant and most commercially successful approach to face these conditions is a method termed Bionic Reading© (Casutt, n.d.), which is based on a typographical algorithm undisclosed by its creator. It is widely available commercially in apps and other formats, in a highly customisable form. It is not based on any AI

model as far as known, but in this study, it will be invoked alongside some models the research intends to explore.

The concept of Bionic Reading©, introduced by Swiss typographic designer Renato, is a method that aims to enhance reading efficiency by bolding the initial letters of words, creating fixation points that guide the reader's eyes and allow the brain to complete the word. This potentially facilitates faster and more focused reading. The key features of this method are:

- Cognitive Bias – Bionic Reading© leverages the brain's ability to recognise words from their initial letters, reducing the need to process each letter individually
- Customisation – the method can be tailored to individual preferences, adjusting the number of letters bolded and the intensity of the emphasis
- Accessibility Potential – while not specifically designed for accessibility, some users with Dyslexia or ADHD have reported that Bionic Reading© helps them focus and comprehend text more effectively
- Digital Implementation – Bionic Reading© is available through various digital platforms, including apps and browser extensions, allowing users to apply the technique to different types of digital content

There are contrasting opinions about Bionic Reading©. Having researched this method and the condition, as well as having first-hand experience with young persons with Dyslexia and ADHD, the customisation feature poses concerns. It indicates a weakness in the claim that this method leverages cognitive bias if it cannot be predetermined by the algorithm itself. It is challenging to expect individuals with Dyslexia or ADHD to accurately assess the effectiveness of this method or determine the optimal number and positioning of emphasised letters within words of varying lengths to maximise its benefits. This seems to be a serious flaw in the principles of this method, potentially creating more confusion than it would solve.

In the supporting experiments discussed below, one needs to verify the controlling factors, such as pre-deciding on the length and location of the boldened letters by whoever is conducting the experiment and perhaps adjusting this accordingly until positive results were reported, an idea that will be revisited with this in mind and reported on later in this thesis.

The introduction of Bionic Reading© has sparked interest and debate. Some users report improved reading speed and comprehension, while others find the boldened text distracting. Critics point out the lack of extensive scientific research validating its effectiveness, and caution against relying solely on this method, especially for developing readers who benefit from traditional reading practices.

In summary, Bionic Reading© presents an innovative approach to reading by emphasising key parts of words to guide the reader's focus. While it may offer benefits for some individuals, particularly in digital reading contexts, further research is needed to fully understand its efficacy and implications for different reader populations.

BIONIC READING© IN OTHER LANGUAGES

As this is a closed model, no technical information is available. Additionally, even if Bionic Reading© proved to be useful in Latin-script alphabetic languages like English and French, it remains challenging to determine that this benefit can extend to other languages like Arabic and Japanese which do not follow this form of writing. Such benefits may be limited at best or does not exist at all.

For instance, the definite article in Arabic often becomes part of the word, as in the English phrase “The bird”, where the two distinct words become one “الطير”. Applying Bionic Reading© to the Arabic word by only boldening the first part to make it “الطير”, renders the Arabic word almost unreadable since only the definite article is boldened, thus, in English, it would appear as “**The** bird”.

To expand the subject of Dyslexia and ADHD in non-Latin script languages, and since the researcher is an Arabic speaker, the Arabic language was an obvious choice for investigation and could be used as a model for other non-Latin script languages.

Dyslexia in Arabic reading can present differently from Dyslexia in Latin-script languages like English, due to the structure of Arabic script and its reliance on short vowels (diacritics), root-based morphology, and letter connectivity. Here is an example to illustrate how a person with Dyslexia might struggle with reading Arabic:

Original Arabic sentence:

الولدُ يذهبُ إلى المدرسةِ

(Al-waladu yadhhabu ila al-madrasa)

Possible dyslexic reading:

الولدُ يحبُ إلى المدرسةِ

(confusing “goes” with “loves”, due to visual or phonological similarity)

الولدُ يذبه إلى المدرسةِ

(letter confusion between ذ and ه due to similar shapes)

الولد يذ... (يذهب on stuttering)

(difficulty decoding unfamiliar or morphologically complex verbs)

الولدُ يذهبُ إلا المدرسةِ

(confusing إلى with إلا, a common mistake due to visual similarity and frequent usage)

الولدُ يذهبُ إلى المدرصةِ

(inserting or misreading a letter, e.g., turning مدرسة into مدرصة)

These mistakes can result from:

- Difficulty distinguishing similar-looking letters (e.g. ت، ث; ص، ض; ع، غ)
- Challenges with vowel diacritics (which are essential for correct pronunciation and meaning)
- Issues with right-to-left directionality
- Morphological complexity (e.g. root-pattern system)

Dyslexia in Arabic reading and writing is a particularly complex issue for the reasons mentioned above, as it could be in similar semitic languages such as Hebrew and perhaps other languages around the globe.

For ADHD currently, as previously detailed, the official Bionic Reading© method is designed exclusively for languages that use the Latin alphabet, such as English and German. It does not support Arabic, and there are no immediate plans to extend support to non-Latin scripts.

The thinking behind any such endeavour should be the generalisation of the potential benefit of such a system, if any. Therefore, a model based loosely on this system is developed here for Arabic writing. However, there have been independent efforts to adapt the Bionic Reading© concept for Arabic readers:

- Freelance Projects – some developers have created tools that transform Arabic text into a Bionic Reading©-like format, aiming to assist individuals with Dyslexia or other reading difficulties
- Community Initiatives – platforms like Instagram have featured posts from groups such as *neurodivergentmuslims*, offering Bionic Reading© -style adaptations of Arabic texts, including religious content like the Quran.

These adaptations are not officially affiliated with Bionic Reading© and may vary in effectiveness. In this research, the concept of extending this style to Arabic writing seems to be a good pilot for introducing this practice to other non-European languages.

FIGURE 2: 10015.IO ARABIC TRANSFORMATION

An example of this is the above output from the initiative called 10015.io (Prototypr, n.d.)(Fig. 2). This is an online toolbox offering a wide array of free utilities across various categories, including text, image, coding, colour, and social media tools, including a version of Bionic Reading©. The input transformation yielded a very distorted Arabic text as if it was processed manually without any control behind it.

As with most investigation in this work, a prompt was presented to ChatGPT to determine whether a similar simple task could be attained successfully as a starting point of building a more robust and flexible model. The encouraging result of that is illustrated below (Fig. 3).

FIGURE 3: CHATGPT ARABIC TRANSFORMATION

CUSTOM ARABIC TRANSFORMATION MODEL

Following this, such a model was developed harnessing the capabilities of some of the existing transformers from the various libraries mentioned previously.

As stated, the Bionic Reading© method highlights the first few letters or syllables of each word to guide the reader's eyes and improve reading speed and

comprehension. For Arabic, the same concept can be adapted, though with awareness of word structure and semantics. The rules applied to the trial Arabic sentence were as follows:

1. Highlight the beginning of each word, usually the first one or two letters, depending on the word's length and morphology.
2. For words starting with definite articles like "ال", the article is included in the emphasis since it is semantically attached, to avoid the breaking of the word as in the example above, which was simply generated by forcing the bolding of the first two letters of the word.
3. Short function words like "في" were fully emphasised due to their brevity.

Below is the Python code to do that for the following Arabic sentence :

السمسرات يتوقفن في الحارات الغير مملوءة بالأرجل

For clarity and to capture the bolding of the letters, the output was generated in a Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) and regenerated below as an image.

```
from camel_tools.tokenizers.word import simple_word_tokenize
def emphasize_start(word):
    if word.startswith("ال") and len(word) > 3:
        prefix = word[:3]
        rest = word[3:]
    elif len(word) > 2:
        prefix = word[:2]
        rest = word[2:]
    else:
        return word
    return f'<span dir="rtl"><span style="font-weight:bold;">{prefix}</span>{rest}</span>'
def bionic_reading_arabic(sentence):
    words = simple_word_tokenize(sentence)
    emphasized_words = [emphasize_start(word) for word in words]
    return ' '.join(emphasized_words)
# Your sentence
sentence = "السمسرات يتوقفن في الحارات الغير مملوءة بالأرجل"
output = bionic_reading_arabic(sentence)
# HTML output
```

```

html_content = f"""<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="ar" dir="rtl">
<head>
<meta charset="UTF-8">
<title>Bionic Arabic</title>
<style>
  body {{
    font-family: 'Segoe UI', 'Arial', 'Tahoma', sans-serif;
    font-size: 24px;
    direction: rtl;
    text-align: right;
  }}
</style>
</head>
<body>{output}</body>
</html>
with open("output.html", "w", encoding="utf-8") as f:
    f.write(html_content)
print("✅ Output written to output.html")

```

The output from this transformation (Fig. 4):

FIGURE 4: PYTHON ARABIC TRANSFORMATION

The above text was chosen purposefully to illustrate the transformation in a long sentence to highlight where the bolding takes place.

Without further refinement and thoughtful design, it is not clear that the effect of Bionic Reading®, in this instance, differs significantly from the original text. Nevertheless, this exercise primarily aims to explore its potential for generalisation across other languages.

BIONIC READING® IN EXPERIMENTS

From the last point made, there may be another area of research opportunity to find what assistive developments may be beneficial for other languages, such as in the example of Arabic speaking people with Dyslexia.

Summarising the paper entitled “No, Bionic Reading© does not work” (Snell, 2024), one of many sceptical pieces of literature written on this theme, it states:

“Bionic Reading© might facilitate reading by guiding the eyes to optimal locations within words, but on the other hand, it may be detrimental because it may force a considerable number of unnecessary fixations on words that would otherwise be skipped. Also, Bionic Reading© may impair word recognition because of the visual inconsistencies within words that are applied without consideration for syllable or morpheme boundaries” (pp.2-3).

It concludes that an empirical test of the method's efficacy is indicated.

The paper entitled “Improving the Reading Comprehension of Senior High School Students through Bionic Reading” (Santos, n.d.) investigates the effectiveness of Bionic Reading© as an intervention to enhance reading comprehension among Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students. The study employed one-group pre-test-post-test experimental design, involving 75 students identified at the frustration level in reading comprehension, selected through non-probability purposive sampling. The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) served as the assessment tool, validated by experts. Data analysis, conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics, incorporated descriptive statistics and the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test.

The authors believe and state their confidence in the effectiveness of Bionic Reading© without submitting any evidence, which may indicate some bias in the design of their experiment, if not in the evaluation. Amongst its findings was a significant improvement in students’ reading comprehension levels, with a majority progressing from the frustration level to the instructional level. Their conclusion, therefore, was a very positive review for this system as a pedagogical tool for enhancing reading comprehension skills among senior high school students, particularly those initially at the frustration level. The implementation led to measurable improvements, highlighting its potential as an innovative approach in educational settings.

Another approach was taken by Higasa, et al. (2023), advocating that language learners should regularly engage in reading challenging materials as part of their study routine. For that, the paper presents a novel approach named the ‘Gaze-driven sentence simplification-system’, designed to enhance reading comprehension while maintaining the learner’s focus on the content. When the

system identifies comprehension difficulties, it provides simplified versions by replacing complex vocabulary and grammar with simpler alternatives via GPT-3.5.

An experiment was conducted with 19 English learners, collecting data on their eye movements while reading English text. The results demonstrated that this system is capable of accurately estimating sentence-level comprehension and found that GPT-3.5 simplification improved readability in terms of traditional readability metrics and individual word difficulty, paraphrasing across different linguistic levels. Therefore, this approach could be considered an AI driven reading aid for individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD, hence its inclusion in this survey.

The work of Kamarozaman, et al. (2023) is the most relevant and daring attempt at creating an AI tool to help Dyslexia and ADHD readability, as it leverages T5 and combines that with bolding techniques borrowed from Bionic Reading©.

It claims that Bionic Reading© is proven as an effective tool for helping but provides no evidence or scientific background for this claim. It also claims that their tool of combining the two techniques produced positive results from an experiment with ADHD students, but no details or statistical analysis were provided. It is also unclear which specific principle or configuration of Bionic Reading© was implemented in this case. The authors admit that the tool may not be as good at transforming complex technical material.

In a pilot model developed in this project, the researcher had independently followed this approach leveraging a YAM technique to simplify complex input. When some features of Bionic Reading© are used, this model specified certain parts of words in the text to be boldened according to a predetermined rule. This being only one of a few, if not the only research carried out leveraging a transformer and combining it with another technique, demonstrates the poor attention given to this subject, and indicates a wide-open field for future research.

On the subject of Dyslexia specifically, Zhao, et al. (2025) point out that this condition affects 12% of the global population (other sources put this figure as high as 15-20%), and that it presents significant challenges to reading ability and quality of life. Their research introduces the concept of Let AI Read it First (LARF) and find it helpful with participants with reading difficulties in the experiment conducted. They additionally realise the cost and inconvenience of other methods like text to speech,

and also that the change in the text might create distortion. This is why a simple HTML conversion could also borrow from the Bionic Reading© system. The experiment in this research is well reported. Nonetheless, in the opinion of this researcher, this system also failed to recognise the full potential of the utilisation of YAM.

1.2.6 METHODOLOGIES AND METRICS

With the aim of ascertaining the best approach to evaluating TBMs once a research design is selected for this study, the remaining part of this survey considers the research methodology and methods involved in the evaluation studies referred to above.

Researchers have two overarching approaches to their research: pure or applied/practical. Once an approach is selected, a research methodology needs to be considered to suit the overall approach. These are quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methodology. A qualitative study may include experimental trials, empirical measurement, or statistical analysis of the result of the work, but it is based on a specialist's criteria and/or interpreted accordingly. Applied research in general tends to take the quantitative route, or apply a mixed methodology, since there will be some practical testing and trials to be conducted to reach results.

The intended research here would be an applied one, as evaluating TBMs would involve designing and running test trials, which need to be measured. Therefore, a quantitative methodology was initially planned. However, after designing the main trials in this research, it became clear that some considerable input from multi-disciplinary experts would be needed to provide the golden standard (which is by nature a human explanation) as one of the parameters against which an outcome from a TBM is measured.

The intended comparative and evaluative work was initially to be conducted using SARI (Systematic Analysis of Reductions and Insertions), introduced by Xu, et al. (2016), which is a metric that can be used to evaluate text simplification models provided by the Hugging Face Transformers library (Hugging Face Diffusers, n.d.). Hugging Face is a platform which offers an extensive number of transformer models that users can explore and deploy directly, or finetune for specific applications. The SARI score measures how well a model simplifies a sentence while preserving its

meaning. It works by comparing the model's output with the original sentence, using multiple human-written simplifications to check if the output aligns with what a person would consider good simplifications. A higher SARI score indicates a better simplification. The score ranges from 0 to 100, with human-level simplifications typically scoring above 40. Below is an example from Python to demonstrate how SARI is calculated for evaluating a simplified sentence:

```
# Example sentences
original_sentences = ["The boy is playing in the park."]
simplified_sentences = ["The child plays in the park."]
reference_simplifications = [{"The kid is playing in the park.", "The
child is in the park."}]
# Compute SARI score
sari_score = corpus_sari(orig_sents=original_sentences,
                        sys_sents=simplified_sentences,
                        refs_sents=reference_simplifications)
print("SARI Score:", sari_score)
```

As will be seen in the next section, since only the output from TBMs will be measured against a golden standard, SARI was ruled out as a suitable metric for this research. Subsequently, a long exercise was embarked on to identify a more suitable metric tool for evaluating the TBMs and their output in these trials. The selection of such a tool would be BERT-based (Bidirectional Encoder Representations) developed by Google (Devlin, et al., 2018) that excels at Natural Language Understanding (NLU) by processing text in a bidirectional manner. Unlike earlier models that read text sequentially (left-to-right or right-to-left), BERT reads the entire context at once, making it highly effective for many NLP tasks.

The first model evaluated was Cross-Encoder (Reimers, n.d.), which is a TBM used for comparing two text sequences by jointly encoding them into a single representation, unlike Bi-Encoders, which encode each input separately. The following example demonstrates invoking Cross-Encoder in Python:

```
from sentence_transformers import CrossEncoder
# Load a pre-trained Cross-Encoder model
model = CrossEncoder('cross-encoder/stsb-roberta-large')
# Define sentence pairs
sentence_pairs = [
```

```
    ("The cat is on the rug.", " The cat is on the rug.", " ),  
    ("It is raining outside.", ""),  
]  
# Compute similarity scores  
scores = model.predict(sentence_pairs)  
print(scores) # Higher score = More similar
```

The researcher altered the code, in order to get the two extreme results of 1 (in the first case where the two strings compared were identical), and 0 (in the second case where the second string was empty). Instead, when the above code is executed, the results were [0.9656447 0.07573838], while the result expected was 1 for the first of the two pairs of sentences, and a maximum of approximately 0.3 for the second pair. Possible reasons some metric models return 0.3 for an empty string, could be:

- Some models have a default similarity baseline, which is the minimum similarity score they can give that is not zero (several of the models tested here gave results of approximately 0.3, as this model). For many models, even an empty string is normalised and mapped to a default vector other than a zero vector, hence the result of the cosine similarity (the mathematical measure of similarity) (Tan, et al., 2019) will not be zero.
- The non-zero value could also be a result of a bias in the training dataset, or the presence of some special non-visible characters in a string that causes the positive result.

In this research trial, the empty text scenario will never materialise due to the nature of the test dataset, which will always have texts. The exercise above, as well as in the example below, serves only to establish a base and aid the selection of the most appropriate method of scoring similarities.

It is worth keeping in mind that all models, without highly finetuning them, would indeed be bound by their training datasets and may not be as accurate as one expects. For this reason, the researcher has conducted the following exercise, one with the same model as above, using the same code with the exact sentence in the first instance, and an empty string in the second. The exercise was then repeated using a bi-encoder which directly compares the two inputs and encodes each sentence separately before computing similarity. This model scored 1 when the two

compared sentences were identical as seen in the Python code below, and 0.3898 cosine similarity when the second sentence was just an empty string. The latter scoring, where zero was expected, is explained above.

```
import torch
from transformers import BertTokenizer, BertModel
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity
# Load pre-trained BERT model and tokenizer
tokenizer = BertTokenizer.from_pretrained('bert-base-uncased')
model = BertModel.from_pretrained('bert-base-uncased')
def encode_text(text):
    """
    Encodes a given text using BERT to obtain a fixed-length vector.
    """
    # Tokenize the input text
    inputs = tokenizer(text, return_tensors='pt', truncation=True,
padding=True, max_length=512)
    # Get the model's output
    with torch.no_grad():
        outputs = model(**inputs)
    # Use the [CLS] token embedding as the sentence representation
    # outputs[0] is the last hidden state of the model, we take the
    first token's embedding (CLS token)
    sentence_embedding = outputs.last_hidden_state[:, 0, :].squeeze()
    return sentence_embedding
def compute_similarity(text1, text2):
    """
    Computes cosine similarity between the embeddings of two texts.
    """
    # Encode both texts
    embedding1 = encode_text(text1)
    embedding2 = encode_text(text2)
    # Compute cosine similarity
    similarity = cosine_similarity(embedding1.unsqueeze(0),
embedding2.unsqueeze(0))[0][0]
    return similarity
# Example texts
text1 = "Paris is the capital city of France."
text2 = "Paris is the capital city of France."
# Compute similarity
similarity = compute_similarity(text1, text2)
```

```
print(f"Cosine similarity between the two texts: {similarity:.4f}")
```

For the above explained reasons, the researcher believed that choosing the latter model for the trials to be carried out here would be more appropriate, since it is likely that completely different syntactical presentations would be seen between the various models in the trial. As long as they have a similar contextual meaning, they would be deemed of a high level of transformation accuracy.

COSINE SIMILARITY

As the cosine similarity was mentioned several times above, its principle and role in the research of domain-domain transformation might require further explanation:

The concept of cosine is a mathematical term representing a ratio from trigonometry, which has been adopted in the field of data science to determine how similar two non-zero vectors are in an inner product space. Vectors are entities that not only have magnitude but also a direction, determined by a particular angle from a base line.

The cosine similarity is commonly used in text analysis, recommendation systems, and machine learning, to compare documents, sentences, or feature vectors. It measures the cosine of the angle between two vectors. Given two vectors A and B, their cosine similarity is computed as:

$$\cos(\theta) = (\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}) / (||\mathbf{A}|| ||\mathbf{B}||)$$

Where:

- $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ is the dot product of vectors A and B.
- $||\mathbf{A}||$ is the Euclidean norm (magnitude) of vector A.
- $||\mathbf{B}||$ is the Euclidean norm of vector B.
- θ is the angle between the two vectors.

The value range of the cosine similarity is from -1 to 1, where -1 is when the two vectors have opposite directions, 0 is when they are completely different, and 1 is when the vectors are identical, i.e. point in the same direction but not necessarily

have the same value(s), unlike their Euclidian equivalent. This is the reason why cosine similarity is used in NLP where absolute magnitude such as word frequencies may vary significantly.

In practice, with many AI metric models used for evaluating sentences, even if one string is empty, they measure a constant vector as default, and they produce a similarity of a fixed value, such as 0.3. The following computation example will illustrate how the cosine similarity is calculated:

Take two vectors, A and B to be $A = (1, 2, 3)$, and $B = (4, 5, 6)$, then the dot product will yield

$$A \cdot B = (1 \times 4) + (2 \times 5) + (3 \times 6) = 4 + 10 + 18 = 32$$

To calculate the magnitude

$$\|A\| = \sqrt{(1^2 + 2^2 + 3^2)} = \sqrt{(1 + 4 + 9)} = \sqrt{14}$$

$$\|B\| = \sqrt{(4^2 + 5^2 + 6^2)} = \sqrt{(16 + 25 + 36)} = \sqrt{77}$$

\therefore the cosine similarity would be

$$\cos(\theta) = 32 / (\sqrt{14} \times \sqrt{77}) \approx 0.97$$

This indicates that the two vectors are very similar, as the result is very close to 1 (one might think of these two vectors as two points in three-dimensional space with similar, but not necessarily the same, coordinates).

In NLP, since words are not naturally numerical, one needs a way to represent them as vectors to accurately compute their cosine similarity. Words could be similar to the vectors in the example above where each coordinate is assigned to some characteristic of the word by any number of encoding methods. Once words or sentences are converted into vectors, the cosine value can indicate their similarity according to the formula above.

This technique is crucial for evaluating TBMs for domain-domain transformation, Dyslexia correction, and error recovery. For instance, if a model transforms “melody” into “harmonic sequence,” the cosine similarity can help measure how semantically accurate the transformation is.

1.3 SURVEY OF DYSLEXIA AND ADHD DATASETS AND MODELS

Building an entire dataset for AI training in the features of the two conditions of neurodivergence would require considerable resources. It was therefore necessary, as an extension of the review of academic literature of TBMs, to continue exploring various platforms in search of pretrained Dyslexia and ADHD models and datasets. The findings are discussed below.

1.3.1 PRETRAINED DYSLEXIA CORRECTION MODELS

There are few potential sources for pretrained models and tools to aid Dyslexia correction. In the vast library of Hugging Face of nearly 1.6 million models, there are only six models found with reference to Dyslexia. As the object of this survey is to study such models, a detailed description of these will follow, based on the discussion above about the criteria for judging the effectiveness of models in aiding readability and comprehension for individuals with Dyslexia.

The first two models are *ghadaaa/sdxl_finetuned_dyslexia* and *ghadaaa/gen_images*. These two models, found in the Hugging Face library under 'Models', were developed by the user known as "ghadaaa". They are a finetuned version of the Stable Diffusion XL (SDXL) model (Hugging Face Diffusers., 2025), which is a visual aid model, tailored to generate images associated with Dyslexia.

The finetuning is likely to have involved techniques such as DreamBooth (Ruiz, et al., 2022) being a finetuning technique originally developed by Google to personalise image generation, and Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA), a technique to adapt the model's output to specific themes or concepts related to Dyslexia. Using DreamBooth for finetuning these models helps them learn new concepts or styles (like a specific person, object, or idea) by providing it with a few images.

Finally, both models have 'AutoTrain' as one of their components, which is an internal model of the Hugging Face platform that serves to simplify the transformation process of training without requiring significant human interference.

Despite their visual approach, these models could be incorporated in a dyslexia-focused AI model for text transformation, which is useful in generating visual aids, where necessary, to aid comprehension of difficult concepts.

The third model on this list is *asmaemou/detecting_dyslexia*. There was no model card associated with this model and therefore there is no documentation and subsequently no information about its function and architecture. For the sake of completeness, it is included in this survey.

The fourth model on the list is *asmaemou/research-dyslexia*. The author in this case, incidentally the same author of the third model, Asmae Mouradi, given above as *asmaemou*, has given only a brief description on the model's card of the function of this model:

"This is my first trial. Hello, I am Asmae Mouradi. This model is trained to classify handwriting images related to Dyslexia using an OmniVec-like architecture."

It can be concluded that the model's purpose is to classify handwriting images. Its goal is to detect or categorise patterns that are associated with Dyslexia. This could be beneficial in early detection or educational support for individuals with Dyslexia.

As stated above, the model uses 'OmniVec-like' architecture. This probably refers to a vision-based neural network, possibly inspired by multi-modal or transformer-based designs like OmniNet (Tay, et al., 2021). It likely includes visual feature extraction components suited for handwriting analysis.

Since this is the first version or an early experiment, it is not a final or fully tested model yet, thus its performance might still be under evaluation. For this reason, and other unknown items about this model, such as the dataset used for training or the requirements for its input image, amongst others, it is not possible to ascertain the value of this model and its contribution to this field of research.

The fifth model *Neurodiverse/dyslexia-reading-assistant*, was still undergoing testing at the time of this research, and as such no information was available.

The final model is *IAyamina/IBM_hackathonIA_granite_finetuned_dyslexia*. Once more, apart from Dyslexia in the naming of the model, no other information was found about its purpose and architecture. This limits any judgement or evaluation of this model for the purpose of this study.

In conclusion, since only a few models related to Dyslexia could be found in the largest depository of AI models, the further focused research and development of Dyslexia models is imperative.

1.3.2 DYSLEXIA DATASETS

There are existing datasets that list and classify common errors made by individuals with Dyslexia. Some of these datasets available outside Hugging Face library are:

- Dyslexic Sight Words (DSW) (Kishan, 2024)
- DysList (Rello, et al., 2014)
- ispravi.me (Šojat & Kovačić, 2023)

These datasets have been extensively studied for general spelling correction across various languages, and the respective studies provide insights that could be relevant to addressing dyslexic spelling errors. However, in this survey, the focus is centred on the Hugging Face library due to its relevance to the development of TBMs in terms of their availability, accessibility, and nature. This makes their models readily useable by developers of TBMs, unlike the datasets mentioned above which may only be available commercially, or at least, only with authorisation from their creators. They may not be easily accessible or formatted in a way to facilitate the development of TBMs, and they may not be possible to use without preprocessing which may involve a great deal of resources.

It is worth exploring this point further, since it may create an obstacle in the development of specialised TBMs for neurodivergence such as Dyslexia, and perhaps to highlight to researchers and developers in the future, the need to establish more accessible datasets. Additionally, once fully accessed and paid for, they could be made available for other developers to advance this field of research and development, possibly with sponsorship from organisations concerned with the welfare of individuals with such neurodivergence.

A further reason for expanding this discussion, is to highlight the limitations, constraints, and efforts that might be needed, to adapt these datasets for the purpose of developing easily accessible TBMs. As alluded to above, many datasets related to Dyslexia, such as DSW, DysList, or tools like ispravi.me, often present

access and usage limitations, which can make working with them challenging for research or development. To sum up these constraints and difficulties:

1. Commercial Availability

Many specialised datasets are only commercially available or may be restricted to authorised users.

- They are not freely available in public domains like open research platforms.
- One may need to purchase access or request permission from the dataset creators (e.g. institutions, research groups).
- Commercial datasets are usually curated for specific use cases, and the terms of use may include restrictions on redistribution or modification.

2. Access Through Authorisation

Some datasets require explicit authorisation or collaboration with the dataset creators before one can access them, for example:

- Institutional permissions – if a dataset was collected through a university or research project, one might need approval to use it for own research or development.
- Data privacy concerns – in some cases of safeguarding or data protection, creators may limit access to protect participants' privacy. This is usually the case with datasets that involve vulnerable populations (such as individuals with Dyslexia, children, or those with disabilities) as in this case, where additional ethical considerations apply.

3. Preprocessing Requirements

Even if a dataset is accessible, it often requires preprocessing to be usable for the specific task a TBM is to be designed for and developed. Some of the challenges here include:

- Formatting issues – many datasets are not in the format required by TBMs or Deep Learning (DL) frameworks, e.g. text could be in raw Comma Separated Values (CSV) files, or Portable Document Format (PDF) scans, instead of tokenised text. To explain further, 'tokenised' refers to breaking words into smaller items (tokens) to facilitate processing and finetuning.

- Missing labels or incomplete data – datasets may need to be cleaned and annotated, which could require a lot of time or effort, particularly if they are inconsistent or incomplete.
- Large dataset sizes – premanufactured datasets tend to be too large for the purpose of developing TBMs, which would require significant computational power to preprocess and train the models.

4. Alternative datasets

In order to avoid the issues of accessing and preprocessing commercial datasets, developers can mitigate this by a number of ways. Hence, in this study, Hugging Face library features heavily since it is considered the best open access source of materials (models, datasets and apps). There are other alternatives, but open access locations like these listed below are the first and preferred method.

- Open Access Datasets – while datasets specific to Dyslexia might be limited, there are general-purpose text simplification datasets or handwriting datasets available publicly, which can be adapted to the task with some preprocessing.
- Synthetic Data – often real datasets are hard to come by, one can consider generating synthetic datasets, for instance, by simulating dyslexic patterns or some other variation of that.
- Crowdsourcing – Polific (Kiros, et al., 2022), which is a public dataset of political figures' communications used for NLP tasks like stance detection, ideology classification, or political discourse analysis, as well as Amazon Mechanical Turk, which is a platform where researchers, companies, and developers can outsource tasks to a large pool of human workers, called *Turkers*, to complete small, time-consuming tasks (called HITs or Human Intelligence Tasks) for a fee. These are two examples of crowdsourcing platforms for labelling or creating datasets, which could be utilised for gathering data or performing annotations.
- Collaborations – this could be considered by exchanging knowledge or benefits with the authors of the datasets for potential collaboration, or to obtain access. Many are open to collaborations when it aligns with their own work.

To summarise, datasets like DSW, DysList, and ispravi.me may not be freely available and could require authorisation or collaboration to access. Additionally, preprocessing may be needed, and it can require substantial effort to convert the data into a usable form for TBMs development. Furthermore, commercial datasets or those with specific access restrictions can slow down development, but alternatives (like synthetic data or crowdsourcing) may help overcome some limitations.

In contrast to the above, using Hugging Face datasets has several advantages, especially when working with machine learning models, particularly TBMs. The main reasons why it is often better to use Hugging Face datasets are as follows:

1. Preprocessing and Tokenisation

- Hugging Face datasets are typically formatted and pre-processed to work directly with its own TBMs without the need for cleaning, tokenising, or structuring data.
- Hugging Face provides tokenisers that are tightly integrated with their models. This ensures that the input data is converted into a suitable format for training and inference without having to manually handle the tokenisation process.

2. Variety and Quality

- A massive library of datasets across multiple domains of text, images, speech, and more is hosted by Hugging Face ready to be used, amongst which there are datasets specifically designed for NLP, computer vision, and other domains, making it easier to find a dataset suited for a specific task.
- The datasets on Hugging Face are often curated and quality-checked, which reduces the risk of using messy, incomplete, or unstructured data.

3. Integration with Transformers

The datasets on Hugging Face are designed to integrate seamlessly with the TBMs, making it easy to download and train models without additional steps. In addition, this integration allows models from Hugging Face's Model Hub to be used, which have already been finetuned on popular datasets. Furthermore, Hugging Face datasets provide confidence and assurance that the data will work well with the pretrained models, as they are designed to match the models' input requirements.

4. Ease of Use

Hugging Face makes it simple to access datasets using just a few lines of code. For instance, one can easily load datasets with the datasets library, which handles the downloading, caching, and preparation automatically. An example of Python code to load the films dataset IMDB can be achieved by these two simple lines of code:

```
from datasets import load_dataset
dataset = load_dataset("imdb")
```

Datasets imported from Hugging Face are typically standardised, meaning the structure (e.g. columns, format) is consistent. This makes it easier to train models, as one does not have to be concerned about variations in how data is structured.

5. Performance Efficiency

Hugging Face datasets are optimised for performance, allowing for loading large datasets in a memory-efficient way. They support streaming, which allows loading data directly from the disk without consuming too much memory, even when working with very large datasets. In addition, for more efficiency, one can apply preprocessing steps like filtering, shuffling, and mapping functions without having to manually code these operations. This speeds up the entire data pipeline. A pipeline in AI development is a structured sequence of steps used to process data, train models, and deploy AI systems.

6. Documentation

Hugging Face provides excellent documentation for both datasets and models. This includes tutorials, guides, and examples to help getting started with the datasets quickly, as well as understanding how to preprocess and finetune them for a specific use case.

7. Large Language Models' Comparison

As it is always necessary to search for the optimal fit for any research or application (such as the aim of this research project to provide a comparison), Hugging Face provides such a search facility on its Leaderboard page (Fig. 5).

FIGURE 5: HUGGING FACE LEADERBOARD

All current models in the library are listed according to their popularity. Although ranked in descending order by their Average score, for each model a number of other metrics are also listed (Fig. 6), including their CO₂ cost as the last feature. The other metrics indicate to the researcher the area(s) that the particular model excel at despite its popularity rating.

FIGURE 6: HUGGING FACE MODEL METRICS

To summarise the features and advantages of using Hugging Face datasets – they are easy to access and preprocess, come preformatted for use with TBMs, and they are of high quality, consistent, and widely used in the AI community. They also provide a large variety of datasets across multiple domains, integrate well with Hugging Face models, and reduce the development cycle.

1.3.3 DYSLEXIA DATASETS ON HUGGING FACE

Amongst some 360,000 datasets available in the Hugging Face library, only four were found with a reference to Dyslexia:

1. gpric024/wmt14_injected_synthetic_dyslexia

This is the first dataset on the list according to appearance on Hugging Face. It was created to test the capabilities of State Of The Art (SOTA) machine translation models on dyslexic style text. It is a modified version of an earlier version which is based on an English test set. As the name indicates, it is a synthetic Dyslexia dataset and was designed for research related to machine translation and how it handles text with dyslexia-like errors. The objective is to evaluate how well state-of-the-art machine translation models perform when faced with text containing errors that are synthesised to look like those made by individuals with Dyslexia. Since obtaining large amounts of real-world dyslexic-text is very difficult, this dataset uses synthetic methods to inject common dyslexic-style errors into existing text.

It is based on the WMT14 (Bojar, et al., 2014) dataset, a standard benchmark for machine translation. This dataset includes text with synthetically injected errors, simulating common dyslexic-writing patterns with variations in spelling, homophones, and letter confusion. Its output contains translations from several LLM translation services, allowing for comparisons.

This dataset is useful for improving the robustness of machine translation systems, particularly for making them more accessible to individuals with Dyslexia. It helps to bring awareness to the challenges that people with Dyslexia face when utilising machine translation tools, which aligns with the purpose of this research.

2. Neurodiverse/dyslexia-simplified-text-dataset

This promisingly named dataset is simply a place holder for a future dataset, as it is currently empty.

3. Neurodiverse/dyslexia-handwriting-dataset

Just like its sister in 2 above, this dataset was found to be empty.

4. datasets-CNRS/dyslexiques_vs_lambda

This dataset originates from CNRS (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique), a French public research organisation. It contains audio recordings from three different speakers, each performing three tasks, one of which is narrating a comic strip.

It was designed for research involving speech analysis, potentially with a focus on comparing speech patterns. The "dyslexiques_vs_lambda" part of the name suggests a comparison between speech from individuals with Dyslexia and those without (the *lambda* in the name is likely a reference to a control group).

In conclusion of this section, it is evident that this field of research is in its infancy and there is a vast amount of work to be done for research and development in this area alone.

1.3.4 DYSLEXIA DATASETS ON GITHUB

GitHub (n.d.) is a website and platform where developers store, share, and collaborate on code. It is built around Git, a version control system that helps people track changes in code over time, work together on projects, and roll back to earlier versions if needed.

There is a limited number of Dyslexia datasets hosted by this platform, but as detailed below, they are of a neurological nature, which will not be useful for what this research aims to achieve. The datasets in question are:

1. Dyslexia Detection Using Handwriting Samples

This GitHub repository offers a machine learning-based application designed to predict the presence of Dyslexia from handwriting samples. It includes datasets of handwriting samples from both dyslexic and non-dyslexic individuals, along with extracted features and model training scripts.

2. Eye Tracking Dyslexia Detection

A project that focuses on detecting Dyslexia using eye-tracking data, analysed through unsupervised machine learning techniques. The repository contains the relevant dataset and implementation details.

3. Machine Learning

For predicting Dyslexia using machine learning. In this repository, this model provides a machine learning model that predicts Dyslexia risk levels (High, Moderate, Low), based on quiz scores assessing language, memory, speed, and visual and audio skills. It includes the dataset, and an interactive interface built with Streamlit (Streamlit Inc., 2023), an open-source Python library that makes it easy to build and share interactive, data-driven web applications.

4. Deep Learning

Detecting Dyslexia using deep learning. This repository contains code for replicating baseline models and conducting experiments related to detecting Dyslexia using deep learning techniques. It includes datasets and detailed implementation notebooks.

5. Dyslexia Prediction

This project predicts Dyslexia risk levels using a machine learning model with an interactive interface built in Streamlit. The dataset used in this project is sourced from Kaggle's Dyslexia Dataset.

1.3.5 DYSLEXIA DATASETS ON KAGGLE

Kaggle (n.d.) is a free online platform for data science and machine learning. It is similar to GitHub but specifically focuses on datasets, coding competitions, notebooks, and learning tools. The datasets found on this platform of interest are only for Dyslexia detection and testing, so they are once again not of great interest for this study, but are listed for inclusion nonetheless:

1. Predicting Risk of Dyslexia - PLOS ONE

This dataset accompanies the research paper *Predicting risk of dyslexia with an online gamified test* (Rello, et al., 2020), published in PLOS ONE. It includes data collected from an online game designed to assess Dyslexia risk.

2. Dyslexia Handwriting Dataset

This dataset contains handwriting samples categorised into normal, reversal, and corrected classes, totalling 78,275 normal, 52,196 reversal, and 8,029 corrected samples.

3. Dyslexia Datasets

A collection of datasets related to Dyslexia, including the Dyslexia Handwriting dataset and others, organised into directories for easy access.

4. DYSLEXIA(project)

This dataset is labelled *labelled_dysx.csv* and is intended for dyslexia-related projects, though specific details are limited.

5. Prediction of Dyslexia

Another dataset labelled *labelled_dysx.csv* aimed at facilitating Dyslexia prediction models.

In 4 and 5 above, both datasets are termed 'Labelled'. A labelled dataset is a collection of data where each piece of data (e.g. an image, text, or audio clip) is paired with a corresponding label that indicates the correct answer or category for that data. In machine learning, these labels are used as the *ground truth* during training to help a model learn to make predictions or classifications.

1.3.6 ADHD ON HUGGING FACE

As mentioned in the discussion of Dyslexia above, the best source for AI models is Hugging Face and therefore the rest of this survey will focus mainly on models and datasets pertaining to ADHD that are available in its library.

ADHD MODELS

On initial search for ADHD models, the picture looked more promising than what was encountered with Dyslexia models. From nearly 1.6 million models, there were 16 models with reference to ADHD. Unfortunately, 11 of these models' entries (model cards) provided no information at all. It is not certain why this is the case, but as mentioned above in the discussions of the Dyslexia datasets, one can only speculate that these models exist in private repositories or use commercial datasets. This

means that its contents are not publicly accessible, and no specific details about their nature or purpose are available. The remaining five models are listed below:

1. opeakinseloyin/my-awesome-ADHD-model

This refers to a specific machine learning model hosted on Hugging Face, and is based on the SetFit model (Tunstall, et al., 2022), designed for text classification. It is built upon sentence-transformers, utilising an efficient ‘few-shot’ learning technique, which means it is trained to categorise text, and can do so effectively with relatively small amounts of training data. Essentially, it is a specialised text classification model that leverages efficient machine learning techniques.

Classification involves the task of assigning text to predefined categories or labels to determine which category a text belongs to. For instance, determining whether a customer’s review is positive, negative, or neutral.

Reviewing this model, and, while the name of the model contains ADHD, without knowing the specific training data, the precise purpose of the classification remains unclear. It is possible that the model is designed to classify text relating to ADHD. However, since this research is only concerned with models that may be helpful to individuals with ADHD, this may not be of any value in this field.

2. huggingtweets/adhd_93

This is a project and model related to generating ‘tweets’, not specifically a model for classifying text related to ADHD. It is aimed at making AI accessible and demonstrating how to generate text in a specific style. Once again, this offers no demonstrable advantage in enhancing readability for individuals with ADHD.

3. Only-Mike/ADHD_Test_qa_model

This is a question-answering model related to ADHD; the name indicates that the model is specifically designed to answer questions related to ADHD. It does not offer any facility to aid in ADHD readability and therefore proving of little use here.

4. LinaTarasenko99/ADHD_Test_qa_model

Another question-answering model related to ADHD, as its predecessor in 3 above.

5. Phoshco/ADHDvsN

Similar to the model in 1 above, this model's purpose is to classify text, likely to determine whether a given piece of text is related to ADHD or not. Once more, it does not serve the purpose of this research.

ADHD DATASETS

In searching for ADHD datasets, one is likely to encounter various types of data, depending on the research focus. Below is a breakdown of the general types of ADHD datasets and how they relate to the type of research and model structure:

- **Neuroimaging Data:**

These datasets contain brain scans (MRI, fMRI) of individuals with and without ADHD. They are used to study structural and functional differences in the brains of people with ADHD.

- **Behavioural Data:**

These datasets may include information from psychological assessments, questionnaires, or behavioural observations. They often contain data on symptoms, cognitive performance, and other behavioural characteristics.

- **Textual Data:**

In the context of NLP, datasets might contain text from social media, medical records, or other sources, which are then analysed to identify patterns related to ADHD.

There were only six datasets with reference to ADHD amongst the 350,000 datasets in the Hugging Face library. This is an early indication of how this area of research is new at best, or worse being neglected, and hence it is a justification for why this research is necessary to bring to the front this important need for assistive AI for neurodivergence in adults and children of all ages. The relevant datasets are:

1. Rami/adhd_question

The dataset (Rami, n.d.) appears to contain questions related to ADHD. For example, one of the questions found was “Hi Dr Barkley, do you have any advice on how to explain ADHD, more specifically late diagnosis (40's) to friends”. This dataset would not be useful for building TBMs to aid individuals with ADHD.

2. MasaFoundation/huberman_lab_ADHD__How_Anyone_Can_Improve_Their_Focus

This dataset (MasaFoundation, n.d.) is possibly resourced from an episode of the Huberman Lab podcast that discusses ADHD and strategies for improving focus, or from its website. Dr. Huberman's podcast episodes often delve into the scientific mechanisms behind various aspects of brain function and provide actionable advice.

Since Hugging face is a platform commonly used for sharing datasets and machine learning models, it is therefore safe to assume its origin and perhaps could be a useful tool for building a TBM for helping individuals with ADHD.

3. 27Praveen/adhd-dataset

No specific details found on Hugging Face regarding this dataset but from a brief description, this is likely to contain text-based data. It appears that it is a private dataset, with restricted access as mentioned above in the general discussion of datasets. Therefore, its utility for building TBMs could be very limited, if any.

4. Therax/ADHD_data

This dataset comprises 30 text-based questions related to anxiety symptoms and experiences. These questions cover topics such as excessive worry, physical symptoms of anxiety, avoidance behaviours, concentration difficulties, and sleep disturbances. The dataset is relatively small, with a total size of approximately 2.49 kB. Given that the dataset consists of questions pertaining to anxiety rather than ADHD-specific data, its direct applicability to ADHD research or diagnostic tool development may be limited.

5. Peraboom/ADHD_Related_Concerns

This dataset is a compilation of user-generated content from discussions related to ADHD on Reddit (Reddit, n.d.), a social information platform. The dataset includes posts where individuals share their experiences, seek advice, and discuss concerns about ADHD. For instance, one post features a user expressing uncertainty about having ADHD, and other neurodivergences. It has been utilised in research focusing on the classification of ADHD-related concerns, and since it is mainly used for classification purposes, it would not be of interest to developers and researchers in this particular area.

6. MasaFoundation/huberman_lab_Adderall_Stimulants__Modafinil_for_ADHD_Short-__Long-Term_Effects

Just like the dataset in 2 above from the same foundation, this serves in giving advice to sufferers of ADHD but has no significant benefits for developers of TBMs.

1.3.7 ADHD MODELS AND DATASETS IN GITHUB

Several GitHub repositories focus on ADHD through various models and datasets. Below is a selection of notable projects:

1. Diagnosing-ADHD-With-ConvLSTM by deontaepharr

This project constructs a hybrid model combining Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks to analyse both spatial and temporal aspects of fMRI data for ADHD diagnosis.

2. HYPERAKTIV by simula

HYPERAKTIV is a public dataset containing health, activity, and heart rate data from 51 adult patients diagnosed with ADHD and 52 clinical controls.

3. ADHD-DNN by kmlstyle

This repository provides Python code for a deep neural network (DNN) designed to predict the onset of ADHD in children and adolescents. The model utilises 22 features and includes pretrained weights.

4. ADHD-Prediction-rsfMRI by lacomaofficial

This repository investigates the prediction of ADHD using resting-state functional magnetic resonance imaging (rs-fMRI) data. It employs machine learning techniques, specifically Support Vector Machines (SVMs), to differentiate individuals with ADHD from typically developing controls based on brain connectivity profiles.

5. adhd-detector by gariciodaro

This application aims to reproduce results from a master's thesis on resting EEG classification of children with ADHD. It includes trained classifiers and requires GSN HydroCel 128 + CZ EEG recordings to predict ADHD presence.

6. ADHD-Prediction by mkk-1817

This project employs machine learning techniques to predict ADHD in children. It utilises a dataset of 121 children aged 7 to 12 years, comprising 61 diagnosed with ADHD and 60 healthy controls. The methodology includes data preprocessing,

feature engineering, and evaluation of various algorithms such as logistic regression, naive Bayes, artificial neural networks, KMeans clustering, and decision trees.

7. ADHD Dataset by vimalajeewaruh

This dataset contains pupil diameter data collected from 50 children (28 cases and 22 controls) during a visuospatial working memory task. The data includes three groups: ADHD-diagnosed children with and without medication, and neurotypical children.

8. ecml-ADHD by aeye-lab

This project explores the detection of ADHD based on eye movements during natural viewing. It involves running experiments and preparing saliency maps using a state-of-the-art saliency model, DeepGazell (Kümmerer, et al., 2016).

9. ADHD Dataset by rahmarid

This dataset describes phenotypic information of 221 children with ADHD, including eight variables of interest.

10. ADHDDeepNet by AliAmini93

ADHDDeepNet integrates temporal and spatial characterisation, attention modules, and explainability techniques optimised for EEG data in ADHD diagnosis. It incorporates Neural Architecture Search (NAS), hyper-parameter optimisation, and data augmentation to enhance performance and accuracy.

11. FMRI_ADHD_Classification by ChristopherSims

This repository focuses on classifying ADHD from fMRI data using a 3D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN).

12. NLP_ADHD_PTBM by ybannett

This project leverages NLP and machine learning models to improve the measurement of quality-of-care offered to children with developmental and behavioural disorders, including ADHD.

13. AI-Driven Early Detection System by AFLucas-UOM

This repository contains Python scripts for detecting signs of Dyslexia and ADHD using AI and user activity monitoring.

14. ADHDsubtypes_project by brainhack-school2020

This project uses a multimodal dataset comprising EEG data, self-reported symptoms, and behavioural data to predict DSM (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) subtypes of 96 participants with ADHD.

1.3.8 ADHD MODELS AND DATASETS IN KAGGLE

Only three relevant items were found on this platform. These were:

1. ViT_ADHD_92.8%

This is a Kaggle project where a Vision Transformer (ViT) model achieved a performance metric of 92.8% in the context of ADHD detection or classification. Vision Transformers are deep learning models that have shown remarkable success in image analysis tasks. In medical imaging, they can be utilised to identify patterns associated with various conditions, including ADHD.

2. ECNN_ADHD_93%

This is an Enhanced Convolutional Neural Network (ECNN) model applied to ADHD detection, achieving a performance metric of 93%.

3. Knowledge Graph (KG) of ADHD with LLMs

This is the result of a network analysis on a comprehensive knowledge graph (KG) of ADHD, constructed by integrating scientific literature and clinical data with the help of cutting-edge large language models (LLMs), the aim of which is to understand the disorder.

1.4 COMPARATIVE LOOK AT EVALUATION METRICS

To review the evaluation metrics considered in this study, a short comparative look is necessary.

SARI is a special metric usually used to compare and contrast two parameters: original text, and a simplified one. Therefore, to use SARI, the original simplified text needs to be provided. In the case of the trials that follow, that does not apply since the comparison required for this work comes in three parts:

- Original text, untransformed, from one domain

- Transformed text using metaphors from another specified domain
- Golden standard provided by an expert or knowledgeable person in both domains

The main concern of SARI is the quality of simplification, while BERT-based models are concerned with the similarity of input and output texts and their semantic embeddings. It does that by generating a large number of vector values to use for comparison.

The cosine similarity is a formula based on a mathematical (specifically, geometrical) principle for vectors and calculates the proximity of the direction of each two vectors to decide their similarity. Therefore, it complements BERT-based models by taking the vectors generated by them and applying the formula of similarity to them. A summary of this comparison is seen in Table 1.

TABLE 1: EVALUATION METRIC COMPARISON

Metric	Function	Process	Strength	Weakness	Output Format
SARI	Simplification measure	Compares changes	Evaluation of simplifications	Requires original text	Scores 0-100
BERTScore	Semantics & similarity measure	Encodes and compares meaning	Meaning similarity evaluation	Likely to miss out some details	Scores -1 to 1, 1 being closest in meaning
Cosine Similarity	Vectors closeness measure	Measures cosine angle of two vectors	Comparing two numerical vectors' values	Only measures angles but not the vectors' quality	Scores -1 to 1, 1 being closest in direction

To illustrate this with an example, to input “The fox is jumping over the fence” simplified to “Fox jumping fence”, with a golden reference for SARI as “The fox jumps the fence”, the expected score would be:

- SARI ± 35 = Poor simplification due to too many word deletions
- BERTScore ± 0.70 = Sentences are close semantically but not precisely
- BERT-based Cosine Similarity ± 0.85 = Sentences are very close in meaning

Executing this through the following a Python code for verification:

```
from easse.sari import corpus_sari
from sentence_transformers import SentenceTransformer
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity
```

```

from bert_score import score
# Sentences
original = ["The fox is jumping the fence."]
simplified = ["Fox jumping fence."]
reference = ["The fox jumps the fence."] # Gold standard simplified
version
# 1. SARI
sari_score = corpus_sari(orig_sents=original, sys_sents=simplified,
refs_sents=[reference])
print(f"SARI score: {sari_score:.4f}")
# 2. BERT-based cosine similarity
model = SentenceTransformer('all-MiniLM-L6-v2')
original_emb = model.encode(original)
simplified_emb = model.encode(simplified)
cos_sim = cosine_similarity([original_emb[0]],
[simplified_emb[0]])[0][0]
print(f"BERT-based cosine similarity: {cos_sim:.4f}")
# 3. BERTScore (using reference vs system)
P, R, F1 = score(simplified, reference, lang="en", model_type="bert-
base-uncased")
print(f"BERTScore - Precision: {P.item():.4f}, Recall:
{R.item():.4f}, F1: {F1.item():.4f}")

```

The result:

```

SARI score: 35.0463
BERT-based cosine similarity: 0.8693
BERTScore - Precision: 0.6401, Recall: 0.5866, F1: 0.6122
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 %

```

Since the main goal of the trials that will be conducted in this study is to quickly assess overall similarity rather than deep contextual matching, and without the need for large computational power, Cosine Similarity will be used as the preferred metric, as explained fully in section 1.2 above.

The proposed research design, adopted methodology, and methods to be employed, will be discussed in the next chapter.

CHAPTER 2: METHODOLOGY AND METHODS

2.1 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This research focuses on the evaluation and application of Transformer-Based Models (TBMs) for domain-domain transformation. The work is based on Transformative Linguistic Modelling, built on the architecture of the Transformer (Vaswani, et al., 2017).

This framework treats language transformation as a mapping between parallel conceptual spaces. The concept of domain transformation treats domains, such as music education and neurology, as semiotic systems with distinct but partially overlapping structures. Hence, it is conceivable to transform one into another by virtue of this feature. The research is structured around three interconnected vertices:

1. Cross-Disciplinary Mapping with YAMs

Exploring the ability of TBMs to explain one discipline in terms of another using Yet Another Metaphor, or Your Analogy Models (YAMs). This involves comparative trials across varied fields to assess how effectively TBMs can bridge knowledge domains, especially in educational or expert communication contexts.

2. Benchmarking Transformer Models

Establishing a structured evaluation framework to compare multiple TBMs for their accuracy, fluency, and coherence in domain-domain transformations. This includes qualitative expert feedback and quantitative metrics using embedding models like BERT.

3. Applications in Dyslexia and ADHD Support

Applying TBMs to enhance accessibility for individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. This includes simplified sentence transformations and phonetic rule-based modifications to improve comprehension for learners, children or adults. The aim is to integrate AI-driven tools into educational contexts to support neurodiverse learners.

Below is a graphical representation for the research structure as a triangle with equal emphasis on the first three parts (Fig. 7):

FIGURE 7: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

- △ Top: Cross-Disciplinary Mapping (YAMs)
- △ Bottom Left: TBM Benchmarking & Evaluation
- △ Bottom Right: Dyslexia & ADHD Applications
- △ Centre: Transformer-Based Domain Transformation
- △ Arrows to show interrelation and feedback loops

2.2 RESEARCH PARADIGM

This research is primarily comparative and evaluative, thus it will involve a mixed-methods paradigm that combines quantitative performance metrics with qualitative expert feedback, when possible.

The comparative design is aimed at evaluating the performance of TBMs across a range of domain-domain transformation tasks. It attempts to answer the question of identifying the best model for a particular task (domain-domain). For a more comprehensive answer, much larger cross-discipline research will be needed,

but this study could be considered as a first step. It also attempts to generate a framework for such a larger scope, including evaluation methods and statistical analysis of samples, as well as outcomes.

In real life, these models compete for audience to prove their effectiveness as well as their commercial viability. They always endeavour to develop and expand their horizons in order to demonstrate superiority.

At the time of writing, it has been observed that a number of highly specialised AI models started to appear on the market. These tend to be subsets of larger models such as Scite.ai (Scite, n.d.) based on ChatGPT, which is aimed exclusively at the research community. Another example is Eduaide.ai (Eduaide Inc., n.d.), based on similar LLM, and finetuned for education, aimed to help teachers in their lesson planning and similar tasks. The arrival of such specialised models indicates the trend to target niche vertical markets and claim superiority in a particular field, which is partly what this research was attempting to establish. This gives it a *raison d'être*, but the more justified purpose is to highlight the need for AI models to do more in assisting neurodivergent audiences.

The research combines computational experimentation with qualitative expert evaluation in certain places, since the aim of this study deviated from the prime reason (which would have needed extensive feedback) to one that required a more specialist one, as will be explained later.

The working of this research is situated within an evaluative framework that does not aim to develop completely new models, but plant seeds for ones where applicable, and to systematically compare the capabilities of existing models in tasks requiring conceptual translation between domains. The approach is grounded in theoretical perspectives from transfer learning, analogy-based reasoning, and natural language transformation. These inform both the selection of tasks and the evaluation criteria.

The study explores two distinct use cases:

- YAM for cross-disciplinary explanation
- Phonetic simplification for Dyslexia and ADHD support

As briefly mentioned, the life of this research started with putting the bigger emphasis on the first of these two cases but gradually (positively) drifted the emphasis onto the second, with the view of expanding its potential benefit and (given the evident lack of substantial research involving TBMs in this domain) to plant a seed for future research.

The research aims to answer the question of:

- Variances between the large AI models in the way they handle transformation.
- The effect and benefits of establishing the level of such variance, if any, for the world of AI, sociologically and commercially, and the benefit of users, respectively.
- How to benchmark the results of such comparison.

2.3 MODEL SELECTION AND TASKS

Six TBMs were selected for these trials, including ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, DeepSeek, Meta-AI, and Bing Chat (Copilot). Each model was presented with the same set of tasks and prompts to ensure consistency.

The two experimental tasks were as follows:

- YAM Transformation

In the first three trials, the test subjects were asked to transform concepts from one discipline into another (e.g. explaining neuroscience concepts using music analogies), described in short explanatory sentences. In the fourth trial, the input sentences were extended to ensure variety and increased complexity of input, thus a high-level concept from music theory was employed. The output from these trials were measured metrically using other AI tools, scored and analysed mathematically, subject to golden standards provided by informed experts. It was also judged qualitatively for the purpose of inclusion, although a high numerical value scored ensured such quality in the first place.

- Dyslexia/ADHD Simplification and Phonics

This emerged as the central focus of the research. For test purposes, sentences were transformed into phonetically simplified versions to improve accessibility for individuals with Dyslexia. This transformation also included, in the case of ADHD, some visual effects based on another well-known and well publicised technique for helping ADHD readability. There are no given standards to compare these outputs with, which is the motive for focusing on this field in the first place. The only measure of success or failure would be whether a TBM can perform the task at hand according to the given prompts. Outputs were compared to a model created in this research on the principle of a rule-based phonetic transformation system, which could be developed into a fully-fledged TBM in a second life beyond the scope of this research. A small-scale real-life experiment with school children was also conducted to support the aim of this research.

2.4 DATA COLLECTION

The primary data sources for the first part of the research included:

- Researcher prompts for YAM
- Output from each TBM
- Expert-generated golden standards for comparison
- Numerical results from an AI model

The primary data sources for the second part of the research included:

- Researcher prompts of combined instructions
- Dataset manually prepared with pairs of sentences, original and simplified
- Output from each TBM
- Qualitative assessment by the researcher
- Output from a rule-based model created by the researcher
- Results from a real-life experiment

2.5 EVALUATION METHODS

A combination of quantitative and qualitative evaluation methods was used.

Quantitative Evaluation for part one:

- Semantic Similarity Scoring: Outputs were compared to expert reference versions using BERT-based similarity metrics to quantify the closeness of the transformation.
- Execution Time Measurement: Planned in the design of a much larger trial but were not measured for the shorter ones.
- Numerical results from an AI model.

Apart from analysing the results of the real-life experiment, no quantitative valuation was applied for part two of the research as there were no golden standards. It would not be possible to compare the trial output to the output from the rule-based model since the former failed to pass the qualitative assessment.

Qualitative Evaluation for part one:

- Expert Review: Selected model outputs were reviewed by domain experts, who would rate them as acceptable or not, based on their conceptual relevance.
- Expert Analysis: Comparison with the numerical scoring.

Qualitative Evaluation for part two:

- Semantic Similarity: Judged by the researcher.
- Visual Effect: Judged by the researcher.
- Thematic Analysis: Expert comments were analysed for recurring patterns in model strengths, weaknesses, and failure types.

2.6 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Apart from the researcher himself, only one other expert participant was a voluntary contributor, providing small sample sets for comparative materials. No personal data was collected. The study adheres to ethical guidelines for research involving human judgment and AI evaluation as directed and approved by Kennedy University.

This is particularly pertinent when an experiment involving school children was to be conducted as the concluding activity in this research. Ethical measures taken prior, during, and post-experiment will be detailed in Chapter 7 of this thesis.

CHAPTER 3: THE START AND RESEARCH THEME

In this chapter, the early preparation and motivations of this research project is detailed. It also outlines the framework for conducting the research prior to formulating the design. A proposal for a much wider experiment based on the principles is also introduced before concluding with a roadmap for the current project.

3.1 PREPARATION

To determine the ability of AI models to perform similar tasks, ChatGPT was prompted to rewrite the text below. The prompt invited the model to replace the concept of 'spatiotemporal' with a transformation a musician would understand. Here is the original text that was provided¹:

Despite substantial recent progress, our understanding of the principles and mechanisms underlying complex brain function and cognition remains incomplete. Network neuroscience proposes to tackle these enduring challenges. Approaching brain structure and function from an explicitly integrative perspective, network neuroscience pursues new ways to map, record, analyse and model the elements and interactions of neurobiological systems. Two parallel trends drive the approach: the availability of new empirical tools to create comprehensive maps and record dynamic patterns among molecules, neurons, brain areas and social systems; and the theoretical framework and computational tools of modern network science. **The convergence of empirical and computational advances opens new frontiers of scientific inquiry, including network dynamics, manipulation and control of brain networks, and integration of network processes across spatiotemporal domains.** We review emerging trends in network neuroscience and attempt to chart a path toward a better understanding of the brain as a multiscale networked system.

¹ The paragraph in bold in the input and output is where the required transformation occurs.

And here is the response:

Despite substantial recent progress, our understanding of the principles and mechanisms underlying complex brain function and cognition remains incomplete. Network neuroscience proposes to tackle these enduring challenges. Approaching brain structure and function from an explicitly integrative perspective, network neuroscience pursues new ways to map, record, analyse, and model the elements and interactions of neurobiological systems. Two parallel trends drive the approach: the availability of new empirical tools to create comprehensive maps and record dynamic patterns among molecules, neurons, brain areas, and social systems; and the theoretical framework and computational tools of modern network science.

The convergence of empirical and computational advances opens new frontiers of scientific inquiry, including network dynamics, manipulation and control of brain networks, and integration of network processes across different levels of detail and timescales similar to how a musical composition unfolds across different instruments and moments in time.

We review emerging trends in network neuroscience and attempt to chart a path toward a better understanding of the brain as a multi-scale networked system.

ChatGPT also added the following explanation:

By comparing the concept to musical structure (e.g. different instruments interacting over time), the idea of networks operating at different levels and temporal scales becomes more intuitive for musicians.

It was then prompted to rewrite the whole text from a musician's perspective. The response was:

Despite great progress, we still do not fully understand the principles that shape how the brain processes information, creates meaning, and enables complex thought. Network neuroscience approaches the brain much like a musician approaches an orchestra or an ensemble not as isolated parts, but as a dynamic, interconnected system where each element plays a role in the

whole. This field seeks to map, analyse [sec], and model the intricate relationships between different components of the brain, from individual neurone to large-scale brain regions, much like a composer organises melodies, harmonies, and rhythms across multiple instruments.

Two major advances drive this approach: first, new tools allow us to capture detailed processes of neural activity, revealing the way different parts of the brain interact in real time, much like recording and analysing an improvisation session; second, modern computational techniques give us frameworks for understanding these interactions, similar to how music theory helps explain harmonic and rhythmic structures. By combining these empirical and theoretical insights, network neuroscience opens new possibilities of exploring how neural connections shift and adapt, how we might guide or reshape these connections, and how different levels of brain activity integrate over time, much like motifs and themes developing throughout a symphony.

In this review, we explore the latest developments in network neuroscience and outline a path toward a richer understanding of the brain, not just as a collection of isolated notes, but as a living, evolving composition.

It also added:

This version translates the scientific concepts into a language that resonates with musicians, using analogies from composition, performance, and improvisation.

This experiment inspired the researcher to explore in depth the ability of various AI models to transform one discipline in terms of another. This prompted an investigation in the capability of other models to process similar tasks. It was observed that different models perform noticeably differently in their outcome. That observation informed the decision to pursue this study even before embarking on the current project. Other potential avenues of research include:

- designing AI models to recognise the prompter's own speciality and transform texts accordingly
- the ability to recognise target publications for the appropriate transformation
- other applications to help readers and researchers with neurodiversity

The aim of that is to overcome disadvantages, which impair accessibility to specialist materials. Even simpler texts may present a particular difficulty to someone with Dyslexia, for instance.

One could then envisage the practical benefits of such research in fields such as academia, industry, and for accessibility-focused NLP applications. In addition, in a more general social sense, it could lead to developing a scheme for assisting neurodiversity. The ultimate aim is to have a universal model to get answers from fields one is not familiar with, starting with the prompt of the user's speciality as a criterion. The development of such a model will be beyond the scope of this research, or the efforts of most individual experts.

This research aims to inspire other researchers and AI development teams to set this as a target for future work and promote the concept of universality of such applications. As a side contribution to this field, this research introduces an approach to evaluating TBMs and, in particular, a method for comparative view of these models.

3.2 COMPARING TBMS

The research cycle started by conducting several trials to compare the various TBMs on domain-domain transformation. The working hypothesis is that not all TBMs are equally good at the task of simplification, precision, and clarity. However, the null hypothesis would be that all TBMs will perform equally well, and this is what the trials will aim to reject.

Such comparison is especially important in the context of Dyslexia and ADHD, for a few key reasons:

1. Some models (like T5 or GPT variants) may excel at paraphrasing but overcomplicate language. Others, like finetuned BART models (Bidirectional and Auto-Regressive Transformers) (Lewis, et al., 2020), might be better at shortening and simplifying text. Comparing them helps finding the model that best aligns with specific cognitive accessibility needs.

- Dyslexia: Needs models that simplify phonetics, reduce ambiguity, and remove silent letters or complex syntax.

- ADHD: Needs models that restructure content into concise, high-impact formats (lists, cues, visual triggers).

2. Cognitive load varies by output style

Different TBMs might produce different kinds of outputs even for the same input. Some may hallucinate and produce completely nonsensical transformations, as will be observed later. Discovering which model produces outputs that reduce cognitive load is key to matching content delivery to user strengths. Some of these variations might be:

- One model may preserve more meaning but use more difficult words
- Another may simplify too much, losing crucial details
- A third may balance both.

3. User-specific preference modelling

Individuals with Dyslexia or ADHD are not identical in their needs and types of neurodivergence. Their preferences may vary significantly. Comparing models allows selection or personalisation in different ways such as:

- TBMs that align best with this user's reading pattern or attention style
- TBMs which produce outputs that are easiest to act on or remember

4. Benchmarking to be adopted in clinical and educational fields

Any future assistive model for education or neurodivergent support, will need quantitative and qualitative evidence of its superior performance. Such an accolade needs to be evidenced by trials and experiments to:

- Measure reading time, comprehension, or error rate
- Asking experts or users to rate ease-of-use or clarity
- Using metrics like FKGL (Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level) (Kincaid, et al., 1975), and BERTScore. FKGL is a readability formula that estimates the reading grade level required to understand a text.

5. Supporting multimodal or multitasking needs

Individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD often benefit from hybrid outputs (e.g. text combined with audio and/or visuals)². Comparing TBMs can help identify:

- Which ones are better suited to plug into multimodal pipelines
- Which ones adapt better to noisy or partial input (e.g. from dyslexic writing)

It is therefore considered essential, and not just useful, to carry out such comparison in order to support Dyslexia and ADHD readability meaningfully. The comparison will help identify a best-fit model(s) and inform ethical and effective deployment of the most suited model for the task.

A structured comparison framework tailored to domain-domain transformation for supporting Dyslexia and ADHD may involve many aspects of the TBMs tested. Below is a list of these aspects, some of which will also fall beyond the scope of this research, but is still useful to list for any future work:

1. Input-output task design

Choosing representative tasks that reflect real-world cognitive accessibility needs.

For Dyslexia:

- Academic → Simplified, phonetic-friendly English
- Formal → Everyday language
- Scientific → Transformed into metaphors

For ADHD:

- Dense text → Bullet-point summary
- Multi-step instructions → Actionable checklists
- Unstructured notes → Organised plans

² This research will not be examining this feature as it falls outside the main focus of the comparison, which is NLP, but it is worth mentioning for future trials or experiments, research, and development.

2. Model selection

This should include a variety of TBMs with different capabilities:

- General-purpose: ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, DeepSeek, Meta AI, Bing Chat (all included in this research)
- Text simplification-tuned: T5, BART, PEGASUS (some are included implicitly in the work here)
- Compact/efficient: DistilBERT, MiniLM for real-time tools
- Multimodal models with vision or speech options

3. Evaluation metrics

This should be carried out quantitatively using specialised AI models/tools, and qualitatively by inviting experts to judge the quality of output.

A. Quantitative (Automated)

For measuring clarity, accuracy, and semantic alignment:

- BERTScore / BLEURT / COMET – Semantic similarity to expert simplifications
- FKGL – Text readability
- Compression ratio – words reduced while retaining meaning
- Execution time – efficiency on-device or in-app
- Phonetic simplicity score – (custom rule-based metric)

B. Qualitative (experts' rating)

Collect feedback from:

- Experts in special education or cognitive accessibility ³

³ In this research, external multi-disciplinary experts are expected to contribute to the largest of the trials.

- Individuals with ADHD and Dyslexia⁴

C. Using Likert scales (Lindamood & Lindamood, 1998), a tool associated with assessing phonological processing abilities, particularly in people with Dyslexia or ADHD, as yes/no ratings:

- Clarity – easy to read/understand?
- Confidence – would the user trust this output?
- Helpfulness – does it reduce confusion or mental effort?
- Retention aid – easier to remember or act on?

4. Error recovery evaluation

This test is important for noisy input or spelling mistakes:

- Error detection rate – % of occurrence of the model detecting misspelled or broken input
- Correction accuracy – % of outputs that fix the issue while preserving meaning
- Recovery effort – number of iterations needed to reach usable output

5. Sample size and source

Given ample resources for research and evaluation, one should use a mix of:

- 5-10 inputs per task type (dyslexia-friendly, ADHD-friendly, etc.)
- From both natural sources (e.g. real academic texts, student writing) and constructed examples
- Use expert-generated target outputs for benchmarking

6. Comparative output table

⁴ An experiment involving children with Dyslexia/ADHD from a primary school was conducted (Ch. 7).

The results could be tabulated side-by-side for comparison as in the example table below (Table 2):

TABLE 2: MODEL COMPARISON

Model	Task	Output	Readability	BERTScore	FKGL	Human Rating	Notes
ChatGPT	Academic → Simple	"..."	7.2	0.89	6.3	4.5/5	Too verbose
Gemini	Dense → Checklist	"..."	8.0	0.85	5.1	4.8/5	Great focus
.....							
.....							

3.3 THE RESEARCH THEME

The challenges for TBMs in the field of domain-domain transformation are many and complex. This is due to the lack of sufficient training data and error magnification, (when a small error generates poor results, amongst other deficiencies, as compared to human abilities).

As indicated above, this research aims to initiate a concept for testing and evaluating TBMs, where transformer models can be compared in YAM trials to evaluate their strengths in domain-domain transformation.

YAM is a framework for explaining complex concepts in one discipline using analogies or structures from another. For example, a YAM trial between physics and music, will involve taking a concept like a change in wavelength and transforming it into a change in pitch of a musical note. Such trials seem to be absent from the literature survey carried out here, hence the attempt of this research to lead, or at least promote, the concept of testing TBMs from this perspective. This is the initial step in preparing the ground for a special case of TBMs to deal with the more complex and demanding cases of Dyslexia and ADHD readability aids.

The methodology adopted for this research is quantitative, which control dependency by randomisation in experiments, use statistical analysis such as

regression and ANOVA, and by using larger sample sizes to reduce bias. The outputs of TBMs invoked will be evaluated and scored by another AI tool, and according to the criteria of the architecture of that tool.

A benchmark framework for this study would involve:

- The models being tested (ChatGPT, Gemini, etc.)
- The input datasets (expert samples, transformed outputs)
- The methodology for comparison (e.g. human evaluation, automated scoring with BERT similarity)

3.3.1 RESEARCH STAGES

The stages of this research can be summed by the following steps:

1. The Trials

The researcher has conducted several trials on various models before concluding that the Cross-Encoder model from Hugging Face is best suited for this purpose. Employing only pretrained and finetuned models (like ChatGPT) is a convenient approach for general use. The alternative would be embarking on a huge number of models already developed and accessible at Hugging Face, but this could take years to complete. Notwithstanding, new models will always be developed and most, if not all, would need to be finetuned and trained extensively to be beneficial for the general use. As it stands, these models are only available for AI developers who are experts at the architecture of transformers, adept at finetuning them, and familiar with development environments and languages such as Python.

In Table 3 below, the output from each AI model is evaluated against a golden standard. This is a statement from an expert in both fields (source and target). It represents the expert's interpretation of the original concept by simplifying or using a metaphor from the target domain. For example, a golden standard for "symptoms of acute myocardial infarction" from medicine, is "signs of a heart attack", in plain English.

TABLE 3: DOMAIN TRANSFORMATION

Transfer		TBMs Output & Runtime						Golden Standard
From	To	ChatGPT	Runtime	Gemini	Runtime	Runtime	
D1	D2							
D2	D4							
D3	D6							
.....							
.....	Dn							

2. Empirical Evaluation

This stage involves conducting trials of various TBMs on text transformation from one discipline to another, assessing their efficiency, accuracy, and linguistic coherence. This is done by selecting as many publicly available AI models as possible. A number of the most common disciplines were then randomly selected, to avoid bias. The output of each of the AI models is then evaluated against a golden standard, as defined previously. This is carried out by another BERT-based module from the Hugging Face platform. After assessing which model is finetuned to produce accurate results, by using a simple sentence such as “The sun is out today” (scoring high compared to the exact sentence/low compared to an empty string), a selection is made.

3. Universal Model Proposal

Based on the result of the experiment, one of the AI models could be considered best suited to produce good results in various trials with various subjects. The examination of the architecture of this model, together with the datasets it was trained on, will aid the development of even more advanced models.

4. Expected Outcomes

Despite its limited scope in terms of the range of domains used to build this dataset, this will act as a nucleus for constructing a much larger one to be:

- A useful survey of publicly accessible TBMs and their effectiveness
- A performance benchmark to highlight the strengths and limitations of TBMs tested
- A suggestion for a universal TBM that can outperform others across a variety of domains

The last of these expected outcomes is the most complex task, if the actual development of such an all-encompassing model is to be undertaken. Considering the advanced features of the present models, this would be a challenging task. There are many difficulties at different levels for such improvements to be achieved, including the energy needed to develop and run such models. Perhaps with the advancement of quantum computing, this will no longer be an issue. In general, using YAM, improving on the performance of some of the existing AI models is like increasing the speed of a fast fighter jet from Mach3 without using much more power or fuel. This may also need significantly larger datasets to train on, and may additionally benefit from combining them with other types of neural networks, to create more versatile AI systems.

5. Contribution to NLP Research

In conclusion, this study will provide a valuable insight into TBM performance in text transformation, especially for Dyslexia and (potentially⁵) ADHD. It is hoped that it will promote the development of a universal model with adaptable architecture to improve accessibility in various domains, such as education, journalism, and healthcare. It will also suggest alternative approaches to designing other experiments, which may lead to further improvements in the future design of TBMs.

⁵ Considering the complexity of the ADHD condition referred to earlier, and the anticipated difficulty in designing and developing such a specialised TBM.

3.4 RESEARCH TRIAL DESIGN

This section will outline how the above general theme was applied specifically in the current project.

3.4.1 TBM SELECTION

Choosing models such as ChatGPT turned out to be the logical option for several reasons:

- a) Accessibility by anyone – If models other than ones already available for general use were chosen for these trials, they would not be easily accessible to the general public. To access specialised models, such as the ones hosted by various platforms, users would have to employ tools like Python and Java script to generate the desired transformation. They may even have to apply techniques to finetune the resulting model in order to achieve meaningful and useful results. This is something only expert AI developers need to concern themselves with.
- b) Given the limited scope of this research, it would have been an extremely complex operation to identify TBMs in the vast library of hosting platforms. In addition, it would have taken considerable time to finetune those models, which can only be possible by accessing large datasets. As mentioned previously in Chapter 1, it may not even be possible to access those datasets without explicit permissions or considerable cost.
- c) Prior to deciding on the selection of TBMs for these trials, a number of small T5-based models from the Hugging Face library (T5-base, T5-small, T5-large, etc) were tried with simple specialised texts. Each attempt was fraught with the difficulties of setting up the right Python environment, the development tool Xcode (Apple Inc., 2024), and the required models from Hugging Face, or other AI development resources. Despite that, the results of such attempts turned out to be very poor each time. An added drawback to this approach was the extended execution time it took for the shortest text to be transformed in a typical developer's computing environment.

Below is an example of a Python script with its inference result, using T5-small:

```
from transformers import T5Tokenizer, T5ForConditionalGeneration

model_name = "t5-small"
tokenizer = T5Tokenizer.from_pretrained(model_name)
model = T5ForConditionalGeneration.from_pretrained(model_name)
def transform(text):
    input_text = f"Translate neurology to music: {text}"
    input_ids = tokenizer.encode(input_text, return_tensors="pt")
    outputs = model.generate(input_ids)
    transformed_sentence = tokenizer.decode(outputs[0],
skip_special_tokens=True)
    return transformed_sentence
# Example usage:
input_text = "spatiotemporal data that relates both to space and
time"
print(transform(input_text))
```

Output:

```
Neurology to music: spatiotemporal data that relate both to space and
time

(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 %
```

As is evident from the result above, this trial failed miserably, and no transformation took place. Without finetuning this model, which would have meant considerable development effort that is beyond the scope of this research, this approach was ruled out. It would also have meant repeating the same lengthy process for several of the more complex and advanced models, including creating and training them on larger datasets.

This could be a great future research project for a large team of researchers with ample resources of time, expertise, computing power, and financial backing. The example above shows clearly why testing the raw models from Hugging Face and other platforms is impractical and would not yield useful results. In fact, many of the models that can be tested would have needed finetuning in order to produce meaningful and testable results. This would also have introduced bias to the

experiment and deviated from the main objective of the trials to evaluate existing models.

The other issue with this approach is the execution time of testing any of the models, especially the large ones, and the need to have a powerful environment for the exercise. Furthermore, this will contribute nothing to the desired benefit of the research, which is evaluating accessible models, such as ChatGPT.

As mentioned, finetuning TBMs is not a trivial task and certainly not for the general consumer of TBMs. What follows is a simple example of a model from Hugging Face with one attempt at finetuning it, and the steps involved in that process, first in plain English, and then in Python.

TRAINING TBMS (ENGLISH)

Training a TBM involves several steps. It starts by gathering data for training the model. Below is an overview of the process:

Data Preparation

Before training a TBM, a clean and structured dataset is needed. This can be text from books, websites, or any corpus related to the task. For instance, if one is building a Dyslexia correction model, the dataset would consist of text with common dyslexia-related spelling mistakes.

Preparing the data would take several steps as follows:

- Text Cleaning – Remove irrelevant text, special characters, or noisy data.
- Tokenisation – Transformer models like BERT, GPT, and T5 process text as sequences of tokens (words or sub-words). Tokenisation breaks the text into smaller units that the model can process. Libraries like Hugging Face's transformers and tokenisers handle this automatically.
- Dataset Splitting – Split the dataset into training, validation, and test sets. This allows for the training of the model, validates it during training to avoid overfitting, and finally tests its generalisation on unseen data.

Overfitting refers to a modelling error that occurs when a machine learning model captures not only the underlying patterns in the training data, but also its random

noise and specific idiosyncrasies. As a result, the model demonstrates high accuracy on the training data but performs poorly on unseen or test data. This would indicate a failure to generalise to new inputs.

Finetuning Model Selection

The next step in the finetuning process is selecting an appropriate transformer model for the task. The Hugging Face transformers library provides a variety of pretrained models like:

- BERT – Good for text classification and token classification tasks.
- GPT-2 – A generative model suited for text generation tasks.
- T5 – A flexible model that works well for text-to-text tasks (like translation, summarisation, or error correction).
- RoBERTa – A robust version of BERT, better for certain NLP tasks.

One can then start with a pretrained model (i.e. a model trained on a large corpus like Wikipedia or Common Crawl) and finetune it for a specific task.

The Training Process

This is an overview of how TBMs are trained:

A pretrained model, like BERT or T5, can be selected for finetuning for a specific task and dataset. Finetuning involves training the model for a smaller number of epochs on a dataset, using a lower learning rate so that the model adapts to the task but retains its previously learned general language understanding.

The process typically involves:

- Input Embedding – The model converts each token (word or sub-word) into vectors using pretrained embeddings.
- Attention Mechanism – The Transformer’s attention layers calculate how much attention each word should pay to other words in the sequence.
- Feed-Forward Layers – After the attention mechanism, the data flows through feed-forward layers that help the model make predictions.

- **Output Layer** – For classification tasks, the output is a probability distribution over classes. For text generation tasks, it predicts the next token in the sequence.

TRAINING TBMS (PYTHON)

To affect a practical training of a TBM by coding, the steps below have to be followed. To demonstrate this, the process starts by selecting a T5 model from the Hugging Face library. The aim of the training in this example, is converting medical text into layman's terms.

Load a Pretrained T5 Model

```
from transformers import T5ForConditionalGeneration, T5Tokenizer
model_name = "t5-base" # You can also try "google/t5-small" or
"google/flan-t5-large"
tokenizer = T5Tokenizer.from_pretrained(model_name)
model = T5ForConditionalGeneration.from_pretrained(model_name)
```

Prepare Input Data

```
input_text = "transform: The patient exhibits symptoms of myocardial
infarction."
```

Tokenize the input:

```
input_ids = tokenizer(input_text, return_tensors="pt").input_ids
```

Generate Transformed Output

```
output_ids = model.generate(input_ids, max_length=50)
output_text = tokenizer.decode(output_ids[0],
skip_special_tokens=True)
print("Transformed Text:", output_text)
```

Finetune on Custom Data (using domain-specific text pairs)

```
from datasets import load_dataset
dataset = load_dataset("csv", data_files={"train": "train.csv",
"test": "test.csv"})
from transformers import Trainer, TrainingArguments
training_args = TrainingArguments(
    output_dir="./t5_finetuned",
    per_device_train_batch_size=8,
    per_device_eval_batch_size=8,
    evaluation_strategy="epoch",
    save_strategy="epoch",
    num_train_epochs=3,
```

```

)
trainer = Trainer(
    model=model,
    args=training_args,
    train_dataset=dataset["train"],
    eval_dataset=dataset["test"],
)
trainer.train()

```

Deploy the Model

```

model.save_pretrained("t5_transformation_model")
tokenizer.save_pretrained("t5_transformation_model")

```

This illustrates the lengthy and complex process of training and finetuning a model that has not been pretrained.

3.4.2 DOMAIN SELECTION

Initially, it was thought necessary to statistically determine the sample size of domains to serve the purpose of these trials. The other approach would have been following similar evaluation methods from the literature. The topics of the domains selected may then be gathered from a closely uniform source, similar in form, size, and nature. This was intended to eliminate variation and manage dependencies as much as possible.

However, due to the limited scope of this research project, it was opted to collect texts extracted from various scientific, medical, and legal published documents. For each target, an expert in the two domains (source and target), was chosen to produce a golden standard from source to target. The golden standard was subsequently used to evaluate the outcome of each TBM in each trial.

Since the protocol of the trials is equivalent to a pilot study for a much larger-scaled project, it was decided that choosing a sample in this manner was adequate for the purpose. There may be an uncontrolled-for factor in this approach, as this would have introduced bias in the selection process. However, the various randomisation techniques intended to be used in the trials would statistically insure a normal distribution and balanced outcome in a larger-scale experiment.

3.4.3 EVALUATION TOOLS AND METHODS

There are many tools for evaluating TBMs. The nature of the task of evaluation would determine which one is to be employed. For machine translation, for instance, **BLEU** (Bilingual Evaluation Understudy) (Papineni, et al., 2002) seems to be the most popular.

In the literature surveyed, the most commonly used metric tool for text simplification and paraphrasing is the **SARI** scoring system. SARI requires the original text as its first parameter in the form of:

SARI(original text, transformed text, golden standard)

SARI functions by measuring how well a system rewrites a sentence to make it more accessible, while preserving the semantics of the same. It compares the rewritten version to both the original and the simplified golden standard.

In the case of these trials, the comparison of various TBMs needs only to be measured against a golden standard, hence **BERTScore** was chosen, as it is designed for NLU and achieves state-of-the-art results in many NLP tasks. BERTScore was considered the best fit since it focuses on meaning rather than exact wording, and takes only two pieces of text to compare in the format:

BERTScore(modified text, golden standard)

Therefore, one can always evaluate any outcome against one golden standard in one discipline.

An example of Python code to use BERTScore:

```
from bert_score import score
# Example Inputs
generated = ["The child is playing outside."]
references = ["The kid is playing in the park."]
# Compute BERTScore
P, R, F1 = score(generated, references, lang="en",
rescale_with_baseline=True)
print(f"BERTScore F1: {F1.mean().item():.4f}")
```

In conclusion, this model was chosen for the evaluation of the results of transformations in these trials. The next Chapter will put the ideas and steps described in this Chapter into practice.

CHAPTER 4: THE TRIALS IN PRACTICE

In this chapter the trials conducted, and their results, are detailed. A statistical analysis and discussion are also presented at the end of each trial.

4.1 RESEARCH PLAN

When this research started, the focus was on designing and implementing long and extended trials to study and compare various major TBMs, centred on domain-domain transformation. However, the emphasis of this shifted significantly after discovering the dearth of TBMs addressing neurodivergence. It was then concluded that the eventual application and benefit of the research would best serve solutions incorporating AI aids for Dyslexia and ADHD as the foci of this project. These conditions were of particular interest and relevance to the researcher's life experience in education, working with children and young adults, and for realising the importance and prevalence of these conditions.

Given the constraints of time and resources, it was decided to carry out pilot trials on only four domains that either the researcher himself is familiar with, or is connected to experts who can provide the crucial input into these pilot trials.

In what follows, larger trials were discussed and planned but no implementation had been carried out, leaving this opportunity to another team of researchers to carry on where this project leaves off.

Starting with the aims of the larger trials, the list below will sum up its objectives:

- test only the most popular and widely used TBMs
- set the ground for other research programmes to expand these trials, to cover not only the selections of TBMs, but also the parameters of input data in length and complexity
- widen the objective of the trials to cover more aspects and functions of TBMs, and/or focus deeply on specific roles, such as the real-world scenario of transforming lengthy documents like books.

As mentioned above, even if these larger trials were to be conducted in this project, it was considered prudent to carry out pilot trials on a much smaller scale prior to commencing the main trial, using all the models involved.

For these pilot trials, a number of multidisciplinary experts were consulted, and, for each trial, a golden standard was obtained from the relevant expert.

FIGURE 8: TRIALS SCHEMATIC

Before the detailed description of these trials is presented in the next section, a visualised presentation of the various stages of each trial can be seen above (Fig. 8). The diagram represents one trial of transforming from one

domain to another using a golden standard as provided by an expert in both fields.

In each trial, a concept from the first domain is presented to all the TBMs involved in the trial to transform into the target domain. Once this is done, each output is then compared to the relevant golden standard using a BERT-based evaluation metric. These scores are then compared by the researcher numerically in order to rank these TBMs, and also to ascertain the level of variation between them.

4.2 TRIALS IN ACTION

This section will detail each trial conducted. The trials were carried out by apps on an Apple iPad iOS 18.3.2 device.

4.2.1 TRIAL 1

The concept chosen for the first pilot trial is electron quantum entanglement. This is a phenomenon in quantum mechanics where two or more particles become interconnected in such a way that the state of one instantly influences the state of the other(s) when they are apart, regardless of the distance between them.

The metaphor in music theory that best describes this phenomenon is the effect of tuning one musical instrument to affect another instrument located at a distance from the first one.

The prompt used to initiate these pilot trials was:

Describe quantum entanglement in terms of music in a short sentence using metaphors.

The golden standard, obtained from a PhD holder in physics who is also a keen musician, used for comparison was:

Quantum entanglement in music is like tuning one instrument will change the tuning of another one found at a distance from the first in the same way.

The scoring was carried out via the Python module used in Chapter 1, where each output was measured against the corresponding golden standard.

TABLE 4: OUTPUT FROM PILOT 1

TBMs	Output	Cosine Similarity
ChatGPT	Quantum entanglement is like two musicians on opposite sides of the world who, without hearing each other, play perfectly in sync—change one note, and the other instantly follows.	0.9022
DeepSeek	Entangled particles are distant violins in a silent symphony, one's whispered chord echoing instantly through the other's unseen strings.	0.6796
Claude	Quantum entanglement is like two instruments playing in perfect harmony across an orchestra hall, each instantly matching the other's rhythm and key without communication, as if their musical souls are forever intertwined beyond the constraints of space.	0.7987
Bing Chat (Co-pilot)	Quantum entanglement is like two distant musicians playing a duet on instruments tuned to the same cosmic key—pluck one string, and the other vibrates in harmony, no matter how far apart they are.	0.8257
Meta AI	Quantum entanglement is like harmony, where two connected notes resonate together, echoing each other's changes, even when played apart.	0.8890
Gemini	Like two notes perfectly harmonized across vast distances, even when plucked separately, their resonance remains inextricably linked.	0.7176

The inference output of various executions of the Python code above is shown below for evidence:

```
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini test.py % python3 pilot.py
ChatGPT Score is
Cosine similarity between the two texts: 0.9022
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini test.py % python3 pilot.py
DeepSeek Score is
Cosine similarity between the two texts: 0.6796
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini test.py % python3 pilot.py
```

```
Claude Score is
Cosine similarity between the two texts: 0.7987
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini test.py % python3 pilot.py
Bing Chat Score is
Cosine similarity between the two texts: 0.8257
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini test.py % python3 pilot.py
Meta-AI Score is
Cosine similarity between the two texts: 0.8890
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini test.py % python3 pilot.py
Gemini Score is
Cosine similarity between the two texts: 0.7176
```

It is interesting to note that the analysis that follows was made by the researcher prior to calculating the cosine similarities above (table 4), demonstrating the difference between qualitative and quantitative analyses.

Qualitative analysis of the above answers favours the transformation offered by Bing Chat (Co-pilot) followed by the one given by ChatGPT.

In the former, as in quantum mechanics, when an electron's condition changes, a distant entangled electron changes its condition in the same way; a D string of a violin plucked by a musician would cause the D string of the entangled distant violin to vibrate.

In the ChatGPT explanation, the second (distant) instrument is also plucked by a musician and does not resonate spontaneously (as opposed to the above explanation where the second string reacts without further intervention). Therefore the earlier transformation is the one that the musicologist/quantum physicist would favour, as it does not require an external force to affect the change.

It is evident from the result above, that the limited qualitative analysis does not agree totally with the quantitative one. The analysis places ChatGPT as second best and the difference between it and the numerical best is only 0.0765, which is equivalent to just over 0.07%. This remains an indication of good results from both models.

Before continuing the discussing of the results above, it is worth introducing the concept of the Null Hypothesis (H_0) in statistical hypotheses testing. This hypothesis states that there is *no difference between groups or no relationship between the variables to be tested*. Therefore, such hypothesis only needs to be rejected to satisfy the outcome of research or an experiment, and to support another hypothesis (H_1).

For this research, H_0 , is the assumption that most of the variables, in this case the TBMs, must have more in common in terms of their architecture and the datasets used for training, and therefore, their outcome. A casual observation of the output various TBMs generate, may easily give this impression. However, with a background in research and with the belief of approaching questions like these methodically, the trials set out to reject the H_0 hypothesis.

Returning to the discussion of the results of the first pilot trial, the other noticeable thing about the result from this trial is the significant range of variation between the top and bottom scoring at 0.2226 (more than 22%). This is evidence that the Null Hypothesis (the lack of significant difference between the level of accuracy of TBMs in the field of domain-domain transformation) is rejected. This conclusion would be inconclusive until all other trials in this project were conducted. Should this phenomenon continue, then even larger trials on different fields and tasks should be conducted. It thus validates expanding this kind of comparative study, and could even perhaps lead to a larger commercial product for public consumption, akin to other products such as comparisons in the insurance market. For these reasons, three further pilot trials were conducted.

4.2.2 TRIAL 2

The concept chosen for the second pilot trial was Newton's third law of motion. The law states that *for every action, there is an equal and opposite reaction*. The prompt was for this to be explained through metaphors from aviation. The researcher is familiar with these two fields, Newtonian physics and aviation, as a science graduate and an aviator.

The obvious metaphor in aviation is how planes achieve flying by thrusting backward to attain enough forward acceleration (the two equal but opposing forces), together with the aerodynamics of the wings and other surfaces, to give planes the lift they need.

This prompt was specifically designed to test the knowledge of the TBMs in this trial, of established and well-documented facts, without explicitly referencing them (such as Newton’s third law of motion).

The prompt used to initiate this pilot trial was:

Explain Newton's third law of motion in aviation metaphors in one sentence.

The golden standard used for comparison was obtained from a pilot who read aerodynamics, and it was:

Planes produce backward thrust to generate forward acceleration of equal value to generate lift.

TABLE 5: OUTPUT FROM PILOT 2

TBMs	Output	Cosine Similarity
ChatGPT	Newton's third law in aviation is like a jet engine pushing hot gases backward, which in turn propels the aircraft forward through the sky.	0.6609
DeepSeek	Newton’s third law in aviation is like a jet engine’s roar: for every furious thrust of air hurled backward, the plane surges forward—just as wings wrestle wind downward, the sky defiantly lifts the aircraft upward, an eternal dance of action and reaction.	0.5529
Claude	In every aerial dance of physics, a jet's thrust propels it forward only as forcefully as the air is pushed backward, ensuring that the sky always collects an equal and opposite reaction for each action it permits.	0.6635
Bing Chat (Co-pilot)	Newton's third law of motion, in aviation terms, is like a jet engine propelling exhaust gases backward with force, while the plane is	0.7149

	simultaneously thrust forward with equal and opposite force, soaring through the skies.	
Meta AI	Newton's third law is like takeoff and landing: for every upward lift, the runway receives an equal downward force.	0.6938
Gemini	For every action an aircraft exerts (like pushing air downwards for lift), there's an equal and opposite reaction (the air pushing the aircraft upwards).	0.7310

In this trial, once more the Null Hypothesis is clearly rejected as various TBMs produced varying results, deviating from the golden standard.

It is also noticeable, compared to the result from pilot 1, that the general level of scoring is lower. This is due to the various theories of aviation and the variety of forces acting on planes that can either be attributed to Newton's third law or to Bernoulli's principle of pressure variation.

Having said that, the range of the scoring in pilot 2 is narrower than the range in pilot 1. This is merely ~18%, yet significant enough to reject the Null Hypothesis.

It was felt necessary to conduct a third mini trial on a slightly different theme and another two familiar subjects to the author, the environment and architecture. In addition, by building a significant amount of data, a statistical analysis can then be conducted by a method such as ANOVA to calculate the significance of these trials. This statistical method will be explained prior to employing it, at the end of these trials.

4.2.3 TRIAL 3

The concept chosen for the third pilot trial is the Serengeti Rule in environmental science. It explains the ecosystem that maintains a balance in a natural environment.

The obvious metaphor in architecture is how certain elements of any architecturally designed structure, relies heavily on some other particular elements to sustain it. Without such an element, imbalance or even collapse of the structure could follow.

This prompt was specifically designed to test the knowledge of the TBMs of the Serengeti Rule as well as their knowledge of architectural principles.

The prompt used to initiate this pilot trial was:

Give some metaphors from architecture to explain the Serengeti Rule in one sentence.

The golden standard used for comparison, obtained from an architect with 30 years' experience who is also an environmentalist, was:

Removing any key player from a natural habitat is like removing a corner stone of a building and believing it won't collapse.

TABLE 6: OUTPUT FROM PILOT 3

TBMs	Output	Cosine Similarity
ChatGPT	The Keystone Arch: Just as a single keystone holds an entire arch together, a keystone species maintains the stability of an ecosystem.	0.7840
DeepSeek	Just as a keystone locks an arch in place, a single species can uphold an entire ecosystem	0.7827
Claude	Like how load-bearing columns prevent a building's collapse, keystone predators maintain ecosystem integrity by controlling herbivore populations, or how a well-designed arch distributes pressure evenly across its structure, the Serengeti Rule shows that removing apex predators causes ecological imbalance that cascades through every trophic level.	0.7912
Bing Chat (Co-pilot)	The Serengeti Rule, which highlights the importance of keystone species in ecosystems, can be likened to the foundation of a building: just as removing the foundation can lead to the collapse of the entire structure, eliminating a keystone species can unravel the stability of an entire ecological system.	0.8049

Meta AI	The Serengeti Rule is like urban planning: just as a single broken window can destabilize an entire city block, one invasive species can disrupt the entire ecosystem.	0.8351
Gemini	just as a keystone supports an arch, or a load-bearing wall stabilizes a building, a single critical species, when removed, can cause the entire ecosystem's structure to collapse.	0.7923

Once more, in this trial, the Null Hypothesis is rejected, albeit by a reduced margin of approximately 5%. This result is predictable since the Serengeti Rule has been widely compared to a keystone in architecture terms. Despite that, it is noticed that some TBMs moved away from this ubiquitous metaphor as in the response of Meta-AI model which incidentally scored the highest in this trial.

4.3 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

For a more methodical approach to evaluate the results from the pilots above, it was decided, even if the size of collected data is small, to conduct an ANOVA statistical analysis to determine the validity of the results. This will also confirm that the Null Hypothesis can be rejected (i.e. there will be significant enough difference between the TBMs in the trial to pursue a much bigger trial).

Before an ANOVA analysis is conducted, one needs to ensure that the input data is normally distributed. To do that, it was decided to use a well know algorithm, the Shapiro-Wilk test of Normality (Shapiro & Wilk, 1965), and a module form the Python library called "Shapiro".

The Shapiro-Wilk test is a statistical test used to check whether a sample comes from a normally distributed population. It is one of the most powerful tests for normality, especially for small sample sizes. It tests that the data was drawn from a normal distribution. A low p-value (typically < 0.05) suggests that the data deviates significantly from normality.

The following Python code is used to preform that test:

```
from scipy.stats import shapiro
# Sample data: three groups of six values each
```

```

Pilot1 = [0.9022,0.6796,0.7987,0.8257,0.8890,0.7176]
Pilot2 = [0.6609,0.5529,0.6635,0.7149,0.6938,0.7310]
Pilot3 = [0.7840,0.7827,0.7912,0.8049,0.8351,0.7923]
# Perform Shapiro-Wilk test of Normality
print("Shapiro-Wilk test of Normality")
# Print results
print("Pilot1:" , shapiro(Pilot1))
print("Pilot2:" , shapiro(Pilot2))
print("Pilot3:" , shapiro(Pilot3))

```

The result of executing the model above with the results from the pilot trials was as follows:

```

(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini test.py % python3 Normal.py
Shapiro-Wilk test of Normality
Pilot1: ShapiroResult(statistic=np.float64(0.9305718673686105),
pvalue=np.float64(0.5845253471982663))
Pilot2: ShapiroResult(statistic=np.float64(0.8697064916731644),
pvalue=np.float64(0.22503757973123864))
Pilot3: ShapiroResult(statistic=np.float64(0.8139463390812085),
pvalue=np.float64(0.07816608131518435))

```

The results from the Shapiro-Wilk test indicate for each group:

1. Test Statistic (*statistic*) – This value ranges from 0 to 1, where values closer to 1 suggest the data is more normally distributed.
2. p-value (*pvalue*) – A p-value greater than 0.05, indicates that the data does not significantly deviate from normality and may be considered approximately normally distributed. If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, the null hypothesis of normality is rejected, suggesting that the data is not normally distributed.

To interpret the results from the Python execution:

- Pilot 1
 - Statistic = 0.931
 - p-value = 0.585 (greater than 0.05)
 - Interpretation – No significant deviation from normality. The data is likely normal.

- Pilot 2
 - Statistic = 0.870
 - p-value = 0.225 (greater than 0.05)
 - Interpretation – No significant deviation from normality. The data is likely normal.
- Pilot 3
 - Statistic = 0.814
 - p-value = 0.078 (greater than 0.05, but close to 0.05)
 - Interpretation – No strong evidence against normality, but it's borderline. The data may have some deviation from normality.

In conclusion of this test:

- Pilot 1 and Pilot 2 are likely normally distributed.
- Pilot 3 is close to the threshold and might have some deviation, but normality cannot be ruled out with high confidence.

All three Pilots have p-values > 0.05, so there is no strong evidence against normality and one can proceed with parametric tests (e.g. ANOVA).

Since three pilot trials were being compared, a one-way ANOVA method is chosen to handle these three trials. Unlike a t-test which compares only two groups, ANOVA can compare multiple groups.

Performing a one-way ANOVA using a module from the Python library:

```
import scipy.stats as stats
import numpy as np
# Sample data: three groups of six values each
Pilot1 = [0.9022,0.6796,0.7987,0.8257,0.8890,0.7176]
Pilot2 = [0.6609,0.5529,0.6635,0.7149,0.6938,0.7310]
Pilot3 = [0.7840,0.7827,0.7912,0.8049,0.8351,0.7923]
# Perform one-way ANOVA
f_stat, p_value = stats.f_oneway(Pilot1,Pilot2,Pilot3)
# Print results
print(f"F-statistic: {f_stat:.4f}")
print(f"P-value: {p_value:.4f}")
```

The result:

```
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini test.py % python3 Anova.py
ANOVA
F-statistic: 8.2297
P-value: 0.0039
```

Interpreting the result above:

Since the p-value is 0.0039 (<0.05), this means that the difference between at least one of these groups is statistically significant.

Further interpretation:

- The F-statistic (8.2297) shows there is a noticeable difference between groups.
- The p-value (0.0039) confirms that this difference is unlikely to be due to chance (with a 0.039% probability of error).
- Conclusion – At least one of the three groups is significantly different from the others.

Although it is unusual to subject a pilot's data to statistical analysis of this kind, it is reassuring to apply it to demonstrate that the Null Hypothesis is rejected so that the research can proceed.

To evaluate how closely each pilot trial aligns with the expected ideal outcome of 1, a one-sample t-test was conducted using Python's `scipy.stats.ttest_1samp` function. This test assesses whether the mean of each pilot group significantly deviates from the ideal. A p-value greater than 0.05 indicates no statistically significant difference from the ideal, supporting the validity of the data.

```
import scipy.stats as stats
# Ideal value is 1
ideal = 1
# Sample data
Pilot1 = [0.9022,0.6796,0.7987,0.8257,0.8890,0.7176]
Pilot2 = [0.6609,0.5529,0.6635,0.7149,0.6938,0.7310]
Pilot3 = [0.7840,0.7827,0.7912,0.8049,0.8351,0.7923]
```

```

# Perform one-sample t-tests
t1, p1 = stats.ttest_1samp(Pilot1, ideal)
t2, p2 = stats.ttest_1samp(Pilot2, ideal)
t3, p3 = stats.ttest_1samp(Pilot3, ideal)
# Print results
print(f"Pilot1: t={t1:.4f}, p={p1:.4f}")
print(f"Pilot2: t={t2:.4f}, p={p2:.4f}")
print(f"Pilot3: t={t3:.4f}, p={p3:.4f}")

```

And the results:

```

(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini test.py % python3 T_Test.py
Pilot1: t=-5.3995, p=0.0029
Pilot2: t=-12.7558, p=0.0001
Pilot3: t=-25.1256, p=0.0000

```

The interpretation of the result above is found below:

- If $p < 0.05$, the mean of that pilot group is significantly different from the population mean.
- If $p > 0.05$, there is no significant difference.

All p-values were less than 0.05 which means every pilot is significantly different from the Ideal. To identify which pilot trial performed best in the ANOVA test, a *post_hoc* test was performed on the pilot trials. A *post_hoc* test is a statistical procedure used after an initial analysis (usually ANOVA) to reveal a significant difference. Its purpose is to identify exactly which groups differ from the others.

```

import scipy.stats as stats
import numpy as np
from statsmodels.stats.multicomp import pairwise_tukeyhsd
# Sample data
group1 = [0.9022,0.6796,0.7987,0.8257,0.8890,0.7176]
group2 = [0.6609,0.5529,0.6635,0.7149,0.6938,0.7310]
group3 = [0.7840,0.7827,0.7912,0.8049,0.8351,0.7923]
# Combine all data into one list
data = np.concatenate([group1, group2, group3])
# Create a list of group labels

```

```

labels = ['Pilot1'] * len(group1) + ['Pilot2'] * len(group2) +
['Pilot3'] * len(group3)
# Perform Tukey's HSD test
tukey_results = pairwise_tukeyhsd(data, labels, alpha=0.05)
# Print results
print(tukey_results)

```

The result:

```

Multiple Comparison of Means - Tukey HSD, FWER=0.05
=====
group1 group2 meandiff p-adj  lower  upper  reject
-----
Pilot1 Pilot2 -0.1326 0.0075 -0.2293 -0.0359  True
Pilot1 Pilot3 -0.0038 0.9944 -0.1005  0.0929  False
Pilot2 Pilot3  0.1289 0.0092  0.0322  0.2256  True
-----

```

The interpretation of the result from the *post_hoc* test:

- If a comparison shows $p < 0.05$, that means the two groups have a statistically significant difference.
- The test adjusts for multiple comparisons, reducing the risk of Type I errors (false positives).

This *post_hoc* test result compares three pilot groups pairwise, assessing whether there are statistically significant differences between them. The output shows the result of a Tukey HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) *post_hoc* test, interpreted as follows:

- **group1, group2** – The two groups being compared
- **meandiff** – The difference in group means (meandiff = group1 – group2)
- **p-adj** – Adjusted p-value for multiple comparisons (lower is more significant)
- **lower, upper** – The lower and upper bounds of the 95% confidence interval
- **reject** – Whether the Null Hypothesis (no difference) is rejected (True = significant difference)

Therefore, the interpretation of this result:

1. Pilot 1 vs Pilot 2

- Mean difference = -0.1326
- $p = 0.0075 \rightarrow$ statistically significant
- CI = [-0.2293, -0.0359]
- Reject Null \rightarrow These two groups differ significantly.

2. Pilot 1 vs Pilot 3

- Mean difference = -0.0038
- $p = 0.9944 \rightarrow$ not significant
- CI = [-0.1005, 0.0929]
- Do not reject Null \rightarrow No significant difference.

3. Pilot 2 vs Pilot 3

- Mean difference = 0.1289
- $p = 0.0092 \rightarrow$ statistically significant
- CI = [0.0322, 0.2256]
- Reject Null \rightarrow These groups differ significantly.

In summary:

- Pilot 1 and Pilot 2 are significantly different.
- Pilot 2 and Pilot 3 are significantly different.
- Pilot 1 and Pilot 3 are not significantly different.

4.4 FURTHER TRIALS

After conducting the initial pilot trials, it was decided that no larger trials would be carried out, as the focus shifted to concentrate on surveying TBMs from the point of view of finding applications in the field of neurodivergence, specifically for Dyslexia and ADHD. Therefore, further pilot trials were conducted with increased input-size prompts and specialised topics.

4.4.1 TRIAL 4

To explore the robustness of the TBMs surveyed, one further trial was conducted with longer sentences.

The prompt for this pilot trial was:

In few short sentences, transform the following in terms of fine art painting using metaphors: Harmony and counterpoint in music

The golden standard was obtained from a musicologist who has studied fine arts (painting), and it was:

In music harmony refers to vertical blending or contrast of notes, like a painter may use complimentary or contrasting colours in one shape/subject on a canvas. Counterpoint refers to two or more different horizontal melodic lines in the same piece of music. Like there may be two or more different shapes/subjects on a canvas, each with its own complimentary or contrasting colours, and together they make one work of art.

TABLE 7: OUTPUT FROM PILOT TRIAL 4

TBMs	Output	Cosine Similarity
ChatGPT	Balance and contrast are fundamental in fine art painting, much like harmony and counterpoint in music. Chord progression mirrors the gradual blending of colors, guiding the eye across the canvas with fluid transitions. Voicing is akin to brushwork—each stroke carefully placed to create depth, texture, and emphasis, ensuring every element interacts with intention and clarity.	0.8402
DeepSeek	Harmony in painting is a symphony of hues, where colors [sic], blend like a choir in unison, each tone softening into the next as dawn melts across a canvas. Counterpoint emerges as a visual fugue—vivid impasto strokes converse with wispy glazes, their textured dialogue a dance of light and shadow, independent yet intertwined, crafting a tapestry where contrast and unity breathe as one.	0.7174
Claude	The canvas of melody unfolds as brushstrokes of harmony dance across it—rich pigments of chords blending at their edges while maintaining distinct hues. Counterpoint weaves like intersecting lines	0.7318

	in a Mondrian composition, creating visual tension and balance. Each chord progression acts as a subtle shift in light and shadow, while voicing provides the textural impasto that gives depth to the musical landscape.	
Bing Chat (Co-pilot)	Harmony and counterpoint in music are like the interplay of light and shadow on a canvas. Harmony serves as the rich, unifying hues that saturate the painting, bringing depth and cohesion. Counterpoint, on the other hand, is the brush's delicate dance, creating intricate strokes that contrast and complement the colors [sic], —each voice an individual line weaving through the artwork, giving it motion and life. Together, they craft a masterpiece where every element contributes to the rhythm and soul of the visual symphony.	0.7599
Meta AI	Harmony and Counterpoint in Music: A Symphony of Color. Brushstrokes of harmonious hues dance across the canvas, a symphony of color [sic], where every note is perfectly in tune. Counterpoint's bold rhythms weave in and out, a delicate balance of light and shadow that creates an ever-changing melody of emotion. Each pigment, a musician in its own right, blends and clashes in a beautiful expression of artistic harmony.	0.7129
Gemini	To transform the concepts of musical harmony and counterpoint into the realm of fine art painting, we can use these metaphors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmony: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Imagine harmony as the canvas's foundational color, palette, where hues blend and support each other, creating a sense of overall balance and emotional resonance. The chord progression is the artists careful selection of the order that those colors, are laid down, to create the emotional journey of the piece. • Counterpoint: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Counterpoint is like the interplay of distinct brushstrokes, each a separate line of color, and texture, yet all weaving together to form a complex and engaging visual narrative. The voicing is the way that the artist organizes the placement of those individual brush strokes, to create a pleasing overall image. 	0.8412

From this trial, the results show a range of over 13% from the top scoring model (Gemini = 0.8412) to the lowest scoring one (Meta-AI = 0.7129). This may be due to the fact that the source domain, music theory and in particular the chosen concept of counterpoint and harmony, is a very complex one to interpret despite the closeness of the two subjects – music and fine art.

4.4.2 PUBLICATION TRIAL (TRIAL 5)

Before concluding this section, the idea of comparing these TBMs in their awareness of various academic publications is of a special interest to the research community and was considered worth exploring. Each model was prompted to rewrite a short piece to a well-known academic journal. To make it more challenging, the text is chosen from a discipline quite different from the target one but not considered so far removed that no transformation would be possible. The task, then, is not only to transform the given text using YAM, but according to the style and format of the target journal, without explicitly stating these or even that it is a condition of the transformation. The TBMs were asked to rationalise their transformation so an accurate judgment can be made of each result.

The text chosen was an extract from this thesis describing the structure of TBMs and the journal chosen was The Journal of Architecture. There was no golden standard for this trial and therefore the assessment will be primarily qualitative.

The prompt for this trial was:

Rewrite the following piece for the Journal of Architecture and explain your approach. The piece is "In general, most TBMs share the same fundamental basic architecture, the keys of which are in two parts; Encoder, which is responsible for processing the input sequence, by converting it into numerical sequence of digits, and a Decoder, which generates the output sequence according to the specific function of the model whether it is a summarisation, simplification, or translation."

ChatGPT Response

In conceptual and structural terms, Transformer-Based Models (TBMs) exhibit a consistent architectural logic that parallels the fundamental principles of modern architectural design: modularity, hierarchical processing, and spatial flow. At the core

of all TBMs lies a bifurcated system comprising two primary components. The *Encoder* acts as a receptacle and interpreter of the input "site"—a textual sequence transformed into a numerical landscape through intricate embedding and attention mechanisms. The Decoder, by contrast, is generative in orientation, sculpting a coherent output from this encoded substrate according to the model's design intent—whether that be summarisation, simplification, or translation. The encoder-decoder framework represents the foundational typology of Transformer architecture, echoing dualities familiar to architectural theory: structure and skin, programme and form, input and output.

Approach Explained:

1. **Disciplinary Framing:** The Journal of Architecture values analogical reasoning and theoretical positioning. I framed the TBM architecture using architectural language—drawing parallels with concepts like modularity, spatial hierarchy, and duality—to make it meaningful to architectural readers.
2. **Lexical Style:** The vocabulary was shifted from plain technical to a more scholarly architectural register (e.g., "bifurcated system," "substrate," "typology").
3. **Metaphorical Layer:** I used architectural metaphors—e.g., "site" for input, "structure and skin" for encoder-decoder—to create a conceptual bridge between neural architecture and building design.
4. **Analytical Tone:** Instead of explaining in a didactic or manual-like tone, the paragraph adopts a reflective, analytic tone—more appropriate for a journal audience interested in cross-disciplinary insight. **Score 10+8=18**

Gemini Response

The foundational architecture underpinning a broad spectrum of Text-Based Models (TBMs) converges on a bipartite structure. This fundamental design comprises two core modules: an **Encoder**, tasked with the initial processing of the input sequence. The Encoder transforms the linguistic input into a numerical representation, effectively translating the symbolic nature of language into a format amenable to computational manipulation. Subsequently, a **Decoder** module receives this encoded representation. Its function is to generate the output sequence, tailored

precisely to the intended task of the model. Whether the objective is summarization, simplification, or translation, the Decoder interprets the encoded information to construct a contextually relevant and functionally appropriate output."

Explanation of the Approach:

The goal was to elevate the original piece to a level suitable for an academic journal like the Journal of Architecture. This involved several key considerations:

1. **Elevated Language and Terminology:** The language was made more formal and precise. Phrases like "in general" were replaced with more academic alternatives like "a broad spectrum of." "The keys of which are in two parts" was rephrased as "converges on a bipartite structure" and "comprises two core modules" for greater sophistication. Terms like "numerical sequence of digits" were refined to "numerical representation" and "format amenable to computational manipulation" to convey a deeper understanding of the underlying process.
2. **Emphasis on Fundamental Principles:** The rewrite emphasizes the *foundational* nature of this architecture. Terms like "fundamental design" and "core modules" highlight the importance and ubiquity of this structure across different TBMs.
3. **Clarity and Conciseness:** While using more formal language, the rewrite also aims for clarity. The functions of the Encoder and Decoder are explained in a logical sequence, emphasizing the transformation of input and the generation of output based on the model's specific task.
4. **Stronger Verbs and Active Voice:** The rewrite employs stronger verbs (e.g., "converges," "comprises," "transforms," "interprets," "constructs") and maintains an active voice to create a more direct and impactful statement.
5. **Connecting to Broader Concepts (Implicit):** While not explicitly stated, the language used hints at the underlying principles of information processing and representation that are relevant in various fields, including potentially architectural design processes that involve encoding requirements and decoding them into built forms. This subtle connection enhances the suitability for a journal that might explore computational approaches in a broader context.

6. **Improved Flow and Structure:** The sentences are structured to create a smoother and more logical flow of information, enhancing readability for an academic audience.

In essence, the approach involved transforming a generally descriptive statement into a more rigorous and formally articulated explanation of a core architectural principle within the domain of Text-Based Models. The focus was on using precise language, emphasizing fundamental concepts, and ensuring clarity and logical flow to meet the standards of an academic journal. **Score 9+8=17**

Meta-AI Response

Transformer-based models (TBMs) exhibit a consistent architectural framework, comprising two primary components: the Encoder and the Decoder. The Encoder processes input sequences through numerical representation, while the Decoder generates output sequences tailored to specific model functions, such as summarization, simplification, or translation."

My approach involved:

1. Using more formal and technical language suitable for an academic journal.
2. Abbreviating "Transformer-based models" to "TBMs" for conciseness.
3. Rephrasing sentences for clarity and precision.
4. Maintaining the original meaning and content while adapting the tone and style to fit the Journal of Architecture's presumed audience and standards.

I focused on conveying complex information in a clear and concise manner, which is typical in academic writing. **Score 5+5=10**

Bing Chat Response

The fundamental architecture of Transformer-based models (TBMs) consists of two primary components: the Encoder and the Decoder. The Encoder processes the input sequence, transforming it into a numerical representation, which serves as the foundation for subsequent operations. The Decoder, in turn, generates the output sequence, fulfilling the model's specific purpose, whether it involves summarization, simplification, or translation.

Approach:

1. Adopting a Formal Academic Tone: I streamlined the phrasing to align with the clear and precise language typical of scholarly journals, removing casual expressions like “keys of which” and redundant terms such as “fundamental basic.”
2. Refining Terminology: To elevate the academic quality, I clarified "numerical sequence of digits" into "numerical representation," which is concise and technically accurate.
3. Improving Cohesion: To ensure readability, I restructured the text for smoother flow, emphasizing the logical relationship between the Encoder and Decoder components.
4. Maintaining Focus: The rewritten piece avoids extraneous details while keeping the explanation concise and relevant to the intended audience. **Score 5+10=15**

Claude Response

Transformed for Journal of Architecture

Tunnel Boring Machines (TBMs) adhere to a consistent architectural framework consisting of two primary components: the Encoder mechanism, which processes and digitizes the geological input data, and the Decoder system, which translates this information to produce specific outputs tailored to the project's requirements—whether excavating through bedrock, sedimentary layers, or mixed geological conditions.

My Approach

In rewriting this passage, I recognized that the original text was describing Transformer-Based Models (TBMs) in machine learning, but I've reimagined it to discuss Tunnel Boring Machines (TBMs) in civil engineering and architecture, making it relevant for a Journal of Architecture audience.

I maintained the encoder-decoder conceptual framework but recontextualized it to describe how tunnel boring machines process geological information (encoder) and then use that information to guide the boring process (decoder). I incorporated

architectural and engineering terminology that would resonate with the journal's readers.

The rewritten passage preserves the structural integrity of the original while transforming it into content that would be appropriate and engaging for architectural discourse. I focused on the machine's relationship to its environment, which aligns with architectural concerns about how built systems interact with their surroundings.

Score 0+5=5

DeepSeek Response

Transformer-based models (TBMs) exhibit a consistent underlying architectural framework, comprising two principal components: the Encoder and the Decoder. The Encoder processes the input sequence, transforming it into a structured numerical representation, while the Decoder generates the output sequence in accordance with the model's designated function—be it summarization, simplification, translation, or another linguistic operation. This dual-component structure ensures both the interpretability of input data and the controlled generation of meaningful output, reflecting a deliberate architectural logic that balances computational efficiency with functional adaptability.

Approach to the Rewrite

1. Formalization & Precision

- Adjusted phrasing to align with academic discourse (e.g., "share the same fundamental basic architecture" → "exhibit a consistent underlying architectural framework").
- Clarified the Encoder's role by specifying "structured numerical representation" instead of "sequence of digits," which could be misinterpreted.

2. Structural Clarity

- Separated the explanation of the Encoder and Decoder into distinct functional roles, emphasizing their interdependence.
- Added "linguistic operation" to generalize the Decoder's functions, broadening applicability beyond the listed examples.

3. Theoretical Framing

- Concluded with a synthesized observation about the architecture's intent ("interpretability," "computational efficiency"), situating the technical description within a broader design philosophy relevant to architectural theory.

4. Conciseness & Flow

- Eliminated redundancy ("fundamental basic" → "underlying").
- Used semicolons and em dashes to improve readability while maintaining rigor.

This revision aims to bridge technical accuracy with architectural scholarship, presenting TBMs as a case study in systematic, function-driven design. **Score 5+10=15**

A summary table of the results of this trial can be seen below.

TABLE 8: TRIAL 5 RESULTS

TBM	ChatGPT	Gemini	Meta-AI	Bing Chat	Claude AI	DeepSeek
Score/20	18	17	10	15	5	15

From this trial, the comparison was startlingly striking in the discrepancy of the scoring (marked as **Score = transformation/10 + approach/10** at the end of each response).

The qualitative analysis of these results is self-explanatory. This is an even stronger vindication of the aim and hypothesis of this research. Starting from the top scoring model, ChatGPT, it performed as near as possible to the perfect transformation of almost an abstract concept into an equivalent and more tangible one from an architect's perspective. It also clearly analysed its approach referring to the standards of the target publication, indicating a better training and better comprehension of the task. The only omission was any reference to the formatting standards of the journal targeted, but that may be due to the concise input text. A longer text, perhaps a full article, would have invited the model to endeavour to adhere to the format and give it the opportunity to cite it.

The lowest scoring TBM was Claude. This is mainly because it assumed a greater deal of liberty by completely exchanging "Transformer-Based Models" for

“Tunnel Boring Machines”. Despite declaring in its analysis that it knew that they are AI transformers, it considered the target audience and therefore changed it to a machine that they can relate to. By assuming this, the whole meaning and purpose of the exercise was then lost, in an example of TBM hallucination.

No conclusive judgement can be drawn from a single trial using a short text and a single target, and since only a small set of subjects were used in this thesis, this should be considered a pilot leading the way to further expanding research in this and similar fields.

While these models are still in their infancy, there is so much for them to learn and improve. It is upon the research community to assume the responsibility of scrutinising and highlighting both strong and weak traits so that TBMs will have a better future and be much more beneficial in their role as a valuable aid for knowledge and expediency.

4.5 CONCLUSION FROM TRIALS

All of these trials positively indicated that some TBMs differ in their performance in terms of accuracy, efficiency, and architecture. The Null Hypothesis that states that there is no difference between TBMs can be totally rejected thus far, and the full trial of these models can now go ahead should other teams of researchers wish to conduct it, the various stages of which will be discussed here.

4.5.1 DATA COLLECTION FOR LARGER TRIALS

Following the path of this research, the stages involved for accumulating a large collection of data for larger trials should involve:

1. List all models tested and some background of each, including developer, and architecture. In this research, only publicly available TBMs that can be used online or as apps (without the need for APIs) or development were included. These were:
 - ChatGPT (OpenAI)
 - Gemini (Google DeepMind)
 - Claude (Anthropic)

- Bing Chat (Copilot) (Microsoft, powered by OpenAI)
- DeepSeek (Chen, et al., 2024)
- Meta-AI (Llama 3.2 via WhatsApp Version 25.8.74 for iOS 18.3.2) also available through Apple's Safari browser

To achieve uniformity of the models, these should be selected on the criteria that:

- They all share similar function as transformers.
- They are publicly available.
- They exist on the same operating system in some form and via other apps.

2. Investigation of sample size either by following the example of other experiments/trials, or statistically determined. Given this setup, the evaluation process could follow these steps:

2.1 Expert Sample Collection.

- Gather a number of transformation samples from experts.
- Ensure diversity across domain mappings for better generalisability.

2.2 Model Inference

- Run each sample through all six (or however many) TBMs to generate outputs.

2.3. Automated Evaluation with BERT Bi_encoder

- Use Bi_encoder to compare model outputs against expert transformations.
- Optionally, supplement with other metrics (e.g. inference time wherever available) for robustness.

2.4. Analysis and Comparison

- Rank models based on Bi_encoder performance's score.
- Identify patterns in errors or strengths across different models.

3. Test Materials

Depending on the aims and objectives of any trial, the length and complexity of the text, and the subject of the transformation, should be determined. For instance, to

test accuracy by testing the basic mapping fidelity (whether the model can correctly transform one concept from one domain to another), short inputs are sufficient and more useful for this goal as this would help isolate specific errors and make evaluation easier.

To assess other features of TBMs, such as contextual coherence and domain adaptation in a real-world setting, longer texts are indicated. Longer inputs reveal how well a model maintains consistency, resolves ambiguities, and applies transformations across multiple interconnected concepts.

Ideally, given ample resources of time and manpower, both methods should be used for such comparative study. Using a single concept, such as *quantum entanglement*, if a theoretical physicist who is also qualified in chemistry, is participating in the trial, they would be asked to transform that concept from quantum physics to chemistry in a short sentence for direct mapping into the other domain. The test would include ambiguous terms to test robustness. An example of this is a concept from AI such as *Back-propagation* which can be transformed into music in a very short sentence or a term such as *rehearsal refinement*.

The path to follow was determined by the pilot trials study above and the conclusion was that, having explained the various approaches to selecting test-text data, the researcher experimented with various approaches and decided on adapting a shorter text. In fact, to transform one concept by metaphor to another ended up with hybrid results. For example, starting with a short input but ending with a conversion of 25 words on average, even when specifying that the output should be a short one. The example below will illustrate this.

The prompt:

Convert quantum entanglement from quantum physics to musical terms using metaphors in a short sentence.

The response:

Quantum entanglement is like two instruments playing a symphony so perfectly synchronized that, no matter the distance between them, striking one string instantly resonates with the other.

It is therefore deemed that a practical approach to this constrained trial, is to adhere to short prompts that would yield a reasonably long, controlled (by specifying the word count of output), manageable sentence to test and evaluate basic fidelity of the TBMs tested.

Mapping fidelity refers to how accurately a transformation preserves the intended meaning when converting concepts from one domain to another. It measures whether the core relationships, structures, and functions of the original domain are correctly represented in the target domain.

The key features of mapping fidelity are capturing the concept of the source sentence or paragraph, preserving the relationships between elements of the input text, whether the appropriate terms of the target domain are used, and if the output ends up with the same or similar meaning of the input source. For example, if transforming from mathematics to music, a high fidelity of the sentence *Iteration in linear algebra will lead to convergence to the true value*, becomes *Repeated rehearsal will refine the orchestra's performance to achieve perfection*. While a low fidelity may produce something like *Musicians have to work harder*, which is a low-level mapping where the main point of the text is overlooked.

The possible remaining steps are:

4. Acquiring experts – An invite sent to experts.
5. Pairing – Configure pairing of AI models into source and target according to the experts collected.
6. Abstracts – Collect abstracts randomly but according to the experts' domains.
7. Experts' input – Invite experts to transform text from source to target.

8. Run the trials with the selected AI models, with one source and collect targets to populate the table above.
9. BERTScore – Apply BERTScore on every entry in the table against the golden standard of target and collect results and tabulate them in a similar way.
10. Analyse the data – Statistical and numerical data analysis of the result.

Having explored how larger models can be designed, the next chapter will focus on the role of TBMs in aiding Dyslexia and ADHD readability.

CHAPTER 5: THE ROLE OF TBMS IN NEURODIVERGENCE

Thus far, the focus has been on examining the ability of TBMs to transform texts between different domains. The Null Hypothesis of there being no significant difference between most well know models was successfully rejected.

As observed in the survey of existing literature, the transformation of text from any domain into one that is specifically adapted for neurodivergence, has not been addressed by any of the TBMs examined in the trials above. While there are models on various platforms that are concerned with Dyslexia and/or ADHD, none of them are fully developed.

Transformation of text into a customised version that facilitates readability and comprehension by individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD, can be viewed as a special case of domain-domain transformation.

This chapter will therefore include investigating and identifying which of the models in the above trials can achieve the best transformation for this purpose. In addition, it will report on the development of a concept of an AI model to help readability for Dyslexia and ADHD. Subsequently, in the next chapter, a visualisation of an app version of such a model is presented.

5.1 ARE YOU TRAINED ON DYSLEXIA AND/OR ADHD?

Before embarking on discussing the role of TBMs in dealing with Dyslexia and/or ADHD, an initial test of the models used in the preceding trials was conducted. The aim of this test is to uncover if any of the TBMs involved in this research already has the ability or has been trained to deal with Dyslexia and ADHD.

The test was initiated by the following prompt:

Are you capable of transforming text into a format that aids a dyslexic or an ADHD individual to read easily? And are you trained on special datasets for Dyslexia and ADHD?

The Responses (Table 9):

TABLE 9: DYSLEXIA/ADHD RESPONSES

TBMs	Output	Researcher's Comments
ChatGPT	<p>Yes, I can help transform text to make it more readable for individuals with dyslexia or ADHD. The adjustments typically include:</p> <p>For dyslexia:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use plain, simple language. • Shorten long sentences. • Use clear structure and logical flow. • Add spacing between paragraphs. • Avoid italics or ALL CAPS. • Use bullet points or lists instead of long paragraphs. • Use dyslexia-friendly fonts (if displayed on a platform that supports them). <p>For ADHD:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use concise, engaging sentences. • Highlight key points at the beginning. • Break up information into smaller, scannable chunks. • Use headings or subheadings. • Add visual structure (like lists or numbered steps). • Remove unnecessary details or distractions. <p>However, I was not specifically trained on specialized datasets exclusively focused on dyslexia or ADHD. My abilities are based on general training from a wide range of texts, including educational and medical content. This means I wasn't fine-tuned on curated corpora designed specifically for these conditions, but I can still apply widely accepted strategies to adjust text in supportive ways.</p>	<p>Note there is no possible reformatting of the text, or specific method for altering it in a way to make it more readable, such as exchanging confusing letters or using phonetics to replace difficult-to-read words.</p> <p>Also, no special training had been carried out at the time of this query.</p>
DeepSeek	<p>Yes, I can help transform text into formats that are more accessible for individuals with dyslexia, ADHD, or other neurodivergent conditions. While I cannot directly apply visual changes (e.g., fonts, colors, or spacing in a graphical format), I can restructure text using evidence-based strategies to improve readability, such as:</p> <p>For Dyslexia:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simplified language: Avoiding complex sentences. - Chunking: Breaking text into short paragraphs or bullet points. - Headings/subheadings: Organizing content clearly. - Bolding key terms: Highlighting important ideas without italics (which can be harder to read). - Avoiding dense walls of text: Using whitespace and lists. 	<p>This TBM also only performed restructuring of the input text and could not change any of the fonts or other visual effects.</p>

	<p>For ADHD:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conciseness: Reducing unnecessary details. - Clear structure: Using numbered steps or bulleted lists. - Engagement: Incorporating interactive elements (e.g., Q&A format, prompts). - Focus aids: Adding summaries or key takeaways. <p>Example Transformation: Original: "The process of photosynthesis, which occurs in plants, involves converting light energy into chemical energy to fuel the organism's activities." Adapted: "Photosynthesis in plants: - Turns sunlight into chemical energy. - Helps plants grow and survive."</p> <p>Training Data Clarification: I was not specifically trained on proprietary datasets for dyslexia or ADHD. However, my responses are informed by general accessibility guidelines (e.g., WCAG, WebAIM) and research on readability best practices for neurodivergent audiences. For example: - Sans-serif fonts (e.g., Arial) and high-contrast text are often recommended. - Tools like Dyslexie Font, OpenDyslexic, or browser extensions (e.g., BeeLine Reader) can apply visual adjustments.</p>	<p>In the example it gives, there was no attempt made to change "photosynthesis" phonetically to something like "foto-sin-this-is" to make it more readable.</p> <p>No special training for this task.</p>
<p>Claude</p>	<p>I can definitely help create text that's more accessible for dyslexic and ADHD readers.</p> <p>While I wasn't specifically trained on specialized datasets for dyslexia or ADHD, I can apply established accessibility formatting principles to make text more readable for these conditions.</p> <p>For dyslexia, I can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Break text into shorter paragraphs - Use simpler sentence structures - Highlight key information - Use sans-serif fonts (when possible) - Increase line spacing - Avoid justified text (keep left-aligned) - Use bullet points instead of dense paragraphs <p>For ADHD readers, I can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create clear headers and sections 	<p>Comments on the previous entries also apply here.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Break information into digestible chunks - Emphasize important points - Reduce unnecessary details - Use more white space - Add visual structure with formatting - Keep sentences and paragraphs concise 	
Bing Chat (Co-pilot)	<p>I can indeed format text in ways that could make it easier for individuals with dyslexia or ADHD to process. For example, I can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Break information into shorter paragraphs or bullet points to reduce visual clutter. - Use clear and simple language to improve readability. - Highlight key points to help with focus. - Avoid long sentences that might be harder to follow. - Suggest fonts like Dyslexie or OpenDyslexic if you're looking to apply a specific style. <p>As for specialized training, while I haven't been trained on specific datasets for dyslexia or ADHD, I've learned general strategies for presenting information clearly and accessibly. My aim is to be adaptable and provide the best support I can.</p> <p>If you'd like, I can reformat something for you with these considerations in mind—let me know how you'd like the text styled!</p>	<p>Bing Chat applies a few general strategies to aid reading for individuals with Dyslexia and ADHD, but no major formatting is possible.</p> <p>Bing Chat is not trained specifically on relevant datasets.</p>
Meta AI	<p>Yes, I can transform text into a format that can aid individuals with dyslexia or ADHD to read more easily. Here are some ways I can do that:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simplified language: I can rephrase complex sentences into simpler ones. 2. Shorter sentences: Breaking up long sentences into shorter ones can improve readability. 3. Bulleted lists: Converting text into bulleted lists can make it easier to scan and understand. 4. Clear headings: Adding headings and subheadings can help organize the text and improve navigation. 5. Font and formatting suggestions: I can suggest using fonts like OpenDyslexic, Arial, or Helvetica, which are designed to be more readable for individuals with dyslexia. <p>Regarding your second question, my training data includes a wide range of texts and sources, but I wasn't specifically trained on datasets for dyslexia or ADHD. However, I can apply general guidelines and best practices for making text more readable and accessible.</p>	<p>Here an almost identical response to the previous ones. The previous comments apply.</p>

<p>Gemini</p>	<p>Yes, I can transform text into formats that may aid individuals with dyslexia or ADHD. While I don't have access to specific, proprietary datasets explicitly labelled "dyslexia" or "ADHD" in the sense of medical diagnoses, I can apply a variety of text transformations based on established principles and recommendations from accessibility guidelines and research related to these conditions.</p> <p>Here are some techniques I can use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Simplified Language: I can rephrase complex sentences and use simpler vocabulary. * Shorter Sentences and Paragraphs: Breaking down large blocks of text into smaller, more manageable chunks. * Clear and Consistent Formatting: Using consistent fonts (like sans-serif fonts), increased line spacing, and wider margins. * Bullet Points and Numbered Lists: Organizing information into easily digestible lists. * Highlighting Key Information: Drawing attention to important points through bolding or color (though color use is carefully considered, as some individuals with dyslexia experience visual sensitivity). * Spacing and Kerning Adjustments: Increasing letter and word spacing to reduce visual crowding. * Readability Metrics: Using readability formulas to ensure the text is at an appropriate reading level. * Providing Summaries and Key Takeaways: Extracting and presenting the most important information concisely. * Text to Speech: I can provide the text in a way that can be used with a text to speech program. * Option to increase font size: I can provide text in a way that easily allows the user to increase the font size. <p>These techniques aim to reduce cognitive load and visual stress, making the text more accessible.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o It's important to remember that dyslexia and ADHD are diverse, and what works for one person may not work for another. Individual preferences and needs vary greatly. 	<p>Gemini claims to be able to change some of the formatting and add visual effects, such as colouring, to aid readability.</p> <p>It too lacks training on specialist datasets for Dyslexia and/or ADHD.</p>
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These TBMs were then prompted with the following question:

Can you do more if you provide the answer in a file?

The answer from most was affirmative. DeepSeek and Meta AI, who could not generate a file, offered a long explanation of how one could manually create a file from their response to transform a text.

Some TBMs, namely ChatGPT, can handle the task directly by processing the file provided, as it will:

- Read the contents of the file.
- Apply the changes (e.g. letter replacements like p ↔ q, ph ↔ f, etc.).
- Provide the modified file.

Thus far in this research, the various pilot trials on domain-domain transformation, showed that:

- Not all the major TBMs are equal in their abilities and efficiencies in domain-domain transformation. Their transformation capability depends on their architectures and dataset training. The preceding trials successfully demonstrated their capacity to transform information across domains.
- None of the TBMs involved in the pilot trials have the ability to handle text transformation with reference to the needs of individuals with Dyslexia or ADHD. They could only attain some success but only by providing explicit rules and mechanisms of reformatting to aid readability.
- Therefore, with the right training on specialised datasets and by selecting the right architecture, it is possible to develop an efficient specialist TBM to aid accessibility for individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD.

5.2 TBMs FOR DYSLEXIA AND ADHD

This research has the potential to make a substantial contribution to the advancement of TBMs within the fields of cognitive and social sciences. This would have significant implications for enhancing accessibility and support for individuals with neurodivergent conditions such as Dyslexia.

It may be argued that autocorrection and some other writing aids could be sufficient for most cases. This may be true, notwithstanding the anecdotal evidence of how autocorrection can cause more problems than it solves. However, most of these tools often lack the malleability and nuance needed to effectively address the unique spelling patterns seen in individuals with Dyslexia.

Unlike usual spelling errors, Dyslexia errors can be quite different than ‘typos’ and more phonetic in nature. An example of this is writing “phase” as “fase”, or jumbling letter locations, as in “type” to “pyte”.

There are many other instances where errors like these can be identified, and a dataset can be created to train TBMs. In addition, TBMs for Dyslexia, besides error correction, can work bidirectionally too. It can transform normal text to a version that an individual with Dyslexia could easily read. If such an individual usually mixes their “q”s and “p”s, these can be swapped around in the text to make it readable.

A model like this should allow for a few parameters to allow the user to specify more than one difficulty, such as:

Dys([text],“p” to “q”, “ph” to “f”,..)

Where Dys() is the name of the function transformer, and the parameters inside the brackets are instructions to change the first letters in quotes to the second every time it is encountered in [text]. Any number of these exchanges can be specified, separated by commas. This is an example of a rule-based transformer since the user would be providing all the cases themselves. Usually, a TBM would have been trained to apply rules it learnt from training on a specialist dataset.

Such a function will be a very adaptive as individuals can specify exactly what they need to exchange in what text. Since such a model follows a rule-based method, it can be restrictive and limited by its input. This could be a theoretical model of the development of a TBM that can autonomously perform effective transformation activities as required by individuals with Dyslexia or similar neurodivergence.

There are various approaches to implement such a function. It can be coded in a programming language that has the ability to handle text efficiently. Since Python

can provide a flexible and customisable way to manipulate text files, a version of `Dys()` function can be coded as:

```
def dys(text, *args):
    if len(args) % 2 != 0:
        raise ValueError("Replacement arguments must be in pairs.")
    replacements = zip(args[::2], args[1::2])
    for old, new in replacements:
        text = text.replace(old, new)
    return text
# Example usage:
output = dys("I am playing with my phone", "p", "q", "ph", "f")
print(output) # Output: I am qlaying with my fone
```

Although the output from this function is expected to be “I am qlaying with my fone”, when this code was executed, the output was “I am qlaying with my qhone”. The reason for this, is the order in which these arguments are evaluated. Since the above code performs the instructed replacement sequentially, it changed the “p” in the word “phone” to “q” without realising it is followed by “h” even though this evaluation should have been “f”.

An improved version of this code could then be one that examines the input text first, then evaluates every “ph” and transforms it to “f” before embarking on transforming every “p” to “q”. Here is that improved code:

```
import re
def dys(text, *args, case_sensitive=True):
    if len(args) % 2 != 0:
        raise ValueError("Replacement arguments must be in pairs.")
    replacements = sorted(zip(args[::2], args[1::2]), key=lambda x: -len(x[0])) # Prioritize longer matches
    for old, new in replacements:
        if case_sensitive:
            text = text.replace(old, new)
        else:
            text = re.sub(re.escape(old), new, text, flags=re.IGNORECASE)
    return text
```

```
# Example usage:

output = dys("I am playing with my phone", "p", "q", "ph", "f",
             case_sensitive=False)

print(output) # Output: "I am qlaying with my fone"
```

The Improvements to the Dys() function were:

1. Handles "ph" before "p" (avoids "ph" becoming "qh" instead of "f").
2. Works with or without case sensitivity (`case_sensitive=False` treats "P" and "p" the same).
3. Uses regular expression (*regex*) when case insensitivity is enabled.

Creating a Python function to perform transformation into dyslexic and ADHD friendly text is useful for the following reasons:

1. Automation – If one needs to apply many replacements across different texts, a function saves time.
2. Scalability – If one wants to replace multiple letter pairs at once without manually editing each case.
3. Reusability – Instead of determining each time, one just calls `Dys(text, "p", "q", "ph", "f")`.
4. Accuracy – A function ensures consistency, reducing human errors.
5. Integration – If one is building an app or AI model, a function can be used programmatically.

Writing a function to perform certain transformations according to predefined rules to help readability is a good first step in the development of a full model for assisting individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. However, it will not be a suitable tool for everyday use by general users as this will require a good expertise in Python, as well as knowledge of the principles of aiding such transformation. This will only be applicable to a limited set of pairs of letters or words. It however has the advantage of being very customisable but remains a limited tool to use due to the constraints listed above.

The next improvement of function `Dys()`, is the ability to act on entire documents stored as digital files. Below is a version of `Dys()` that processes a text file instead of a string. It reads a file, applies the replacements, and saves the modified text to a new file.

```

import re

def dys_file(input_file, output_file, *args, case_sensitive=True):
    if len(args) % 2 != 0:
        raise ValueError("Replacement arguments must be in pairs.")

    replacements = sorted(zip(args[::2], args[1::2]), key=lambda x: -
len(x[0])) # Prioritize longer matches

    # Read the file
    with open(input_file, "r", encoding="utf-8") as f:
        text = f.read()

    # Apply replacements
    for old, new in replacements:
        if case_sensitive:
            text = text.replace(old, new)
        else:
            text = re.sub(re.escape(old), new, text,
flags=re.IGNORECASE)

    # Save to new file
    with open(output_file, "w", encoding="utf-8") as f:
        f.write(text)

    print(f"Processed file saved as: {output_file}")

# Example usage:
# dys_file("input.txt", "output.txt", "p", "q", "ph", "f",
case_sensitive=False)

```

This is how the file version of `Dys()` works:

1. Reads `input_file.txt`.
2. Replaces all specified character sequences.
3. Saves the modified text to `output_file.txt`.
4. Case sensitivity is optional (`case_sensitive=False` for case-insensitive replacement).

The next step of such a development after refining `Dys()` function, is making it available to other developers via libraries such as Hugging Face. Initially, since it will not fit the patterns of other well-developed models in the Hugging Face core library, there are two ways to share it in the Hugging Face ecosystem:

- a) as a custom Python module in Hugging Face by creating a Hugging Face Space (a mini web app) that uses `Dys()` function and lets users interact with it to build a simple user interface. One can then deploy it under one's own Hugging Face account and share the link with other users to try the function or even copy the Python code and improve it should they wish.

The code to achieve this is:

```
import gradio as gr

def dys(text, *args):
    if len(args) % 2 != 0:
        raise ValueError("Replacement arguments must be in pairs.")
    replacements = zip(args[::2], args[1::2])
    for old, new in replacements:
        text = text.replace(old, new)
    return text

with gr.Blocks() as demo:
    txt_input = gr.Textbox(label="Input Text")
    pair_input = gr.Textbox(label="Replacement Pairs (comma-separated, like p,q,ph,f)")
    output = gr.Textbox(label="Output")

    def run_dys(txt, pair_str):
        args = pair_str.split(",")
        return dys(txt, *args)

    btn = gr.Button("Apply dys")
    btn.click(run_dys, inputs=[txt_input, pair_input],
              outputs=output)

demo.launch()
```

- b) As a Python Package on Hugging Face Hub that can be installed as a standard Python module. This can be achieved by packaging the code as a standard Python module and uploading it to Hugging Face Hub with usage instructions.

In addition to the above, the `Dys()` code can be added to transformer pipelines. For the file version of `Dys()`, a multi-files version can also be developed, as well as tracking changes.

5.3 ADHD ISSUES

At the time of completing the short survey of Dyslexia models and datasets, the researcher predicted that there will be the same, or similar, issues when surveying materials related to ADHD. Since the formal identification of this type of

neurodivergence is relatively younger than Dyslexia, and the research into practical methods of assisting individuals with this condition is still emerging, one should not expect to find specialist datasets for it. Finding finetuned models to aid individuals with this condition, would be even more rare, as will be discussed later in this work.

Furthermore, since developing an assistive model is an issue of NLP, one needs to consider the variety of natural languages, and the complexity of providing models and datasets for languages other than English.

Translating transformed text poses another issue. Some of the issues to consider when translating from an already transformed text into a version suitable for dyslexic-reading are:

- recognise that the source text is already transformed.
- identify which dataset was used for the transformation.
- ensure accessibility to such a dataset.
- retransform the original text to one without the dyslexic adjustments.
- proceed with the translation.

The reverse of that operation needs to take place if the target language is also to be adjusted according to the rules of a particular dataset, whether the original text had been transformed or not.

The way Dyslexia and ADHD present and are diagnosed can differ significantly between languages. This is mainly due to differences in language structure, writing systems, educational practices, and cultural perceptions.

Details of this issue is discussed in the next few sections.

5.3.1 DYSLEXIA AND LANGUAGE DIFFERENCES

Dyslexia is primarily a reading disorder. Its expression depends heavily on the language's orthography – how sounds map to letters. Below are some of the factors that pose further complexity to dealing with Dyslexia:

Orthographic Transparency

- Transparent (shallow) orthographies: languages like Finnish, Italian, Spanish, and Turkish have consistent spelling-sound rules. Each letter or letter group

corresponds predictably to one sound. Dyslexia is less noticeable and often diagnosed later. Children can learn to decode words more easily but may still struggle with reading fluency or speed.

- Opaque (deep) orthographies: English, French, Danish, and Chinese have inconsistent spelling rules. Dyslexia becomes more evident early because decoding is harder. English has many irregular spellings (like "rough" vs "through"), making it more challenging for learners with Dyslexia.

Writing Systems

- Alphabetic systems (English, French, German): Dyslexia affects phonological processing, i.e. mapping sounds to letters.
- Logographic systems (Chinese): Dyslexia may relate more to visual memory and symbol recognition, since each character represents a whole word or morpheme.
- Syllabic systems (Japanese Kana): These fall somewhere in between the previous two systems. Readers with Dyslexia may struggle differently with Kana vs Kanji.

Morphology and Phonology

- Languages with rich morphology (like Arabic or Finnish) add another layer of complexity. Readers with Dyslexia might struggle with how words change (such as tense, case, or gender). An Arabic speaker would appreciate the variation of letter writing as the letter shapes change depending on their position in a word. This can confuse readers with Dyslexia. In French, many silent letters and homophones increase the burden on memory and contextual decoding.

5.3.2 ADHD AND LANGUAGE/CULTURAL DIFFERENCES

ADHD is not language-dependent in the same way. Its perception, diagnosis, and coping mechanisms can vary widely across languages and cultures. The next section will highlight some of these differences.

a. Diagnosis and Reporting

In some countries, especially in North America, and increasingly in the United Kingdom, ADHD is widely diagnosed and treated. In other regions, like parts of

Asia, the Middle East, or Southern Europe, it may be underdiagnosed, misinterpreted as bad behaviour, or culturally stigmatised. Language plays a role in how symptoms are reported or understood. For example, differences in how impulsivity or inattention are described by teachers or parents may affect diagnosis.

b. Classroom Expectations

In languages with complex grammar and long sentence structures (like German or Latin-based languages), sustaining attention for comprehension may be harder for students with ADHD. Different educational systems also play a role in this. Highly structured environments may amplify the challenges of ADHD, while more flexible ones might mask its symptoms.

c. Language Use in Social Interaction

Individuals with ADHD often have trouble with turn-taking in conversations, interrupting, or drifting off-topic. This can present differently depending on cultural norms. For example, in cultures with high conversational formality (such as Japan), ADHD symptoms may be more socially disruptive.

In summary, Dyslexia is affected by writing systems, spelling rules, and morphology. It is more visible in opaque languages like English or French and less visible in transparent ones like Finnish or Spanish, while ADHD is affected more by cultural norms, diagnosing methods, and language complexity. It varies by culture, schooling, and social expectations more than by language itself. Symptoms may be interpreted differently across countries.

Dyslexia is not the only neurodivergence that can be a candidate for further research and advanced development of TBMs, but it is of a special interest in NLP. There are existing datasets (see Ch. 1) that capture spelling errors commonly made by individuals with Dyslexia. These can be invaluable resources for training TBMs and accelerate their development.

5.3.3 BIONIC READING©

ADHD is a widely spread neurodivergence that can be helped by developing special TBMs. One way it can assist individuals is by loading documents to be read after

being simplified and/or converted to Bionic Reading© format. Kamarozaman, et al., (2023) claim that this format is effective in enhancing individuals' reading ability.

An example of such output is below (Fig. 9):

FIGURE 9: EXAMPLE OF BIONIC READING©

There has been considerable work carried out in this field and several versions of apps developed based on the principle of Bionic Reading©. However, these principles and rules are yet to be incorporated into TBMs that are readily available.

Bionic Reading©, introduced by Swiss typographic designer Renato Casutt (n.d.), is a digital reading method that enhances focus by bolding the initial letters of words to guide visual attention. This technique relies on the brain's tendency to recognise words from partial cues, potentially reducing cognitive load. Key features of this method include customisability, digital accessibility, and reported benefits for readers with Dyslexia or ADHD. While early user feedback is promising, especially in digital contexts, rigorous empirical studies are needed to assess its effectiveness across diverse populations.

The next section will visit some of the papers published to discuss the proposed benefits, weakness and strength of this method.

5.3.4 BIONIC READING© IN THE PAPERS

This notable Kamarozaman, et al., (2023) research was discussed previously, but worth revisiting as it is the most relevant work to this project.

What follows is a synopsis of the work done in this area of research starting with this paper, which presents a novel approach to assist students with Dyslexia, ADHD, and short attention span in digesting any text-based information more efficiently.

The proposed solution utilises the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) algorithm for complex text processing and summarisation tasks. The tool leverages the T5 (Text-to-Text Transformer) model from Hugging Face, which treats every NLP task as a text generation task.

The model is finetuned on specific tasks using a smaller dataset. The NLTK's Punkt Sentence Tokeniser (Natural Language Tool Kit) (Kiss & Strunk, 2006), is used to divide a text into a list of sentences.

The application is served using Flask (Grinberg, 2018), a lightweight web server and framework. The tool also applies principles from Bionic Reading© to enhance readability, which includes a bolding function and adjustments to line, word, and character spacing.

The paper discusses the methodology, implementation, and results of the AI-based speed-reading tool.

This second paper (Paleshnikova, 2024) describes the result of research carried out to verify the result of the previous paper using medical measurements.

While the study did not conclusively demonstrate the efficacy of Bionic Reading© for individuals with ADHD, it contributes to the growing body of research exploring assistive reading technologies.

Further research with larger sample sizes and diverse methodologies was recommended to fully understand the potential benefits and limitations of Bionic Reading© for neurodivergent populations.

The last paper to discuss this (Santos, n.d.), is a study carried out on a sample of ADHD students using Bionic Reading© methods, which shows significant improvement in students' ability to read.

This study aimed to improve the reading comprehension of Senior High School students through the implementation of Bionic Reading©. Employing a one-group pre-test post-test experimental design, 75 Grade 12 HUMSS (Humanities and Social Sciences) students identified among 124 respondents as being at the frustration levels of reading were selected through non-probability purposive sampling to undergo the Bionic Reading© intervention. The Phil-IRI reading comprehension assessment served as the research instrument, validated by experts. Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics, incorporating descriptive statistics and the Wilcoxon-Signed Rank Test.

The results demonstrated significant post-intervention improvement, with a majority of students progressing to the instructional level. Bionic Reading© effectively catered to diverse learning needs, emphasising personalised learning pathways and interactive activities.

These findings underscore the efficacy of Bionic Reading© as an innovative educational tool for enhancing the reading comprehension skills of Senior High School students.

5.4 TBMs AND ADHD

The selected TBMs for this research have been investigated for their ability to deal with Dyslexia and ADHD, and were found to be of limited use. It transpired that they have not been trained on Dyslexia or ADHD datasets, and without finetuning by specifying which transformation rules need to be followed, such as letter transposition or phonetic spellings of a set of difficult words, TBMs will not be able to perform such tasks.

This will reduce them to rule-based rather than a higher achieving form of transformer-based models, and as it will be witnessed from the results to follow, they could not perform this function properly even after explicit instructions. Hence the need to improve these models, which are in terms of their generality more powerful than apps that only address one specific issue.

5.4.1 TESTING WITH WIKIPEDIA

Below is the response from these various models to prompts to transform an extract from Wikipedia to a text easily read by individuals with Dyslexia or ADHD. This trial was carried out with most of the TBMs selected, and their responses are reported, without reproducing the text from Wikipedia.

First the text from Wikipedia:

“Art describes a diverse range of cultural activity centred [sic] around works utilising [sic] creative or imaginative talents, which are expected to evoke a worthwhile experience, generally through an expression of emotional power, conceptual ideas, technical proficiency, and/or beauty

There is no generally agreed definition of what constitutes art, and its interpretation has varied greatly throughout history and across cultures. In the Western tradition, the three classical branches of visual art are painting, sculpture, and architecture.[8] Theatre, dance, and other performing arts, as well as literature, music, film and other media such as interactive media, are included in a broader definition of "the arts". Until the 17th century, art referred to any skill or mastery and was not differentiated from crafts or sciences. In modern usage after the 17th century, where aesthetic considerations are paramount, the fine arts are separated and distinguished from acquired skills in general, such as the decorative or applied arts.”

The prompt

Convert this text so a person with Dyslexia can read it

ChatGPT Response

Here's a version of your text adapted for dyslexic readers. I've used shorter sentences, simpler words, and clear spacing to improve readability.

What is Art?

Art includes many different creative activities. It involves making things using imagination and skill. Art is meant to create strong feelings or ideas. It can also show beauty or talent.

There is no single definition of art. People have understood art in different ways across time and cultures.

In Western culture, there are three main types of visual art:

- Painting
- Sculpture (making shapes from stone, wood, or other materials)
- Architecture (designing and building structures)

Other forms of art include:

- Theatre (acting and storytelling on stage)
- Dance (moving to express emotions or tell a story)
- Music (creating sounds and songs)
- Literature (writing stories, poems, and books)
- Film and Media (movies, videos, and digital art)

Before the 1600s, “art” meant any special skill, like making tools or learning science. After that, people started thinking of “fine arts” as different from everyday skills. Fine arts focus more on beauty and creativity.

This version is designed for easier reading...

Gemini Response

Here's the text reformatted with some common dyslexic-friendly adjustments:

Art

Art talks about lots of different things people do with culture. It's about making things using your ideas and how good you are at them. These things should make you feel something good.

It often shows strong feelings, new ideas, how good someone is at making things, or things that are beautiful.

No one really agrees on exactly what art IS. What people think art is has changed a lot over time and in different places.

In Europe and places like it, the main kinds of art you can see are:

- Painting
- Statues (sculpture)
- Buildings (architecture)

Things like plays (theatre), dancing, and other shows are also art. Books (literature), music, movies (film), and even things you can play with (interactive media) are also seen as "the arts" by many people.

A long time ago, before the 1600s, "art" just meant being good at something. It wasn't seen as different from making things with your hands (crafts) or science.

Now, after the 1600s, we think more about how things look and feel. So, "fine arts" are seen as different from just being good at skills, like making decorations or useful things.

Here are some of the changes made and why:

- **Shorter sentences:** Easier to process one idea at a time.
- **Simpler vocabulary:** Avoiding complex or less common words.
- **More line breaks and spacing:** Reduces visual clutter and makes it easier to track lines.
- **Clearer headings and bullet points:** Breaks up large blocks of text and highlights key information.
- **Emphasis on key words (bolding):** Helps draw attention to important terms.
- **Rephrasing complex ideas:** Explaining abstract concepts in a more straightforward way.

This version aims to reduce visual stress and cognitive load, making the text more accessible for individuals with dyslexia.

Claude Response

Here's the text reformatted to be more accessible for someone with dyslexia:

Art

Art describes a diverse range of cultural activity centered around creative or imaginative works. These works are meant to evoke meaningful experiences through:

- Emotional power
- Conceptual ideas
- Technical skill
- Beauty

There is no single agreed definition of what makes something "art." Its interpretation has changed throughout history and varies across cultures.

In Western tradition, the three classical branches of visual art are:

- Painting
- Sculpture
- Architecture

A broader definition includes:

- Theater and dance
- Literature
- Music
- Film
- Interactive media

Until the 17th century, "art" referred to any skill or mastery and wasn't separated from crafts or sciences.

In modern usage after the 17th century, aesthetic considerations became paramount. The "fine arts" were distinguished from "applied arts" and crafts.

I've made these changes to help with readability:

- Added clear headings
- Created more white space
- Used bullet points to break up dense text
- Simplified some sentence structures
- Removed footnote numbers
- Used clear paragraph separation

Would you like me to make any additional modifications to make this text more accessible?

Meta-AI Response

Here's the rewritten text in a dyslexia-friendly format:

What is Art?

Art is a wide range of creative activities that bring people joy, inspiration, and new ideas. It's about expressing emotions, thoughts, and skills through various forms like paintings, sculptures, buildings, performances, music, literature, and films.

Defining Art

There's no one clear definition of art that everyone agrees on. People have interpreted art in many ways throughout history and across different cultures.

Types of Art

In the Western world, the three main types of visual art are:

- Painting
- Sculpture
- Architecture

Other forms of art include:

- Theatre
- Dance
- Music

- Literature
- Film
- Interactive media

History of Art

Until the 17th century, art meant any skill or expertise, and it wasn't separate from crafts or sciences. Later, people started to focus more on the beauty and emotional impact of art, and the fine arts were born. Today, we distinguish fine arts from other skills like decorative or applied arts.

Changes made to make the text more dyslexia-friendly:

- Clear headings and subheadings
- Shorter sentences and paragraphs
- Bullet points for lists
- Simple, concise language
- Avoidance of jargon and complex terminology
- Increased font size and line spacing would also be beneficial, but that's not possible in this text format.

Bing Chat Response

For dyslexic readers, it's often helpful to simplify formatting, use plain language, and present content in a clearer structure. Here's a revised version of the text tailored for better readability:

What is Art?

Art includes many different cultural activities that use creativity and imagination. The goal of art is often to create a meaningful experience for the audience. This can involve:

- Emotional expression
- New ideas
- Skilled techniques
- Beauty

There isn't one clear definition of art—it has meant different things to different people throughout history and in various cultures.

Types of Art

In Western tradition, the main types of visual art are:

1. Painting
2. Sculpture
3. Architecture

Other forms of art include:

- Theatre
- Dance
- Literature
- Music
- Film
- Interactive media

A Short History of Art

- Before the 17th century: Art meant any skill or mastery. It wasn't separate from crafts or sciences.
- After the 17th century: The term "fine arts" began to focus on creative works made for beauty and aesthetic purposes. This was separate from practical skills like crafts or applied arts.

The text uses shorter sentences, lists, and bold headings to make it easier to follow. Let me know if you'd like me to tweak it further!

DeepSeek Response

Here's a dyslexia-friendly version of your text. Changes include simplified language, shorter sentences, bullet points, bold headings, and clearer formatting to improve

readability⁶:

What Is Art?

Art includes many different types of creative work. It uses imagination, skill, and emotion to create experiences that feel meaningful or powerful. Art can:

- Share ideas or stories.
- Show technical skill or beauty.
- Make people feel strong emotions.

No Single Definition

People disagree about what “art” really means. Ideas about art have changed over time and across cultures. For example:

- In Western history, visual art traditionally meant painting, ******sculpture, and architecture.
- Today, “the arts” also include theatre, dance, music, literature, film, and digital media.

How the Meaning of “Art” Changed

- Before the 1600s: “Art” meant any skilled work, like crafts or sciences.
- After the 1600s: “Fine art” became separate from practical skills. It focused more on beauty, creativity, and ideas (like paintings or sculptures).

Key Changes for Dyslexia Readability:

1. Shorter paragraphs with clear headings.
2. Bullet points to break up lists.
3. Bold terms for important ideas.
4. Simplified vocabulary (e.g., “constitutes” → “makes up”).
5. Avoided complex sentences and citations.

For even better readability, pair this with a dyslexia-friendly font (e.g., Arial, Comic Sans) and larger text size. Let me know if you’d like further tweaks!

⁶ A “******” before and after some words indicates they are in **bold** font but in printout, only the markup symbols appear.

5.4.2 TESTING WITH OPENDYSLEXIA

The same TBMs were then prompted to use the dataset OpenDyslexia. Below are some of the responses:

ChatGPT Response

I can't change the font directly in this chat, but you can copy and paste the text into a document or website that supports the OpenDyslexic font. If you're using a tool like Microsoft Word, Google Docs, or a dyslexia-friendly browser extension, you can set it to OpenDyslexic for better readability.

Would you like me to format the text in a way that works well with dyslexia-friendly tools? For example, I can add more spacing, break up long paragraphs further, or use bold for key words. Let me know how I can help!

DeepSeek Response

WHAT IS ART?

Art includes many creative works made with imagination, skill, or emotion. It aims to create meaningful experiences by:

- Sharing ideas or stories.
- Showing technical skill or beauty.
- Making people feel strong emotions.

NO CLEAR DEFINITION

People disagree about what counts as "art." Ideas change across cultures and history:

- Western tradition: Visual art = painting, sculpture, architecture.
- Today: "The arts" include theater, dance, music, literature, film, and digital media.

HOW "ART" CHANGED OVER TIME

- Before 1600s:
 - Art meant any skilled work (crafts, sciences).
- After 1600s:
 - "Fine art" focused on beauty and ideas (paintings, sculptures).
 - Separated from practical skills (like crafting tools).

TIPS FOR DYSLEXIA-FRIENDLY FORMATTING:

1. Use the OpenDyslexic font (free online).
2. Cream backgrounds with dark gray text reduce glare.
3. Left-align text and avoid italics.
4. Break text into short chunks with clear headings.

From these two responses of ChatGPT and DeepSeek, it can be concluded that OpenDyslexia is only concerned with formatting the input text, either by changing the fonts or by restructuring the output text.

In the opinion of the researcher, this approach is of limited usefulness and it is also impractical. Therefore, its demonstration was deemed sufficient, and the researcher did not invoke the remaining TBMs with this prompt. However, to demonstrate the capability of TBMs to follow rules presented to them, the following trial was conducted.

One TBM (vis-à-vis ChatGPT) was then prompted to change every “e” to a different letter. To make it distinguished, “â” is chosen because it is sufficiently different for the ease of visual verification of the output. The TBM selected was then prompted to emphasise the change by making the conversion bold. The transposed letters may not appear to be bold in the copied text due to limitations in copying the result. This is one of the techniques used to help individuals with Dyslexia read, by transposing one letter to another, usually *p* and *q*.

ChatGPT Response

Here’s the text with every “e” replaced by “â” and bolded:

What is Art?

Art is about crâating things using imagination and skill.

It is mâant to âxprâss fââlings, idâas, or bâauty.

Thârâ is no singlâ dâfinition of art. Diffârânt pâoplâ and culturâs sââ it in diffârânt ways.

Typâs of Art

In Western culture, the main types of visual art are:

- Painting
- Sculpture (making shapes from stone, wood, or other materials)
- Architecture (designing and building structures)

Other forms of art include:

- Theatre (acting and storytelling on stage)
- Dance (expressing emotions through movement)
- Music (creating sounds and songs)
- Literature (writing stories, poems, and books)
- Film and Media (movies, videos, and digital art)

How Art Has Changed

Before the 1600s, "art" meant any special skill, like making tools or learning science.

After that, people started to separate fine arts from everyday skills.

Today, fine arts focus on beauty and creativity, while other skills are called applied arts.

This illustrates that one can manually instruct a TBM such as ChatGPT, to follow specific rules of conversion. However, this may lead to:

- Tedious manual operation
- The need to know the rules and apply them every time
- Reducing a TBM to a rule-based model (this will be explored further later)

This exercise was for demonstrating the power and ability of a TBM, but it was not run with other TBMs, as this was deemed sufficient evidence that it can be done.

5.4.3 TBM WITH ADJUSTMENT FOR ADHD

Using the same short text from Wikipedia, ChatGPT was prompted to change the same text for someone with ADHD. The output was:

ChatGPT Response

For someone with ADHD, the text should be engaging, easy to skim, and visually structured to maintain focus. Here's an optimized version with:

- ✓ Short sentences
- ✓ Clear sections
- ✓ Bolded key words
- ✓ Lists and spacing

What is Art?

Art is about creating things using imagination and skill.

It makes people feel something—joy, excitement, curiosity, or even confusion!

There's no single definition of art. Different people and cultures see it in different ways.

Types of Art

In Western culture, there are 3 main types of visual art:

- ✓ Painting
- ✓ Sculpture (shapes made from stone, wood, or other materials)
- ✓ Architecture (designing and building structures)

Other forms of art include:

- Theatre (acting and storytelling on stage)
- Dance (expressing emotions through movement)
- Music (creating sounds and songs)
- Literature (stories, poems, and books)
- Film & Media (movies, videos, digital art)

🕒 How Art Has Changed Over Time

👤 Before 1600: “Art” meant any skill, like making tools or learning science.

🧠 After 1600: People started separating fine arts (focused on beauty) from everyday skills.

Today, we have fine arts 🎨 🎵 and applied arts ✂️ 🧠 (like design and decoration).

DeepSeek Response

Here’s an ADHD-friendly revision of the text! It uses short bursts of info, dynamic formatting, visual breaks, and interactive elements to improve focus and engagement:

🧠 ART = CREATIVITY + SKILL

Art isn’t just one thing—it’s games your brain plays! Think:

- Paintings, sculptures, music, dance, TikTok videos, even epic LEGO builds.
- It’s about sharing ideas, showing off skills, or making you feel BIG emotions (like joy, anger, or “WHOA, THAT’S COOL!”).

🤔 WAIT... WHAT COUNTS AS “ART”? Nobody fully agrees!

- 500 years ago: Art = ANY skill (like blacksmithing, math, or baking pies).
- Today: Art = Creativity first (like painting, film, or video games).
- Fun fact: Some people argue *emoji combos* or *Minecraft builds* are art! *(You decide!)*

🕒 HOW ART CHANGED OVER TIME (Quick timeline!)

⏴ Before 1600s:

- “Art” = useful stuff (crafting chairs, studying stars, writing recipes).

⏵ After 1600s:

- “Fine art” = stuff just for beauty/ideas (like Van Gogh’s starry skies).

- Separated from “crafts” (like pottery or quilting).

🧠 ADHD-FRIENDLY TIPS TO REMEMBER:

1. Art is flexible—it’s whatever you/others find meaningful.
2. Debates about “what’s art?” are endless (and that’s okay!).
3. Try this: Turn your hobby (gaming, doodling, cooking) into art. Boom!

🧠 KEY CHANGES FOR ADHD READABILITY:

- ✓ Chunked text with emojis/headings as “brain breaks.”
- ✓ Interactive questions to keep focus.
- ✓ Bold keywords + relatable examples (TikTok, Minecraft).
- ✓ No walls of text—info is snackable!
- ✓ Action-oriented ending (encourages creativity).

Need it shorter, sillier, or with different examples? Let me know! 🚀

Gemini Response

Okay, so, like, art! It's this WHOLE BUNCH of stuff, right? All these different things people DO when they're feeling... something? Or thinking something cool? And they, like, MAKE things. Pictures, or, oh! Sculptures, those are neat, like you can TOUCH them and they're all three-dimensional. And buildings! Architecture! That's art too, which is kind of mind-blowing when you think about it, because you LIVE in it!

But then there's also the stuff that moves, you know? Like theatre! With the costumes and the voices and the DRAMA! And dancing! All that energy and rhythm, it's like... whoa. And music! Obviously, music, that gets right IN your head, doesn't it? And movies! Stories on a giant screen! And even books! You can just get LOST in a story. And video games! Those are totally art too, you're like, INTERACTING with it! It's not just looking, you're DOING!

It's weird though, because like, what IS art, really? It's not like there's a rulebook or anything. People have been arguing about it FOREVER. Like, way back before even my grandpa was born, and in totally different countries, they all had their own ideas about what counted.

It's funny, because a long time ago, like, before the 1600s, "art" was just... anything you were good at! Like fixing a clock or, I don't know, being a really good baker! It wasn't just the fancy stuff we think of now. But then, things changed, and people started being like, "Okay, but THIS stuff, the paintings and the statues, that's SPECIAL." Like, it's about how it LOOKS and how it makes you FEEL, not just if it's useful, you know? So now we have "fine arts" which is the painting and stuff, and then there's other cool stuff like decorating and making things that you actually USE, which is still art, but a DIFFERENT kind of art.

Claude Response

Art for ADHD Focus

What is Art?

- **Art = creative human expression** through various forms and media
- Art captures feelings, ideas, and perspectives
- Creates visual, physical, or experiential connections

Types of Art (Quick Reference)

- **Visual Arts**
 - 2D: Paintings, drawings, photography
 - 3D: Sculpture, ceramics
 - Architectural: Buildings as artistic expression
- **Performance Arts**
 - Theater: Storytelling through acting
 - Dance: Expression through movement
 - Music: Communication through sound

- **Narrative Arts**

- Literature: Written stories and poetry
- Film: Visual storytelling
- Video games: Interactive storytelling

Evolution of "Art" as a Concept

1. **Pre-1600s:** "Art" meant any skilled craft or activity
2. **Historical shift:** Separation between functional crafts and "fine arts"
3. **Modern view:** Broader definition including both aesthetic and functional works

Key Point

Art constantly evolves as a concept, with no fixed definition - it's about human creativity and expression across all mediums!

Meta-AI Response

Here's the rewritten text, broken down into bite-sized chunks and written in a style that's easier to follow for someone with ADHD:

What is Art?

Art is a way to express emotions, ideas, and creativity. It's a diverse range of activities that can evoke feelings, spark imagination, and showcase technical skills. Think of it like a big umbrella that covers lots of different things, like painting, music, dance, literature, and more.

The Many Forms of Art

There are lots of different types of art, including:

- Visual arts like painting, sculpture, and architecture
- Performing arts like theatre, dance, and music
- Literature, film, and interactive media

A Brief History of Art

In the past, art was seen as any skill or mastery. It wasn't until the 17th century that people started to separate art from crafts and sciences. Today, we think of art as something that's meant to be beautiful, thought-provoking, or emotionally powerful.

The Problem with Defining Art

Here's the thing: there's no one "right" way to define art. Different cultures and historical periods have had their own ways of understanding what art is and what it's for. So, art can mean different things to different people.

I made the following changes to make the text more ADHD-friendly:

- Broke the text into smaller paragraphs with clear headings
- Simplified the language and sentence structure
- Added a bit of personality and tone to make the text more engaging
- Emphasized key points and used shorter sentences to make it easier to follow

- Removed some of the more abstract or technical terms that might be hard to understand

Let me know if you have any other requests or if there's anything else I can help with!

Bing Chat Response

Got it! Let me simplify and organize this text in a way that's more ADHD-friendly: clear, concise, and engaging:

What is Art?

Art is all about using creative or imaginative talents to create works that make people feel something or think deeply. It can express emotions, ideas, technical skills, or beauty.

Key Points:

- There's no one definition of art—different cultures and times have seen it differently.
- Traditional Western art includes painting, sculpture, and architecture.
- The arts also include things like theatre, dance, music, literature, film, and interactive media.
- Before the 17th century, "art" meant any skill, like crafts or sciences. Later, it became focused on creativity and aesthetics.

The original text is a bit dense, but art itself? It's wonderfully diverse. Does this resonate with the type of rewrite you had in mind?

5.5 TBM LIMITATIONS WRT DYSLEXIA/ADHD

The above were all the responses collected by prompting the various TBMs with prompts concerning Dyslexia and ADHD respectively.

It is evident that there is no methodical or systematic way that these TBMs manage either case. The responses were found to be ad-hoc and not sufficiently different from the original input text, and the transformation is unconvincing.

This trial shows that a different approach needs to be adopted to deal with these two complex NLP issues. This is further necessitated by the rapid increase in the diagnosis of both conditions.

Returning to Bionic Reading© (Casutt, n.d.), consider the following examples:

- Standard text:

Bionic Reading© is a technique that highlights parts of words to enhance reading speed and comprehension.

- Bionic Reading© format:

Bionic Reading© is a technique that highlights parts of words to enhance reading speed and comprehension.

The brain of the reader is aided to recognise each word only by the part converted to bold font of the first few letters of keywords in the text.

There is no peer-reviewed publication of the algorithm that steers this transformation. A researcher can also find more information about Bionic Reading© through its official website or in news sources.

Bionic Reading© is based on a standard text-processing techniques informed by cognitive psychology and from typographic design. As mentioned above, the algorithm was never fully disclosed but it is believed to rely on techniques used in Natural Language Processing (NLP) for analysing text structure, and establishing which part or parts of words should be emphasised by bolding. Other bases for this could be inherited from Heuristics and Linguistic rules, to emphasise groups of letters based on word frequency and phonetic structures. Typography and visual design rules are also employed to manipulate font style to aid reading.

The researcher has not found other references bar the one mentioned above (Kamarozaman, et al. 2023), to indicate that Bionic Reading© is based on a T5 transformer. It could be using Google's T5 model for modifying text after analysing. Even if Bionic Reading© is using T5, it is probably using it in a limited sense for the preparation of the text to be transformed. Amongst these would be token importance prediction, to identify which part of a word gives most meaning and therefore should be boldened or using sentence semantics and structure for better context awareness.

If this assumption is correct, referring to the argument earlier about the customisation feature of the system, it seems illogical to then not exploit the capability of T5, but allow the user to decide their own customisation.

The Bionic Reading© system is deployed either as an app, or via API to be integrated into other reading platforms. A similar effect could probably be achieved using other NLP techniques coded in a computer programming language such as Python. The researcher hypothesises therefore that a well-trained TBM on the extensive datasets that exists for Dyslexia and ADHD could possibly be a more effective approach to address this issue. Enhancing existing TBMs without the need for a third-party app or API would be a more desired approach.

There is also a wider scope of improvement using an AI TBM such as further personalisation of such a model by machine learning to understand the reader's habits. This will help with adjusting the bolding pattern by optimising the ability of the TBM to understand context, grammar, and predicting which parts of words are most critical for comprehension. Other benefits of this approach are better error recovery, and multimodal integration to keep the reader engaged, by using text-to-speech for instance.

For this approach, a large-scale experiment needs to be designed using a large sample of individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD, as well as developing and finetuning a TBM.

5.6 DISCUSSION

It was expected, yet disappointing not to discover any ADHD dataset on the largest AI platforms such as Hugging Face and GitHub, to help ADHD sufferers.

Unfortunately, beyond Hugging Face, the only kind of datasets available are of the neuroimaging or detection (behavioural) kind which are not conducive to building helpful TBMs. The kind of datasets that would be helpful, in the opinion of the researcher, are ones that:

- Are more phonetically transparent
- Reduces irregular spelling rules
- Ease cognitive load for decoding unfamiliar or misleading words
- Mimics how speech sounds, which is how readers with Dyslexia often compensate when reading

The argument for this approach is supported by the fact that sound-to-letter mappings are often a key struggle in Dyslexia. Research in linguistic accessibility, especially for non-native speakers and neurodivergent readers, shows that simplified spelling helps comprehension and speed (Higasa, et al., 2023).

The argument against this approach suggests the consistency with standard spelling as altering spelling could cause confusion between what is taught in schools. It will also affect spelling ability.

It could be argued that some accessibility tools, like text-to-speech, would resolve this issue. While there is some merit to this argument, it is not always possible, for instance in public places, to use such a tool conveniently.

The researcher argues that a better approach of phoneme-first transformation could be much more beneficial in many other ways, such as in translating from and to a different language. This is in line with a linguistically informed design for Dyslexia, and possibly ADHD.

With ADHD, this approach may be different from simply restructuring the text in the same manner as discussed here. This is due to the lack of well-identified features and difficulties of how ADHD affects different individuals.

Individuals with ADHD can experience a range of reading difficulties stemming from their core symptoms of inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity. These difficulties can affect both the mechanics of reading and comprehension. Below is a breakdown of common reading challenges:

Difficulties with Focus and Attention

- **Sustaining attention:** Maintaining focus on a lengthy text can be challenging, leading to missed information and reduced comprehension.
- **Distractibility:** Internal thoughts or external stimuli can easily divert attention away from reading.
- **Losing place:** Difficulty keeping track of where they are on the page, skipping lines, or rereading the same lines.

Difficulties with Processing and Memory

- **Working memory:** Holding information in mind while reading and connecting it to previous sentences or overall meaning can be impaired.
- **Processing speed:** Reading and processing information more slowly can affect fluency and comprehension.
- **Retention:** Difficulty remembering what has just been read.

Difficulties with Reading Mechanics

- Decoding: Some individuals with ADHD may have co-occurring learning disabilities like Dyslexia, making it hard to sound out words and connect sounds to letters.
- Fluency: Reading aloud may be hesitant, with pauses, mispronunciations, or reading too quickly without processing.
- Skipping punctuation: Missing or ignoring punctuation marks, which can alter the meaning of sentences.
- Guessing words: Instead of decoding, they might guess words based on the first letter or context, leading to inaccuracies.
- Misreading small words: Overlooking or substituting common function words like *the*, *of*, *an*.
- Leaving off suffixes: Missing endings of words (e.g. -ing, -ed).
- Reading with inappropriate expression: Not varying tone or pace to reflect the meaning of the text.

Difficulties with Comprehension

- Making inferences: Difficulty understanding implied meanings or drawing conclusions from the text.
- Connecting ideas: Struggling to see the relationships between different parts of the text.
- Identifying main ideas: Missing the central themes or key points of a passage.
- Understanding figurative language: Difficulty interpreting metaphors, similes, and other non-literal expressions.
- Integrating prior knowledge: Not effectively linking what they are reading to what they already know about a topic.
- Building a coherent mental representation: Difficulty forming a complete and accurate understanding of the text as a whole.

Behavioural Manifestations

- Avoidance: Disliking or avoiding reading due to the difficulties experienced.
- Restlessness: Difficulty sitting still while reading.

- Frustration: Becoming easily frustrated or giving up when reading is challenging.

It is important to note that not everyone with ADHD will experience all of these difficulties, and the severity can also vary. Additionally, many individuals with ADHD are capable readers, but they may need specific strategies and accommodations to support their reading comprehension and engagement.

5.7 TBM + BIONIC READING© = ADHD AI MODEL

In an attempt to identify symptoms of reading difficulties and creating an AI model to help readability for ADHD, a combined solution borrowed from the approach of Bionic Reading© with TBMs simplification ability was attempted. A text was presented to the TBMs with a prompt to simplify it for ADHD individuals and bolding the first two letters of every word in the text (longer than two letters). The text was:

Individuals with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) often face unique challenges when it comes to reading. These difficulties can be broadly categorised into several areas. They might struggle with sustaining attention, finding it hard to focus on the text for extended periods, which can lead to incomplete reading or comprehension issues. They can also be easily distracted by external stimuli, such as noise or movement, making it challenging to concentrate on reading.

Their working memory limitations can make it difficult to hold onto information, making it harder to understand complex texts or follow instructions. Additionally, they might experience slow processing speed, making reading a laborious process, as they might need more time to process and understand the information.

ChatGPT Response⁷:

FIGURE 10: OUTPUT FROM CHATGPT

⁷ The output was produced as an image to capture the font change

Meta-AI Response:

FIGURE 11: OUTPUT FROM META-AI

DeepSeek Response:

Individuals with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder

(ADHD) often face unique challenges when it comes to reading. These difficulties can be broadly categorised into several areas. They might struggle with sustaining attention, finding it hard to focus on the text for extended periods, which can lead to incomplete reading or comprehension issues. They can also be easily distracted by external stimuli, such as noise or movement, making it challenging to concentrate on reading.

Their working memory limitations can make it difficult to hold onto information, making it harder to understand complex texts or follow instructions. Additionally, they might experience slow processing speed, making reading a laborious process, as they might need more time to process and understand the information.

Bing Chat Response:

Sure! Here's a simplified version of the text with the requested formatting for easier reading:

Individuals with ADHD often face **u**nique challenges with reading. They may **s**truggle to stay **f**ocused for long, leading to **i**ncomplete reading or **c**omprehension issues. **E**xternal distractions like **n**oise or **m**ovement can make it hard to **c**oncentrate.

Limited memory can make it **d**ifficult to hold onto **i**nformation and understand **c**omplex texts or **f**ollow instructions. **S**low processing can make reading feel **l**aborious, as they need **m**ore time to **p**rocess and **u**nderstand.

FIGURE 12: OUTPUT FROM BING CHAT

Claude Response:

People with ADHD often have trouble when reading. Here's why:

- They find it hard to focus for long
- They get easily distracted by noise or movement
- Their memory makes it tough to hold onto information
- They may read more slowly as they need extra time to understand what they read

FIGURE 13: OUTPUT FROM CLAUDE

Gemini Response:

Individuals with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) often face unique challenges when it comes to reading. These difficulties can be broadly categorised into several areas. They might struggle with sustaining attention, finding it hard to focus on the text for extended periods, which can lead to incomplete reading or comprehension issues. They can also be easily distracted by external stimuli, such as noise or movement, making it challenging to concentrate on reading.

Their working memory limitations can make it difficult to hold onto information, making it harder to understand complex texts or follow instructions. Additionally, they might experience slow processing speed, making reading a laborious process, as they might need more time to process and understand the information.

The obvious errors in the responses of the six major models above, demonstrate how these powerful models fail to follow simple instructions and, sometimes, were completely incapable of responding to a combined instruction.

These trials also revealed some weakness in some of these models in handling errors as in the case of Meta-AI *redig*, and Bing Chat *ADHÔD*. In one case, the trial of the same model was repeated as many as ten times without any improvement in the result.

This proves the need for such comparison of TBMs, and for a more precise approach to achieve the desired outcome. To demonstrate this, employing a simple coding method achieved better results than TBMs. The code allows more flexibility and further finetuning as needed.

It is somehow surprising that none of these models performed this multi-task activity satisfactorily. This makes the comparison rather difficult and the only conclusion that can be drawn from this, is the fact that there are definite deficiencies in these models. As will be seen from the results below, one cannot even nominate one over the others for this task. Although the simplification task in all cases was successful, the combination with another task, such as this visual alteration of the text, remains a challenge.

The alternative method, therefore, had to be regressing to a rule-based approach by programming this combination of rules, as in the following Python code. This would be the first step and as a proof of concept for designing a new TBM for this task. The code can also be used, after modification of input and output parameters, to upload a text file and produce an output file.

To achieve this, from the Hugging Face Transformers library, *transformers* was installed first from the *Pycharm* terminal window, for text simplification. Python's built-in string manipulation capability was then invoked for boldening the first two characters of words longer than two letters. The only other feature that will enhance the functionality of this code, is the ability to specify the age ranges that would dictate the level of simplification. Two ranges, 10-20 years and another for over 20 years of age would suffice.

Python Code:

```
from transformers import pipeline from transformers import pipeline
import re
from docx import Document
# Step 1: Simplify the text using a Hugging Face model
simplifier = pipeline("summarization", model="facebook/bart-large-cnn")
# Example input text
text = "Transformer-Based Models (TBMs), which underpin the most sophisticated advancements in contemporary natural language processing, are computational architectures predicated upon the self-attention mechanism, a mathematical apparatus that enables models to dynamically weight the relevance of each constituent token in a sequence relative to all others. Rather than processing linguistic data in a strictly linear or recurrent fashion—as was the case with traditional RNNs or LSTMs—TBMs such as BERT, GPT, and T5 employ a bidirectional or autoregressive architecture that leverages vast contextual interdependencies in parallel, thereby facilitating nuanced semantic disambiguation and syntactic inference across arbitrarily long textual spans. These models are trained on prodigious corpora using unsupervised or self-supervised objectives (e.g., masked language modelling or next-token prediction), which engender latent representations of language that are not merely statistical approximations but rather intricate multidimensional embeddings encoding hierarchical, positional, and contextual information simultaneously."
# Simplify the text
simplified_text = simplifier(text)[0]["summary_text"]
# Step 2: Function to bold the first two letters of every word longer than 2 letters in a Word document
def bolden_first_two_letters_in_docx(text, doc):
```

```

words = text.split() # Split the text into words
# Create a new paragraph for the boldened text
paragraph = doc.add_paragraph()
for word in words:
    # If the word is longer than 2 characters, apply bold to the
    first two letters
    if len(word) > 2:
        # Add the first part of the word in bold
        run = paragraph.add_run(word[:2])
        run.bold = True
        # Add the rest of the word normally
        paragraph.add_run(word[2:])
    else:
        # If the word is too short, just add it normally
        paragraph.add_run(word)
    # Add space between words
    paragraph.add_run(' ')
# Step 3: Create a Word document with the output
doc = Document()
doc.add_heading('Simplified and Boldened Text', 0)
# Add simplified text
doc.add_heading('Simplified Text:', level=1)
doc.add_paragraph(simplified_text)
# Add boldened text
doc.add_heading('Boldened Text:', level=1)
# Apply the boldening function and add the boldened text to the Word
document
bolden_first_two_letters_in_docx(simplified_text, doc)
# Save the document
output_file = "simplified_and_boldened_output.docx"
doc.save(output_file)
print(f"Output has been written to '{output_file}'")

```

First sample output before finetuning:

Simplified Text

This is a sample text for demonstration purposes. The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog. This is a Sample Text for Demonstration purposes. [Click here to see the full text of this sample text.](#) For confidential support call the Samaritans on 08457 90 90 90, visit a local Samaritans branch or see www.samaritans.org.

Boldened Text

This is a sample text demonstration purposes. The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog. This is a Sample Text demonstration purposes. Click here to see the full text of this sample text. Confidential support call the Samaritans on 08457 90 90 90, visit a local Samaritans branch or see www.samaritans.org.

After several finetuning iterations, the following was obtained on a Word document:

Original Text

Transformer-Based Models (TBMs), which underpin the most sophisticated advancements in contemporary natural language processing, are computational architectures predicated upon the self-attention mechanism, a mathematical apparatus that enables models to dynamically weight the relevance of each constituent token in a sequence relative to all others. Rather than processing linguistic data in a strictly linear or recurrent fashion—as was the case with traditional RNNs or LSTMs—TBMs such as BERT, GPT, and T5 employ a bidirectional or autoregressive architecture that leverages vast contextual interdependencies in parallel, thereby facilitating nuanced semantic disambiguation and syntactic inference across arbitrarily long textual spans. These models are trained on prodigious corpora using unsupervised or self-supervised objectives (e.g., masked language modelling or next-token prediction), which engender latent representations of language that are not merely statistical approximations but rather intricate multidimensional embeddings encoding hierarchical, positional, and contextual information simultaneously.

Simplified Text

Transformer-Based Models (TBMs) underpin the most sophisticated advancements in contemporary natural language processing. TBMs such as BERT, GPT, and T5 employ a bidirectional or autoregressive architecture that leverages vast contextual

interdependencies in parallel. These models are trained on prodigious corpora using unsupervised or self-supervised objectives.

Boldened Text

Transformer-Based Models (TBMs) underpin the most sophisticated advancements in contemporary natural language processing. TBMs such as BERT, GPT, and T5 employ a bidirectional or autoregressive architecture that leverages vast contextual interdependencies in parallel. These models are trained on prodigious corpora using unsupervised or self-supervised objectives.

Notes on this code:

- This script uses the *facebook-bart-large-cnn* model for text simplification.
- The bolding of the first two characters of words longer than two letters is done using Markdown syntax (****** for bolding).
- This is a basic example depending on specific requirements. One might want to finetune the simplification model or adjust the bolding logic.

In fact, the program above only manages to shorten rather than simplify the text given. This is an inherent weakness in the model *facebook-bart-large-cnn* and most other generally available simplification models on platforms such as Hugging Face. The strength of these models does not compare to the superior power of larger language models (LLM), such as the ones studied in this research.

As mentioned above, the only other feature that would enhance the functionality of the code above, apart from using APIs to invoke larger models, is if users could specify their age. If the age falls in the range of 10-20 years, then the simplification would be appropriately adjusted. Above that range, the text will still be adjusted but not to the same extent as for the other age group. Unless one is using the larger models, there is no readily available model in Hugging Face that natively takes an age as an input to simplify a text accordingly.

To elaborate the importance of availability of models in platforms such as Hugging Face (or the lack thereof), it is crucial for AI developers to have access to such resources to save considerable effort. Such efforts would be better utilised for developing new models by finetuning and modifying existing models.

It is also essential for apps requiring data privacy, offline access, or compliance (e.g. General Data Protection Regulation), to maintain on-premises development of such models, which would otherwise not be possible. This will also eliminate any usage restrictions without the API constraints.

Additionally, there are cost implications of using APIs, especially if the developed application will be serving many users or building high traffic.

Finally, models in such platforms will allow more flexible pipeline integration with custom machine learning pipelines, data preprocessing, and multi-model orchestration.

Most summarisation and simplifications models (e.g. BART, Pegasus) would only try to shorten a text or make it generally easier, rather than be controlled by age group.

With some perseverance, encouraged by testing all six large models with prompts such as “explain this to a child of 10 years of age” and getting a very satisfactory and convincing answer every time, a solution was finally found. Without such a solution, albeit not perfect for the task without finetuning, no practical user application could be developed (such as the app detailed in this study), which requires age as a parameter.

There are various methods of overcoming this complexity by manually setting target reading grades, or adding extra instructions to the models employed to deal with this issue.

Eventually, using pipelines to invoke some models from Hugging Face, managed to produce satisfactory results, with some room for improvement by finetuning.

A pipeline works automatically to chain together a tokeniser, a model, and a decoder, so that they can easily run complex NLP tasks such as text generation, translation, and summarisation, with just a few lines of code.

Below is the Python code by which a satisfactory result was achieved. It prompts the user for their age and works accordingly. At the end of the code, the results of two interactions were copied.

```

from transformers import pipeline
# Step 1: Create the pipeline
simplifier = pipeline("text2text-generation", model="google/flan-t5-
large", device=-1)
# Step 2: Define your text
text = "Depending on contextual information, a word can mean many
things simultaneously. So a fox could be an animal or a bad character
in a novel. "
# Step 3: Ask user for the age
age = int(input("Please enter your age: "))
# Step 4: Create the prompt based on the age
if age <= 20:
    prompt = f"Explain this to a 10-year-old: {text}"
else:
    prompt = f"Explain this clearly to a 30-year-old: {text}"
# Step 5: Run the model
result = simplifier(prompt, max_length=256, do_sample=False)
simplified_text = result[0]['generated_text']
# Step 6: Print the output
print("\nSimplified Text:\n", simplified_text)

```

Inference from next code

```

firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 % python3 App_age2.py
Please enter your age: 10
Simplified Text:
A fox is an animal.
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 % python3 App_age2.py
Please enter your age: 30
Simplified Text:
A word can mean many things.

```

The other TBMs involved in this research were all tested for their ability to use simplification transformers, and for boldening the first two letters of every word, except those no more than two letters in length, using markdown syntax rules.

The results from all were examined and qualitatively considered of the same quality. Since there was no need in that case to have a golden standard from a specialist, unlike in the case of the YAM test, it was not possible to perform any metric evaluation for comparison.

The nature of ADHD as a condition is much more complex than Dyslexia. While Dyslexia can be described in various ways and narrowed down mainly to two components, decoding and comprehension as in the Simple View of Reading (SVR) model (Gough & Tunmer, 1986), ADHD cannot be defined as succinctly.

SVR can help explain some aspects of reading difficulty in individuals with ADHD, but it does not fully account for all the challenges that individuals with this condition may face. They do not typically have core deficits in decoding or language comprehension, but they may struggle with reading comprehension because of executive function issues like:

- Inattention: Trouble staying focused while reading.
- Working memory limitations: Difficulty holding and integrating information across sentences.
- Impulsivity: Rushing through text without proper processing.
- Poor self-monitoring: Missing errors or inconsistencies.

While SVR explains decoding and comprehension as key pillars, it does not directly address attention, motivation, or executive functioning, which are often the primary obstacles for readers with ADHD.

SVR is useful for understanding reading comprehension in general, but it needs to be supplemented with other cognitive or neurodevelopment frameworks to fully capture the reading difficulties experienced by individuals with ADHD.

In the next chapter, the proceeds from this chapter will be modelled in an attempt to create a proof of concept of building a simple but useful dataset and a prototype rule-based model. This model aims at improving readability for individuals primarily with Dyslexia, but also for ADHD.

CHAPTER 6: PILOT DYSLEXIA DATASET AND RULE-BASED MODEL

The previous chapter demonstrated the shortcomings of the TBMs trialled to generate aids for individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. This chapter presents a template, as proof of concept, for building a simple dataset and a prototype rule-based model for improving readability for such individuals.

6.1 NLP DYSLEXIA MODEL

In general, what may work for a person with Dyslexia, may not necessarily work for someone with ADHD. It may even create more confusion for the latter unless they have Dyslexia as well. Such a transformation may create visual chaos that undermines its intended benefit.

As highlighted, the causes of these two conditions could be vastly different, so could their effects and symptoms.

While the model below is based on the phonetic (decoding of words), the problem with Dyslexia reading is bifold, being phonetic and one of comprehension. Gough and Tunmer (1986), proposed that in the SVR model, reading comprehension is the product of two components, decoding and linguistic comprehension. It follows that this framework implies the existence of three distinct types of reading disabilities:

- impaired decoding skills (commonly associated with Dyslexia)
- deficits in language comprehension (referred to as Hyperlexia)
- combination of both impairments, which is classified as a general reading disability

SVR is a widely used model in reading research and education. It proposes that:

Reading Comprehension (RC) = Decoding (D) × Language Comprehension (LC)

Where:

- Decoding: The ability to translate written words into their spoken forms (e.g. phonics skills).
- Language Comprehension: The ability to understand spoken language – vocabulary, grammar, and context.

The SVR suggests that both components are essential for the following reasons:

- If a person can decode words but does not understand the language, they will not necessarily comprehend the written text.
- If they understand the language but cannot decode it phonetically, they also will not comprehend it.

The multiplication symbol (×) emphasises that if either skills is weak or missing, reading comprehension will suffer, no matter how strong the other is. Therefore, the model below can only deal with the first part of SVR, but it is hoped that correct decoding will aid comprehension.

To commence the process of building a pilot Dyslexia dataset, a basic rule set together with example pairs for phonetic simplification system aimed at dyslexia-friendly transformation are built. Below are the various steps to achieve that:

- **Core Transformation Rules**

Set rules of the transformation as in the table below (Table 10):

TABLE 10: DYSLEXIA RULES

Original	Simplified	Example
ph	f	photo → foto
gh	g/silent	ghost → gost, though → tho
kn	n	knife → nife
wr	r	write → rite
tion	shun	station → stashun
ch	k/ch	character → karakter (if hard ch)
x	ks/z	box → boks, xylophone → zylophone
c (soft)	s	city → sity
c (hard)	k	cat → kat
qu	kw	quick → kwik
ough	uff/ow/o	rough → ruff, though → tho, thought → thot
wh	w	what → wat

Below are a few example pairs of sentences transformed according to the rules in table 10.

Original → Transformed

"The phone is on the table." → "The fone is on the taybul."

"Though he knew the knife was sharp..." → "Tho he nu the nife woz sharp..."

"The station was quiet." → "The stashun woz kwyet."

"She laughed at the rough patch." → "She laft at the ruff pach."

- **Build a Starter Dataset (Comma Separated Values [CSV] format)**

Below is a sample of how this training dataset is structured (Table 11):

TABLE 11: DYSLEXIA DATASET SAMPLE

Input text	Transformed text
The phone is on the table.	The fone is on the taybul.
Though he knew the knife was sharp.	Tho he nu the nife woz sharp
The station was quiet.	The stashun woz kwyet

The generation of such dataset can be accomplished by Python script that will apply these rules to any English text, and output pairs for training T5 or other NLP models.

The Python script is below, performs **phonetic and lexical simplification** of input text. It operates in two stages: **lexical override** and **rule-based phonetic transformation**.

```
import re
def simplify_text(text):
    override_words = {
        "table": "taybul",    # Add other words that need specific
rules here
        "phone": "fone",
        "people": "peepl",
        "laugh": "laf",
        # Add more as needed
    }
    # Split into words and apply the overrides
```

```

words = text.split()
simplified_words = []
for word in words:
    # Handle words with punctuation
    match = re.match(r"(\w+) (\W*)", word)
    if match:
        base, punct = match.groups()
        # Apply override if present, otherwise keep the word
        replacement = override_words.get(base.lower(), base)
        simplified_words.append(replacement + punct)
    else:
        simplified_words.append(word)
# Reassemble the text after applying word-level overrides
simplified = " ".join(simplified_words)
# Phonetic simplification rules (more general rules)
rules = [
    (r'ph', 'f'),
    (r'ght', 't'),
    (r'gh', ''),
    (r'kn', 'n'),
    (r'wr', 'r'),
    (r'ough', 'uff'),
    (r'tion', 'shun'),
    (r'wh', 'w'),
    (r'ch', 'k'),
    (r'x', 'ks'),
    (r'ce', 's'),
    (r'ci', 'si'),
    (r'cy', 'sy'),
    (r'qu', 'kw'),
    (r'c(?=[eiy])', 's'),
    (r'c', 'k'),
    (r'oo', 'u'),
    (r'ea', 'ee'),
    # (r'th', 'd'),
    (r'ou', 'ow'),
]
# Apply phonetic rules
for pattern, repl in rules:
    simplified = re.sub(pattern, repl, simplified)

```

```

        return simplified
# TEST CASE
text = "The phone is on the table."
simplified = simplify_text(text)
print("Original:", text)
print("Simplified:", simplified)

```

The inference from this test:

```

(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 % python3 Dataset.py
Original: The phone is on the table.
Simplified: The fone is on the taybul.

```

Starting with dataset of 50 sentence pairs (original → simplified) in CSV format, using the following Python code, a new set of simplified-generated sentences is built as in the table in Appendix A:

```

import pandas as pd
import re
# Define your phonetic simplification function
def simplify_text(text):
    rules = [
        (r'ph', 'f'),
        (r'ough', 'off'),
        (r'kn', 'n'),
        (r'ght', 't'),
        (r'wr', 'r'),
        (r'wh', 'w'),
        (r'gh', ''), # silent gh
        (r'gu', 'g'),
        (r'ci', 'si'),
        (r'ce', 'se'),
        (r'ck', 'k'),
        (r'ch', 'sh'),
        (r'qu', 'kw'),
        (r'tion', 'shun'),
        (r'eau', 'o'),
        (r'ae', 'e'),
        (r'oe', 'e'),
        (r'kn', 'n'),

```

```

        (r'ps', 's'),
        (r'gn', 'n'),
        (r'x', 'ks'),
        (r'c([eiy])', r's\1'),    # soft c
        (r'c', 'k')              # hard c
    ]
    for pattern, replacement in rules:
        text = re.sub(pattern, replacement, text,
            flags=re.IGNORECASE)
    return text

# Load your dataset
df = pd.read_csv('/Users/firasali/Downloads/dys.csv')
# Apply the transformation
df['generated_simplified'] = df['original'].apply(simplify_text)
# Save the result
df.to_csv('/Users/firasali/Downloads/dys_simplified.csv',
    index=False)
print("Done. Transformed data saved to dys_simplified.csv.")

```

To summarise, this exercise started with the goal to build a simple rule-based system to phonemically simplify English text to make it more dyslexia-friendly.

The steps involved in this exercise were:

1. Dataset Preparation

- a. prepared or downloaded a CSV file ([dys.csv](#)) with a column of original English sentences.
- b. ensured the file path was correct and fixed format issues (e.g. a corrupt file was converted to Excel and saved back as CSV).

2. Simplification Rules

A function ([simplify_text](#)) is created containing custom rules to phonetically simplify words (like replacing "ph" with "f" and "ough" with "uff", etc.).

3. Processing with Pandas⁸

- a. Load the dataset.
- b. Apply the `simplify_text` function to the `original` column.

⁸ Pandas is an open-source Python library that provides data structures and data analysis tools.

- c. Generate a new column called ``generated_simplified`` with the transformed text.

4. Saving Output

- a. The new DataFrame with original and simplified sentences was saved as a CSV
- b. File name: ``dys_simplified.csv``
- c. Location: ``/Users/firasali/Downloads/``

5. Basic Debugging

Using the Python code above with its text simplifying rules (Wagner & Torgesen, 1987), and a simple transformation method, a dyslexic-friendly dataset is created and saved as a CSV file for future use. The final product was a simple rule-based model, which can be considered as a prototype or a proof of concept for generating a dyslexia-friendly dataset.

Later in this thesis, a simple experiment was designed to utilise the generated dataset as detailed in Chapter 7.

This model is then:

- a. Takes standard English text.
- b. Applies manually defined phonetic simplification rules.
- c. Outputs a new dataset pairing, original and simplified text.
- d. Saves this dataset for use in further projects (e.g. training ML models or testing readability).

It is a valid and usable system, especially for rule-based or linguistic research purposes.

Depending on goals for future development and research, this model can be expanded with more rules (e.g. for silent letters, irregular vowels, etc.). A pronunciation dictionary can be used as well for more accurate phoneme-based rewrites, and tuned for consistency (e.g. make sure ``knight`` and ``knife`` are always simplified the same way).

Another approach to utilising this, is generating ML-based model by finetuning a small transformer (like T5 or BART), to use the dataset to learn to generate simplified forms. This would allow for generalisation beyond hand-written rules.

In conclusion, this exercise yielded:

- A functioning rule-based model.
- A pipeline that can generate datasets.
- A strong foundation for expansion or transformation into an ML pipeline or application.

The advantages of the simplicity of the rule-based model can be summed up as:

- Feasibility – It demonstrates the practicality of automatic dyslexia-friendly text generation without relying on resource-intensive methods.
- Efficiency – The approach is computationally efficient and accessible within the timescale and resource limits of this research.
- Establishing a baseline – It serves as a baseline for future more sophisticated models that might incorporate machine learning techniques for enhanced performance.

This prototype system, while simple, represents an effective starting point for addressing the need for dyslexia-friendly text in a low-resource research context.

6.2 DYSLEXIA/ADHD APP VISUALISED

In order to propose readability aids, various TBMs and Bionic Reading© were tried. A number of conceptual Python modules were also developed for the same purpose. In this section, a visual model based on the previous section will be presented. This model could be a nucleus for an actual app in the future. In addition, this visual presentation might shed more light on the narrative that preceded it.

Developed with neurodivergent individuals in mind, this model aims to reduce any cumbersome demands made by other apps of registrations and multitude of verifications. Ultimately, it is hoped that this can be adopted and developed by education authorities around the globe and made accessible to individuals with Dyslexia/ADHD.

The app's landing page (Fig. 14) should be welcoming and amusing. It should perhaps carry a phonetically appropriate title which reflects its functionality. It will time out after a very short time so not to put further cognitive load onto the user to advance it manually. Therefore, there are no more visual prompts on this screen.

The design of the remaining screens should follow the template set by the landing page, reducing the confusion of different designs. A uniformed approach makes the development of the app more economic and rapid.

FIGURE 14: APP LANDING PAGE

In the next screen, the app would invite the user to specify their condition(s) by presenting two checkboxes (Fig. 15). One checkbox is for Dyslexia and another for ADHD. A user can check one or both conditions so the app can determine which process to apply. It will also invite them to specify their age. The simplification can be tailored to an age range of 10-20 years or above. Simplification of text will always be

applied. This would be useful in both cases, as established from the discussion above. Other processes will depend on the choice of condition and the developers' approach. The user can move on to the next screen by clicking the symbol

FIGURE 15: APP OPTIONS PAGE

Different individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD can manifest different symptoms and have different needs. The next screen then (Fig. 16), will allow the user to specify some of these personal needs. In this example, the user can specify any number of letter(s) to exchange. This can be done by providing one letter or more, up to 2, to cater for something like 'ph'. The next input would be the alternative letter(s). A user can **Repeat** this process as many times as they wish until they move to the next screen by clicking

FIGURE 16: APP LETTER EXCHANGE PAGE

FIGURE 17: APP OUTPUT CHOICE PAGE

The next screen will ask the user about the form of output they would like (Fig. 17). The choice is either to display it on the same device or as a saved file. This is also done by selecting one of two checkboxes clearly marked.

If **Save** is selected, a dialogue would follow with an option to save to a default location. Otherwise, the user will be asked to provide a path for saving the output file.

Since this screen contains only two options, once an option is selected, the app will automatically go to the next screen (Fig. 18). This final screen is the input screen. This could be an editing window where a user can paste a text they already copied. The second option is a dialog button to allow them to upload a saved document.

If **Upload** is selected, the app would process the document according to the previous selections.

FIGURE 18: APP INPUT SCREEN PAGE

One of the advantages of this proposed app, is the capacity to include the developers' own ideas and thoughts to aid neurodivergence in this simple framework.

Considering the significant number of individuals who have been disadvantaged by these conditions (see Abstract), such an app is currently as absent as it is needed. This app serves as a practical demonstration of how AI-driven tools can be adapted to support learners with Dyslexia/ADHD. By applying tailored transformation rules, it reduces common reading barriers such as confusing letter patterns and complex spellings. This dynamic tool supports personalised learning and fosters greater reading confidence. Its ease of use and adaptability ensure it can meet diverse needs, providing practical benefits for both educational settings and everyday reading challenges.

Building on this text transformation approach, the following section explores how music-based models can further support individuals with Dyslexia/ADHD by leveraging visual and cognitive pathways.

6.3 MUSIC AND DYSLEXIA/ADHD MODEL

Leveraging more of the visual ability of TBMs to transform objects, this section, will introduce an aid for music score readability. The model is based on colour mapping, a well-known technique for aiding individuals with Dyslexia/ADHD (British Dyslexia Association, n.d.).

Music educators can spend considerable time modifying sheets of music by colouring the notes according to a particular convention such as **C** is red, and **D** is green, and so on. What can be done by harnessing the capability of TBMs, as demonstrated in this small experiment, can be significant for non-expert users.

In this model, a user can assign colours to the notes and let AI do the rest, as long as the model can be fed a music sheet from any number of well-known music writing software applications such as MuseScore (n.d.).

Further, to simplify transposing pieces of music, which involves raising or lower the pitch of the written music, the model also has the ability to perform that task. It could be augmented with the capability to specify to which other instrument such transposing is required. This could be done with the aid of a dataset of musical instruments. In this model, the same can be achieved by a simple input of positive integer for raising the pitch, or a negative for lowering it. This process, once made into more user-friendly app with a friendly User Interface (UI) would be characterised by:

a. Efficiency and ease of customisation

- Mock-ups can be generated instantly, tailored to the user's specifications (instrument, ability level, accessibility need, etc.).
- Traditional design might take hours or days and require software like Finale, Sibelius, or graphic tools, plus musical and visual design skills.

b. Adaptation for different disciplines

The app will be potentially suitable for music education, cognitive accessibility, and as an AI aid for neurodivergence in general, and Dyslexia/ADHD in particular.

c. Accessibility to non-experts

No expertise is needed as a TBM would transform standard music notations into accessible formats. Currently, most musical tools are incapable of doing so.

In attempting to achieve this modest result, the researcher experimented with various specialised software such as Audiveris (n.d.) and a general tool such as Java script. However, due to the complexity or integration issues, these attempts were not successful.

A Python-based solution, invoking various TBMs, was subsequently designed to achieve this task. Ultimately it can be made to allow all of these features:

1. User configuration

It allows the user to choose the type of aid (Dyslexia or ADHD), the level of assistance (low, medium, high), and the output type (visual or audio).

2. Colour mapping

The script uses a colourmap dictionary to assign a colour to each musical note. This helps making the notes easier to read.

3. Apply visual aids

The function `apply_dyslexia_aid` is responsible for altering the score based on the specified level. For high-level assistance, the noteheads are enlarged and colour coded.

4. Export Score

Depending on the user's configuration, the score is either exported as a visual (PDF) or audio (MIDI) file.

5. Main Pipeline

The `run_pipeline` function takes the input file and applies the chosen aids and then exports the result.

Using various TBMs, the Python code below performs a visual transformation of music scores. It also allows for transposing the score if required.

```
from music21 import converter, note, stream, environment, interval
# Set up MuseScore paths
us = environment.UserSettings()
us['musescoreDirectPNGPath'] = '/Applications/MuseScore
4.app/Contents/MacOS/mscore'
us['musicxmlPath'] = '/Applications/MuseScore
4.app/Contents/MacOS/mscore'
# Dyslexia color mapping
color_map = {
    'C': 'red', 'D': 'orange', 'E': 'yellow',
    'F': 'green', 'G': 'blue', 'A': 'purple', 'B': 'pink'
}
# Ask user for config
def get_user_config():
    aid_type = input("Aid type (dyslexia / ADHD): ").strip().lower()
    level = input("Level (low / medium / high): ").strip().lower()
    output_type = input("Output type (visual / audio):
").strip().lower()
    return {
        "aid_type": aid_type,
        "level": level,
        "output_type": output_type
    }
# Ask user if they want to transpose
def get_transposition_interval():
    response = input("Do you want to transpose the piece? (yes / no):
").strip().lower()
```

```

    if response == "yes":
        try:
            interval_value = int(input("Enter number of semitones to
transpose (positive = up, negative = down): "))
            return interval_value
        except ValueError:
            print("Invalid input. Skipping transposition.")
    return 0
# Transpose
def transpose_score(score, semitones):
    if semitones != 0:
        i = interval.Interval(semitones)
        return score.transpose(i)
    return score
# Visual dyslexia aid
def apply_dyslexia_aid(score, level):
    for n in score.recurse().notes:
        if isinstance(n, note.Note):
            if level in ["medium", "high"]:
                n.style.color = color_map.get(n.name, 'black')
            if level == "high":
                n.style.size = 24
    return score
# Export to visual or audio
def export_score(score, output_type):
    if output_type == "visual":
        score.show('musicxml.pdf')
    elif output_type == "audio":
        score.write('midi', fp='output.mid')
# Run everything
def run_pipeline(input_file):
    user_config = get_user_config()
    transposition = get_transposition_interval()
    score = converter.parse(input_file)
    score = transpose_score(score, transposition)
    if user_config["aid_type"] == "dyslexia":
        score = apply_dyslexia_aid(score, user_config["level"])
    export_score(score, user_config["output_type"])
# Run it
if __name__ == "__main__":

```

```
run_pipeline("/Users/firasali/Documents/D_Csc/melody.musicxml")
```

Here is the runtime record:

```
(.venv) firasali@Mac PythonProject1 % python3 Transpose.py  
Aid type (dyslexia / ADHD): dyslexia  
Level (low / medium / high): high  
Output type (visual / audio): visual  
Do you want to transpose the piece? (yes / no): yes  
Enter number of semitones to transpose (positive = up, negative =  
down): 2  
(.venv) firasali@Mac PythonProject1 %
```

The input to this model was this simple two bar music scale (Fig. 19):

FIGURE 19: TWO BAR MUSICAL SCALE

The output without transposing was (Fig. 20):

FIGURE 20: DYSLEXIA - COLOURED MUSICAL SCALE

The output after transposing by 2 semitones (Fig. 21):

FIGURE 21: DYSLEXIA - COLOURED & TRANSPOSED MUSICAL SCALE

In the Python code above, the user's configuration allows them to choose the condition (Dyslexia or ADHD), select the severity (Low, Medium, High), and whether transposing is required. For achieving transposition, a user is invited to specify by how many semitones up or down.

Dyslexia can manifest itself in different forms in different individuals. In a real case scenario reported in Clayton (2023), a ten year old piano student presented with a different symptom of Dyslexia. The child could perfectly read music and play the notes with one hand at a time. However, as soon as the student attempted to play with both hands, confusion ensued as the student tried to figure out which hand was meant to play which stave.

It is reported in Stein and Walsh (1997) that some children with Dyslexia fail to tell left from right. Oglethorpe (2008) confirmed that, with reference to playing the piano, that some children with Dyslexia experience this confusion.

Eventually, and after several attempts to resolve this with various visual effects, Clayton resorted to highlighting all the treble clef in pink and the bass with green. In addition, she marked the back of the student's right hand with the colour of the treble clef and the left with the corresponding colour of the bass clef. This resulted in a resounding success. Figure 22 shows how the score looked with an impression of the hands of the child.

FIGURE 22: MUSIC READING – DYSLEXIA (CLAYTON, 2023)

Using a modified version of the Python code above, this model can apply one uniform colour for each staff efficiently and clearly. This will provide the means to assist music teaching as it can be easily adapted to suit the various real-time cases.

```

from music21 import converter, note, stream
from music21 import environment
us = environment.UserSettings()
us['musescoreDirectPNGPath'] = '/Applications/MuseScore
4.app/Contents/MacOS/mscore'
us['musicxmlPath'] = '/Applications/MuseScore
4.app/Contents/MacOS/mscore'
score = converter.parse("/Users/firasali/Documents/D
CSc/piano.musicxml")
# User Configuration
user_config = {
    "aid_type": "dyslexia", # Options: "dyslexia", "ADHD"
    "level": "high", # Options: "low", "medium", "high"
    "output_type": "visual" # Options: "visual", "audio"
}
# Function to apply color aids for treble clef (red) and bass clef
(green)
def apply_clef_color_aid(score):
    # Loop through each part in the score
    for part in score.parts:

```

```

clefs = part.flat.getElementsByClass('Clef') # Correct method to
access clefs

    # Check if clefs exist for the part
    if clefs:
clef = clefs[0] # Assuming the first clef is the relevant one
    if clef.sign == 'G': # Treble clef (G clef)
        # Color all notes red for treble clef
        for n in part.recurse().notes:
            if isinstance(n, note.Note):
                n.style.color = 'red' # Red for treble clef notes
    elif clef.sign == 'F': # Bass clef (F clef)
        # Color all notes green for bass clef
        for n in part.recurse().notes:
            if isinstance(n, note.Note):
                n.style.color = 'green' # Green for bass clef notes

    return score

# Export function based on user preference
def export_score(score, output_type):
    if output_type == "visual":
        score.show('musicxml.pdf') # Generates PDF output
    elif output_type == "audio":
        score.write('midi', fp='output.mid')

# Main pipeline
def run_pipeline(input_file):
    score = converter.parse(input_file)
    # Apply color changes for clefs
    score = apply_clef_color_aid(score)
    export_score(score, user_config["output_type"])

# Example usage
if __name__ == "__main__":
    run_pipeline("/Users/firasali/Documents/D CSc/piano.musicxml")

```

Below is an example of piano score of the modified code above. The notes in the treble clef are all **red**, and in the bass clef **green** (Fig. 23).

FIGURE 23: DYSLEXIA – COLOURED PIANO MUSICAL SCORE

For completeness, some music writing software would allow manual colouring of notes. However, for large scores, especially ones with a grand staff such as the piano, this process is laborious and liable to human errors.

This model is a novel application of TBMs designed to improve music score accessibility for individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. By leveraging the visual processing strengths of TBMs, the model automates the well-established practice of colour-coding musical notes. In addition, the model facilitates effortless transposition of music pieces.

The impact of this approach is twofold: It significantly reduces the workload for educators while empowering non-expert users to interact more fluently with musical notation. As one of the first AI-driven tools to integrate visual adaptation and key transposition in a unified, accessible framework, this model represents a promising direction for inclusive music education technology.

In the next chapter, a small-sized experiment to test readability involving children with Dyslexia and/or ADHD is conducted to test the small dataset created by the model in this chapter.

CHAPTER 7: THE EXPERIMENT

This chapter describes an experiment which was conducted to put some of the concepts discussed in this thesis to a practical human-intervention trial, albeit with a limited scope.

7.1 DESIGN AND METHOD

An experiment was designed to test a number of school children between the ages of six and eleven years. The aim was to measure the effect of simplifying a baseline sentence for reading and comprehension.

The baseline was modified in various ways as discussed above. The first version was aimed at children with Dyslexia. In addition to simplifications, some words in the baseline were altered phonetically in line with the model in the previous section. The second version was aimed at children with ADHD. In this version, some rules of Bionic Reading© (Casutt, n.d.) were applied to the simplified sentence. The third version was a combination of the previous two versions, aimed at comorbid children with both Dyslexia and ADHD.

To prepare for this experiment, an invitation was sent to the parents and carers of school children of two key stages, KS1 and KS2. A sample of eight children with either Dyslexia and/or ADHD took part in this experiment. Of the two groups, KS1 and KS2, these were subdivided into groups of children with Dyslexia, ADHD, and Dyslexia/ADHD.

The sentences used were originally intended to be selected from the dataset in Appendix A, generated by the model in Chapter 6 of this thesis. Upon closer examination, many of the generated sentences were found to be unsuitable for the intended purpose due to inconsistencies within the dataset. Additionally, several outputs reflected misapplications of the defined transformation rules, indicating limitations in the model's interpretive accuracy. An example of these inconsistencies is changing 'gh' to 'off' where it should be transformed to 'ow'. The model did not pay attention to the sequence of letters before or ahead to consistently make the correct decisions.

The sentences were then chosen by prompting ChatGPT to produce a few examples suitable for KS1 and KS2, as well as comprehension questions. Even the generated sentences were not based on any Dyslexia/ADHD dataset, leaving some aspects of the test's materials with room for improvement.

Since ChatGPT did not use an external dataset, the sentence pairs, both original and simplified versions, were custom generated based on:

- Typical sentence structures and vocabulary suitable for KS1 and KS2 levels.
- Linguistic features known to challenge children with Dyslexia (e.g. irregular spellings, complex syntax).
- Attention and memory considerations for ADHD, favouring shorter, clearer phrasing in the simplified versions.

The simplifications were guided by readability principles, phonetic regularity, and age-appropriate vocabulary, but not drawn from a specific corpus.

A further improvement on this approach, which is somehow generic in nature, would be to collaborate with specialist Dyslexia/ADHD practitioners, and/or educational psychologists to build a more robust dataset. This was informed by a brief discussion with child F from the participants in this experiment, who remarked that they found some spellings of the transformed words, off-putting and unfamiliar.

Contributions from practicing specialists could significantly enhance the quality of future materials and generally aid the formation of a more robust dataset.

7.2 THE PARTICIPANTS

An invitation was sent to the parents and carers of children of a primary school where the researcher acts as a governor. Ten parents responded and volunteered their children but only eight were chosen for their ability to read at KS1 and KS2 level. The conditions of the children were mixed. Two children presented with Dyslexia, two with ADHD, and four comorbid with both Dyslexia and ADHD.

Not all participants were clinically diagnosed but were highly suspected by their parents or the school to be affected by either/both of these conditions. Therefore, they were deemed to be valid subjects for this small and resource-limited experiment.

There was a fair distribution of gender in the sample – three boys and five girls. The experiment was conducted in-person on the chosen school's premises.

7.3 APPARATUS AND MATERIALS

The main materials used for this experiment were the sentences to be read by the participants. These were divided according to the key stages and were as follows:

7.3.1 KEY STAGE 1 AND 2 SENTENCES

Here are the sentences for Key Stage 1:

Baseline – After the heavy rain stopped, the children rushed outside to jump in the muddy puddles.

For Dyslexia – Wen the rayn endid, the kidz ran owt to jump in the mud.

For ADHD – **When the rain ended, the kids ran out to jump in the mud.**

For Dyslexia/ADHD – **Wen the rayn endid, the kidz ran owt to jump in the mud.**

Their comprehension questions:

1 - What did the kids do after the rain? Answer – Went/rushed/hurried out(side)

2 - What did the kids do outside? Answer – Jumped in the mud

Here are the sentences for Key Stage 2:

Baseline – Although the ancient forest was dark and silent, Mia bravely ventured in to find the hidden waterfall.

For Dyslexia – The forist woz old and kwyet, but Meea went in to fynd the sekret wort-fawl.

For ADHD – **The forest was old and quiet, but Mia went in to find the secret waterfall.**

For Dyslexia/ADHD – **The forist woz old and kwyet, but Meea went in to fynd the sekret wort-fawl.**

Their comprehension questions:

1 - Describe the forest? Answer – Old dark quiet

2 - what was Mia looking for? Answer – Secret waterfall

The sentences were printed in large regular font (Times New Roman 20) in landscape format.

7.3.2 INVITATION AND CONSENT

The invitation:

The following email was sent to all parents and carers of the children.

Subject: Invitation to Participate in a Reading Study on Dyslexia and ADHD Readability

Dear Parents and Carers,

I hope this message finds you well. My name is Firas Ali, and I have had the privilege of serving as a governor at the Vineyard school for over six years. I am currently conducting a research project, as part of my PhD in AI, that aims to improve the readability of educational materials for children with Dyslexia and ADHD I developed.

As part of this research, I am inviting pupils with either of these conditions to take part in a small, ethically approved study. The experiment involves reading two short passages, each followed by a brief comprehension test. The activity is designed to be accessible, engaging, and will take no more than 10 minutes in total, to be conducted on the school's premises during normal schooling hours.

Please rest assured that the study will fully observe all ethical principles, including:

- *Complete anonymity of all participants*
- *No personal data collected or stored*
- *Voluntary participation with the option to withdraw at any time*

Your child's involvement could make a valuable contribution to improving how educational content is designed for learners with diverse needs.

If you are happy for your child to take part or would like more information, please reply to this email with your child's details and condition.

Thank you for considering this opportunity.

Warm regards,

Firas Ali

Governor, The Vineyard School

The Consent:

Parental Consent Form for Participation in Research

Study Title: PhD research in Dyslexia and ADHD readability

Researcher: Firas Ali

Institution: Kennedy University

Contact Information: Mob 07967496939

Introduction

You are being asked to allow your child to participate in a research study. This form provides information about the study so you can make an informed decision regarding your child's participation. Please read it carefully and ask any questions you may have before deciding whether to allow your child to participate.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to test a new method to help readability of children with these conditions.

Study Procedures

If you agree to allow your child to participate, they will be asked to read two sentences and answer few questions about them to check their comprehension. The test would last about 10 minutes.

Risks and Discomforts

There are no anticipated risks in this test.

Confidentiality

All information collected during this study will be kept confidential. Your child's identity will not be disclosed in any reports or publications. Data will be stored securely and will only be accessible to authorised research personnel.

Voluntary Participation

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You have the right to withdraw your child from the study at any time, for any reason, without penalty or loss of benefits to which your child is otherwise entitled.

Procedure

1. A room with two entries will be chosen as a venue for this experiment on the school's premises.
 2. Children will be the only participants in the room with two DBS⁹-checked adults.
 3. Explain to each child that they are to read two sentences at their normal reading speed silently with an indication of starting and stopping so time can be recorded on a stopwatch, and they will be asked two simple question to see if they understood the sentences.
 4. The sentences will be presented individually printed on A4 landscape format in a clear child-friendly font of Times New Roman in black size 20 for absolute clarity.
 5. To indicate start and finish of reading, the children will be asked to turn on a desk lamp placed by them at the start, and turn it off at the end.
 6. Children will be asked not to discuss the experiment with other children. To control for this, children will be grouped and made to enter from one end of the room and exit from another.
-
-

Contact Information

If you have any questions or concerns about the study, please contact the researcher at phone number above.

Statement of Consent

By signing this form, you are giving your consent for your child to participate in the study. You confirm that you have read and understood the information provided above and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

I, the undersigned, consent to my child's participation in this study.

Parent/Guardian Name: _____

Child's Name: _____

Signature of Parent/Guardian: _____

Date: _____

Researcher Name: Firas Ali

Signature of Researcher: _____

Date: _____

⁹ Disclosure and Barring Service – A UK government service for background checks on individuals working with vulnerable groups.

7.3.3 OTHER APPARATUS

For timing of the readings, an iPhone stopwatch was used. A battery touch operated multi-coloured light was used for the children to indicate the start and finish of the reading.

7.4 PROCEDURE

Participants were individually met in a meeting room, and the procedure was explained to them. Their names and key stage were confirmed, after which they were presented first with the base-line sentence relevant to their key stage and condition. They were then asked to touch the light as they start silently reading and touch it again at the end. The time of the reading was recorded on the iPhone.

They were then asked the relative comprehension questions, and their reply was noted down for later assessment. They were subsequently presented with the modified sentence and asked to repeat the procedure while their new time was recorded.

After that, they were asked the relative comprehension questions, and their reply was noted down for later assessment.

7.5 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Conducting small-scale experiments with children requires careful adherence to ethical principles to ensure the safety, rights, and well-being of young participants. Key ethical considerations include informed consent, minimising harm, and ensuring the research is appropriate and beneficial for the child population involved.

Although Kennedy University did not have their own ethical terms, it was suggested that the experiment should follow the principles set out in the Belmont report summarised below.

In addition to that report, and since this experiment was going to be conducted in a United Kingdom school, the ethical guidance of experimenting involving children (NSPCC Learning) was also observed.

The Belmont Report (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979) is a foundational document in research ethics in the United States of America. It outlines key ethical principles and guidelines for conducting research involving human participants.

Below is a summary of the Belmont Report:

1. Respect for Persons

- Individuals should be treated as autonomous agents.
- Those with diminished autonomy (e.g. children, people with cognitive impairments) are entitled to additional protection.
- Informed consent is crucial – participants must be fully informed and voluntarily agree to participate.

2. Beneficence

- Researchers must maximise possible benefits and minimise potential harm.
- Risk-benefit analysis is essential to ensure participants are not exposed to unnecessary harm.

3. Justice

- Fairness in the distribution of research benefits and burdens.
- The selection of research subjects should be equitable and not exploit vulnerable populations.

The Belmont Report laid the ethical foundation for Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) and modern research ethics standards.

Since this experiment was to be conducted on the school's premises, a written consent was also obtained from the head teacher.

7.6 METRICS

The reading times were measured using a stopwatch for each sentence. The results of each trial were then measured in each category against the baseline and average was calculated to assess if there was any improvement or otherwise.

Comprehension was assessed and scored by the conductor of the experiment. The data was calculated according to the excel Experiment Data sheet in section 7.7 below.

For a thorough statistical analysis, the data of time and comprehension was assessed for normalisation, and the appropriate test method was then applied according to the level of the normal distribution of the data.

7.7 THE DATA

Child	Key Stage	Condition	Base-Time [BT]seconds	Base-Comprehension % [BC]	Test-Time [TT]seconds	Test-Comprehension % [TC]	Time Difference (BT - TT)	Time Improvement %	Comprehension Diffrence [TC - BC]
B	KS2	Dyslexia/ADHD	9.08	50	19.15	100	10.07	1.11	50.00
C	KS2	Dyslexia	11.73	50	11.51	50	0.22	0.02	0.00
D	KS2	ADHD	8.68	50	9.33	100	0.65	0.07	50.00
E	KS2	Dyslexia/ADHD	34.59	0	24.7	0	9.89	0.29	0.00
F	KS2	Dyslexia	11.93	80	8.45	80	3.48	0.29	0.00
G	KS1	ADHD	3.26	0	3.58	50	0.32	0.10	50.00
H	KS1	ADHD	13.58	50	7.46	50	6.12	0.45	0.00
Average			11.60625	35	10.5225	53.75			
Overall Average							1.08	0.03	18.75
Dyslexia Average							1.85	0.16	0.00
ADHD Average							0.94	0.07	16.67
Dyslexia/ADHD Average							0.09	0.41	25.00

7.8 RESULT ANALYSIS

The first step in the analysis process was checking the collected data for normality. This was carried out for both comprehension and time before and after the test. To test the normalisation of the comprehension data, the following Python code, invoking the Shapiro-Wilk test, was used:

```
from scipy.stats import shapiro
import pandas as pd
# Load your cleaned data
```

```

df = pd.read_excel('/Users/firasali/Documents/D
CSc/Experiment/Experiment Data.xlsx', skiprows=2)
df.columns = [
    "Child", "Key Stage", "Condition", "BaseTime",
    "BaseComprehension",
    "TestTime", "TestComprehension", "TimeDifference",
    "TimeImprovement",
    "ComprehensionDifference"
]
df = df.dropna(subset=["BaseComprehension", "TestComprehension"])
# Convert relevant columns to numeric
df["BaseComprehension"] = pd.to_numeric(df["BaseComprehension"],
errors='coerce')
df["TestComprehension"] = pd.to_numeric(df["TestComprehension"],
errors='coerce')
# Run Shapiro-Wilk tests
shapiro_base = shapiro(df["BaseComprehension"])
shapiro_test = shapiro(df["TestComprehension"])
print(f"Base comprehension p-value: {shapiro_base.pvalue:.4f}")
print(f"Test comprehension p-value: {shapiro_test.pvalue:.4f}")

```

The result of that check was:

```

(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 % python3 ex-
normal.py

Base comprehension p-value: 0.0205

Test comprehension p-value: 0.1499

```

The interpretation of these Shapiro-Wilk test results (Table 12):

TABLE 12: RESULTS INTERPRETATION

Variable	p-value	Interpretation
BaseComprehension	0.0205 (<0.05)	Not normally distributed
TestComprehension	0.1499 (≥0.05)	Likely normal

Even though the **TestComprehension** scores were normal, the **BaseComprehension** scores were not. This means that the scores do not follow a normal and even pattern. Therefore, a non-parametric test needed to be used to measure the significance of the results.

While most scores were around the average, a few were very high or very low. Due to this, the usual statistical tests cannot be used on such a diverse spread of scores, necessitating another method namely the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, which would work better on unbalanced data.

Below is the Python code to run this alternative method:

```
from scipy.stats import wilcoxon
import pandas as pd
# Load your cleaned data
df = pd.read_excel("Experiment Data.xlsx", skiprows=2)
df.columns = [
    "Child", "Key Stage", "Condition", "BaseTime",
    "BaseComprehension",
    "TestTime", "TestComprehension", "TimeDifference",
    "TimeImprovement",
    "ComprehensionDifference"
]
df = df.dropna(subset=["BaseComprehension", "TestComprehension"])
df["BaseComprehension"] = pd.to_numeric(df["BaseComprehension"],
errors='coerce')
df["TestComprehension"] = pd.to_numeric(df["TestComprehension"],
errors='coerce')
# Wilcoxon signed-rank test
stat, p = wilcoxon(df["BaseComprehension"], df["TestComprehension"])
print(f"Wilcoxon signed-rank test p-value: {p:.4f}")
```

The result of that was:

```
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 % python3 ex-test.py
Wilcoxon signed-rank test p-value: 0.0625
```

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test gave a p-value of 0.0625. That means, assuming the typical significance level of 0.05, this result is not statistically significant to reject the null hypothesis that the test materials do not make a difference to the outcome.

With a Wilcoxon signed-rank test p-value of 0.0625:

- The p-value is slightly above the common significance threshold of 0.05.

- This suggests there is not quite enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis at the 5% level.
- In other words, the test does not show a statistically significant difference between the paired samples.

Interpretation:

- The data might show a trend or weak evidence of a difference, but it is not strong enough to confidently say there is a difference.
- The result is borderline, so one might want to consider the context and the practical significance of the findings, not just the p-value.

Anecdotally, child B reported to their parents that they did very well with the test material and even enjoyed it and believe they discovered some good aid for their comprehension. Unfortunately, when the base reading time is compared with the test time, there is a deficit of over 100% which may explain why that subject's comprehension was 100% better than their base comprehension.

The implementation of this experiment depended on such interaction with the subjects as in the instance of child F, reported above, and the use of the multi-coloured touch lights to indicate the start and finish of the reading activity, to gamify the trial. This was effective evidenced by child H requesting to "have another go" after they finished their main trial.

This provided another dimension and insight to this experiment which should be adopted by future ones to gain an in-depth knowledge of the subject and possible strength or weakness of the experiment.

The analysis below was the carried out after eliminating child A's results (the new file was Experiment Data-1) who was reported by his teacher to show no signs of any neurodivergence despite the parent's suspicions. This was evident to the researcher when observing the child's reading speed and level of comprehension. Therefore, this result was deemed to be the outlier of this small set of data.

The data was then checked for normalisation and turned out to be approximately normal. As stated above on examination of the previous batch of

BaseComprehension, normally distributed data implies that most scores fall within a realistic range and no values are much higher or much lower than the rest. It was, therefore, suitable for testing via a method called t-test, which was carried out by the following Python code:

```
import pandas as pd
from scipy.stats import ttest_rel, shapiro
# Load your Excel data
df = pd.read_excel('/Users/firasali/Documents/D
CSc/Experiment/Experiment Data-1.xlsx', skiprows=2)
# Rename columns FIRST
df.columns = [
    "Child", "Key Stage", "Condition", "BaseTime",
    "BaseComprehension",
    "TestTime", "TestComprehension", "TimeDifference",
    "TimeImprovement",
    "ComprehensionDifference"
]
# THEN drop rows with missing values in comprehension columns
df = df.dropna(subset=["BaseComprehension", "TestComprehension"])
# Convert to numeric (in case of string or mixed types)
df["BaseComprehension"] = pd.to_numeric(df["BaseComprehension"],
errors='coerce')
df["TestComprehension"] = pd.to_numeric(df["TestComprehension"],
errors='coerce')
# Run Shapiro-Wilk tests
shapiro_base = shapiro(df["BaseComprehension"])
shapiro_test = shapiro(df["TestComprehension"])
print(f"Base comprehension p-value: {shapiro_base.pvalue:.4f}")
print(f"Test comprehension p-value: {shapiro_test.pvalue:.4f}")
# Paired t-test
t_stat, p_value = ttest_rel(df["BaseComprehension"],
df["TestComprehension"])
print(f"Paired t-test p-value: {p_value:.4f}")
```

The result:

```
(.venv) firasali@Firass-Mac-mini PythonProject1 % python3 T-TEST-
DYS.PY.py
Base comprehension p-value: 0.1088
Test comprehension p-value: 0.2216
Paired t-test p-value: 0.0468
```

Interpretation of output

1. Base comprehension p-value (Shapiro): 0.1088
2. Test comprehension p-value (Shapiro): 0.2216 → Both are above 0.05, so:
 - The distributions of **BaseComprehension** and **TestComprehension** are approximately normal.
 - This validates the use of a paired t-test.
3. Paired t-test p-value: 0.0468 → This is below 0.05, so:
 - The difference in comprehension is statistically significant.
 - One can reject the null hypothesis that there is no difference between base and test comprehension scores.

There is evidence that this test condition led to significantly different comprehension scores compared to the base condition at the 5% significance level. This simply means that the test result was positive, and the trial has made a marked improvement in the comprehension.

By eliminating the outlier's data, the value that did not fit within the range of scores, this result clearly indicates improving accessibility for neurodiverse learners without adding cognitive load, which is a central premise of this research.

The moral of this step is to ensure that participants are properly diagnosed with the correct condition and categorised accordingly. This will ensure data normalisation and avoid skewed results. In this experiment, a mixture of formal and informal assessment was followed due to the limited resources and time set for this.

Subsequently, the above analyses were repeated to check the significance or lack of it, and time improvement in both sets of data. The same Python codes above was used after changing the parameter into base and test times.

The Shapiro-Wilk normality test results for the first complete set of data was:

- Base time: $p = 0.0058$
- Test time: $p = 0.1961$

Since Base time's "p" value is less than 0.05, then Base time is not normally distributed. This violates the assumption required for parametric tests like a paired t-test. The "p" value of **TestTime** is greater than 0.05, then **TestTime** is approximately normal.

Once more, since one of the two sets (**BaseTime**) is not normally distributed, the pair must be treated as non-normal. Therefore, Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used on this pair of sets of data and the result was:

Wilcoxon signed-rank test p-value (time) was 0.4961

A p-value of 0.4961 is well above 0.05, so there is no statistically significant difference in reading time between the base and test conditions.

The trials above were redone after removing child A's date from the datasheet. Without child A, the normality test yielded:

- Base time p-value (Shapiro): 0.0057
- Test time p-value (Shapiro): 0.2614
- **BaseTime** is not normally distributed ($p < 0.05 \rightarrow$ reject normality).
- **TestTime** is approximately normal ($p > 0.05 \rightarrow$ fail to reject normality).

Since at least one of the samples (**BaseTime**) violates normality, one should not use a paired t-test to compare **BaseTime** and **TestTime**. Instead, one should use the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, which is a non-parametric test that does not assume normal distribution.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test p-value (Time) was 0.5469

- This p-value is much higher than 0.05.
- Therefore, one cannot reject the null hypothesis.
- There is no statistically significant difference in reading times between the base and test conditions.

This result shows while comprehension scores improved significantly (0.0468), the reading time did not change in a statistically meaningful way.

Essentially, the intervention improved understanding without requiring more time. Simply put, it didn't slow them down, which is valuable in dyslexia-related interventions.

7.8.1 READING TIME ANALYSIS

To assess whether the test condition influenced the time children spent reading, a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was conducted on paired reading times from the base and test conditions. This non-parametric test was chosen based on a prior Shapiro-Wilk normality test, which revealed that **BaseTime** was not normally distributed ($p = 0.0058$), while **TestTime** was approximately normal ($p = 0.1961$).

The Wilcoxon test yielded a p-value of 0.4961, indicating that the difference in reading times between conditions was not statistically significant. In other words, there was no reliable change in the time it took participants to complete the task under the test condition compared to the base condition.

This result is especially meaningful when considered alongside the earlier finding that comprehension scores almost significantly improved ($p = 0.0625$) under the test condition. The combination of these outcomes suggests that the intervention slightly improved understanding, without increasing the cognitive or temporal load on the students.

This is a desirable result in the context of interventions for children with Dyslexia and/or ADHD, as it indicates enhanced comprehension without sacrificing efficiency.

7.8.2 COMPREHENSION SCORE ANALYSIS

To recap, with the complete data (including child A) for comprehension, the following results were obtained:

Normality (Shapiro-Wilk Test)

Measure	Base p-value	Test p-value	Conclusion
Comprehension	0.0205	0.1499	Non-normal → Use Wilcoxon
Time	0.0058	0.1961	Non-normal → Use Wilcoxon

Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test

Measure	Wilcoxon p-value	Interpretation
Comprehension	0.0625	Not statistically significant (just above 0.05)
Time	0.4961	Evidently not significant

To evaluate the impact of the intervention on comprehension and reading time, Shapiro-Wilk tests were first conducted to assess normality. For comprehension scores, the base condition was not normally distributed ($p = 0.0205$), whereas the test condition was approximately normal ($p = 0.1499$). Similarly, for time measures, the base condition violated normality ($p = 0.0058$), while the test condition did not ($p = 0.1961$). As at least one variable in each pair deviated from normality, the non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used for both comparisons.

The Wilcoxon test for comprehension scores yielded a p-value of 0.0625, suggesting a trend toward improved comprehension under the test condition; however, this result did not reach statistical significance at the conventional alpha level of 0.05. In contrast, the comparison of reading time across conditions showed no significant difference ($p = 0.4961$), indicating that participants read at a similar pace in both conditions.

Overall, the results suggest that the intervention may have contributed to improved comprehension without increasing reading time, although further study with a larger sample size is recommended to confirm this effect.

To evaluate the impact of the test condition on comprehension, without the data from child A, a t-test was conducted comparing scores from the base and test conditions. Prior to this, a Shapiro-Wilk normality test confirmed that both sets of scores were approximately normally distributed (Base: $p = 0.1088$, Test: $p = 0.2216$), justifying the use of a parametric test.

The paired t-test produced a p-value of 0.0468, which is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This result indicates that the test condition significantly improved comprehension scores compared to the base condition.

Taken together with the time analysis, the results show that the test condition enhanced comprehension did not significantly affect reading time. This suggests that the intervention successfully supported deeper understanding without imposing additional time or cognitive load – a key goal in educational interventions for children with learning differences such as Dyslexia and ADHD.

7.8.3 RESULTS SUMMARY

The table below, sums up the results analyses (Table 13):

TABLE 13: RESULTS ANALYSIS

Experiment	Comprehension	Significance	Reading Time	Significance
Complete	0.0625	Not statistically significant but converging (just above 0.05)	0.4961	Evidently not significant (much higher than 0.05)
Without Child A	0.0468	Statistically significant (just under 0.05)	0.5469	Evidently not significant (much higher than 0.05)

7.9 DISCUSSION

The final takeaway from the analyses is that the test condition showed a promising trend toward improving comprehension without significantly increasing reading time.

Although the improvement in comprehension did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.0625$), it was close to the conventional threshold and suggests that the intervention had a positive effect. Importantly, this improvement was achieved without any measurable cost to reading speed ($p = 0.4961$), indicating that the intervention did not impose any additional cognitive or temporal load on the subjects.

This outcome is especially noteworthy given the context in which the experiment was conducted. The study was not based on extensive pre-existing research into tailored Dyslexia or ADHD-specific datasets, nor did it benefit from a large-scale funding or institutional support. The materials were developed with limited resources and without highly specialised personalisation, yet they still showed the potential to benefit young readers, particularly those with learning difficulties. This points to the robustness and practicality of the intervention design.

From an educational standpoint, the findings are encouraging. For students with cognitive or learning divergencies such as Dyslexia or ADHD, improvements in comprehension without added time costs are highly desirable. Many traditional accommodations may help comprehension but at the expense of fluency or speed. An intervention that maintains or even improves comprehension while preserving time demands, aligns well with inclusive education goals and principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL).

UDL (Rose, et. al., 2000) is a framework based on cognitive neuroscience and educational theory. Its aim is to achieve inclusive education and equity in pedagogy by creating a learning environment that accommodates the diverse needs of all learners by offering flexible methods of presentation, engagement, and expression.

Moreover, from the result of the experiment in this study, the fact that even a small-scale trial yielded near-significant results suggests that with further refinement, the intervention could become even more effective. Some of the refinements could be achieved by tuning the language simplification rules, increasing individual tailoring, and/or incorporating feedback from specialists in neurodiverse education. A

larger sample size may also increase statistical power, potentially confirming the observed trends.

The results of this experiment underscore the need for a more flexible and adaptive approach to addressing specific reading difficulties. As demonstrated by the present experiment and the development of a linguistic rule-based model in section 6.1 of Chapter 6, the dataset generated (Appendix A) was insufficient in uniformly supporting readers across the sample. The substantial individual variation observed in participants' performance highlights the importance of accommodating diverse learner profiles rather than relying on a one-size-fits-all solution.

Moreover, informal feedback from participants revealed that certain phonetic simplification strategies, intended to facilitate decoding, were, in some cases, perceived as confusing or counterintuitive. This has likely introduced additional cognitive load, potentially affected comprehension and diminishing the intended benefits of the intervention.

An application such as the one proposed in section 6.2 of Chapter 6, offers a promising way forward. By allowing for a high degree of personalisation, such a tool could be tailored to the unique cognitive and linguistic needs of each user. This would ensure support without introducing unnecessary complexity, thereby enhancing the accessibility and effectiveness of reading interventions for neurodiverse learners.

The findings underscore the viability and potential impact of low-resource, language-based interventions for enhancing educational accessibility among neurodiverse students. They serve as a call for further development, evaluation, and scaling, with the aim of integrating such tools into broader literacy and accessibility strategies in education.

Considering the wider implication of implementing a methodology such as this would first require an extensive and comprehensive scaled research into the symptoms of Dyslexia and ADHD. It will also require assembling a strong team of educational psychologists, Special Education Need (SEN) teachers, and, of course, a technically able group with specific AI bias. Such project will need access to a

considerable amount of computational power to create and store massive linguistic datasets and processing power for the generated AI models.

The intervention would then take the form of a custom-built application that dynamically simplifies reading materials using a TBM or a well refined rule-based linguistic transformations method.

A brief examination of even a relatively small country such as the United Kingdom (UK), suggests that different regional datasets may also have to be generated to accommodate regional accents and phonetic variations.

Phonetic teaching across the UK varies significantly due to differing frameworks. There are four distinct approaches to forming the curricula in the UK depending on the geographical regions. These are:

- England – The curricula here is shaped by the Rose Review (Rose, 2006) and formalised through the National Curriculum (Department for Education [DfE], 2014). The systematic synthetic phonics (SSP) is emphasised and reinforced by the Reading Framework (Department for Education [DfE], 2021).
- Scotland – The Curriculum for Excellence promotes a more integrated approach, offering schools greater flexibility in balancing phonics with broader language development (Education Scotland, n.d.).
- Wales – The approach to form the curricula supports phonics as part of a holistic framework prioritising oracy and meaning making (Welsh Government, 2022).
- Northern Ireland – Here, phonics forms part of a broader developmental literacy framework but is not prescriptively taught (Council for the Curriculum, Examinations and Assessment [CCEA], 2007).

The above would be the main logistical undertaking to widen the potential benefit of this approach to generating speciality datasets and LLMs to aid reading accessibility for school children with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. Prior to that, the experiment carried out for this study needs to be scaled up significantly to justify national-level implementation.

Even after a successful agreement on the principle of such project informed by a scaled-up experiment, the next barrier to this is the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) of a nation-wide project to be adopted by the regional educational authorities for inclusion in the curriculum of reading.

The CBA will evaluate the educational and economic value of a phonetic text simplification tool designed for learners with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. The goal is to determine whether the cognitive and academic gains justify the development and implementation costs.

The potential benefit of this in the context of education will be highly impactful in the sense of standardising teaching methods for children with Dyslexia and/or ADHD nationwide, with consideration to regional variations. This will take the task of guessing and the burden of preparation away from the educators. Further, an application such as this, would have concentrated the most advanced and valuable knowledge of specialist educators and educational psychologists at the disposal of the teachers.

In a survey of AI assistive tools for neurodivergent children (Barua, et. al., 2022), the authors recognise the difficulty that teachers face preparing individualised lessons to help children overcome their learning disabilities, and how this process takes a lot of time and efforts that are not afforded to them. Schools, in general, have shortages of appropriate learning resources. Therefore, an assistive learning tool that can be personalised for children's individual learning challenges and needs would be very helpful for teachers and a great support in helping students meet their individual goals.

The preceding survey highlights the effectiveness of AI-assisted tools developed through machine learning models in supporting students with neurodevelopmental disorders. While many of these tools have focused on improving social interaction and providing educational support, the findings also suggest that AI holds broader potential to enhance various dimensions of learning outcomes for this population.

7.10 EXPERIMENT CONCLUSION

In the previous chapter a rule-based model was developed with the aim to aid readability for those with Dyslexia. It was hoped that the transformation this model achieves could also help readability for other neurodivergent individuals such as those with ADHD. The ultimate aim of the model was to accomplish faster and better comprehension of the text read.

Due to the limited scope, and with the constraints on this research, that model was developed and based on common patterns in English that are known to cause difficulty for dyslexic readers, and the sources included:

1. Phonetic simplification principles – e.g. changing "ph" to "f", simplifying "ough" to "aw" or similar sounds.
2. Removal of silent letters – e.g. dropping the "k" in "knight" or the "b" in "thumb".
3. Established research and dyslexia-focused educational resources such as literacy intervention guides, Dyslexia support tools, and phonics-based simplification systems used in early reading education.

These rules were then applied to a set of 50 sentence pairs (original and simplified), generating a third version (generated-simplified) using that system, which served as a basis for training or evaluating a rule-based model later.

The simplicity of the rule-based model provides some advantages such as:

- Feasibility – It demonstrates the practicality of automatic dyslexia-friendly text generation without relying on resource-intensive methods.
- Efficiency – The approach is computationally efficient and accessible within the timescale and resource limits of this research.
- Establishing a baseline – It serves as a baseline for future, more sophisticated models that might incorporate machine learning techniques for enhanced performance.

However, since that model was developed without any input from SEN teachers or child psychologists, it became clear when preparing for the practical experiment in

this chapter, that the missing contribution from those specialists, had rendered the resulting sentences unsuitable for this experiment as detailed above. The model's output contained inconsistencies and weaknesses which could have been avoided with input from specialist in the field, and with finetuning.

The biggest advantage of this exercise was that it provided a structured and interpretable foundation for simplifying text in a way that directly addresses the known reading challenges faced by individuals with Dyslexia.

By using explicit, rule-based transformations, the approach ensured transparency in how simplifications were made, allowing educators, researchers, and developers to clearly understand and control the changes. This not only made the system more explainable and adaptable to different learners' needs, but also offered a reliable baseline for evaluating the performance of TBMs trained to automate similar transformations. In short, it bridged human linguistic insight with machine learning, offering a hybrid pathway toward more effective and dyslexia-friendly text processing.

The exercise could have been significantly strengthened with input from human specialists such as child psychologists and Special Educational Needs (SEN) teachers. Their expertise would have provided deeper insight into how children with Dyslexia and/or ADHD cognitively process language, allowing for more targeted and nuanced rule creation. For instance, SEN professionals could have advised on which linguistic patterns are most confusing or frustrating for individuals with Dyslexia in real classroom settings. While child psychologists could have contributed knowledge about cognitive load, attention, and working memory, all crucial factors in designing accessible text.

Such expert input would have helped validate and refine the simplification rules beyond phonetic logic alone, ensuring they aligned with pedagogical strategies and cognitive accessibility. This collaboration could also have guided the evaluation process, helping determine not just whether the transformed sentences were simpler linguistically, but whether they were actually easier to comprehend, less anxiety-inducing, and more engaging for children with Dyslexia. In this way, the rule set

would not only be technically sound, but also developmentally and educationally grounded.

The rule-based approach which was reflected in the proposed app in that chapter, extends further to individuals with either Dyslexia or ADHD. It provided the means to customise the output according to very specific individual needs. The app can be used by an individual who knows their exact requirement, or by an educator to help a specific individual with very specific needs anywhere and any time without the need to refer back to a system that may not be as freely accessible.

Despite the limitations of the model from Chapter 6 it serves as a foundational marker for developing more advanced TBMs, which when enriched with insights from child psychologists and SEN specialists could evolve into powerful, adaptive AI tool capable of delivering personalised, cognitively informed text simplification at scale.

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This research seeks to lay the groundwork for future, more in-depth investigations into the capabilities of the most widely adopted AI models. Furthermore, it also considers the potential of alternative models available on various platforms, such as Hugging Face, for further exploration and evaluation.

Although some forms of comparison do exist, such as the Hugging Face Leaderboard discussed in Chapter 1 of this thesis, they are invariably carried out by some empirical metrics. This is an attempt to avoid bias in the measurement of quality and efficacy. However, in the researcher's opinion, it is the cost and lack of human expertise that is the obstacle for real-life evaluation. Therefore, the responsibility of that falls on the shoulders of the academic community as a whole.

As in conducting the trials in this research, human (qualitative) input is crucial in evaluating AI models. This is particularly essential for creativity judgment, nuance, or user impact. It is especially important in:

1. Natural Language Understanding and Generation (e.g. chatbots, translators) – where humans only can assess fluency, relevance, coherence, and tone, which are hard to quantify reliably.
2. Creative Tasks (e.g. music, art, storytelling, design) – as metrics do not capture aesthetic value or originality as humans would.
3. Instruction Following and Alignment – as even if outputs are technically correct, they may fail to match users' intent or social norms.
4. Bias, Fairness, and Ethics – where quantitative tests often miss subtle or context-specific harms and therefore, human input is needed to identify bias, stereotypes, or offensive content.
5. General-Purpose Models (e.g. GPT, Gemini) – broad human evaluation helps measure performance across diverse, unpredictable scenarios.

In summary, while quantitative metrics such as accuracy, BLEU, or CO₂ cost are essential for assessing performance, qualitative human evaluation remains indispensable for determining what truly matters to users.

8.1 THE TRIALS

The initial aim of this research was to identify the most efficient TBM for domain-domain transformation by surveying the major publicly accessible models. This was planned to be carried out by a large-scale trial with multiple disciplines and experts in those subjects.

Once such a TBM is qualitatively identified by the experts, and quantitatively by some formulae, it would have been subjected to in-depth study to identify the architecture and features that make it a better all-round model. Should more than one model have been identified as such, their combined characteristics would have constituted the candidate for a universal model for this task.

Pilot trials were conducted initially in order to reject the Null Hypothesis which assumed there is no significant difference between these various models. This was soon rejected after demonstrating that a marked difference between those models exists.

From those trials, a table of results is presented herewith (Table 14):

TABLE 14: TRIAL RESULTS

TBM	Trial1	Trial2	Trial3	Trial4	Average
<i>ChatGPT</i>	0.9022	0.6609	0.7840	0.8402	0.797
<i>Gemini</i>	0.7176	0.7310	0.7923	0.8412	0.771
<i>Claude</i>	0.7987	0.6635	0.7912	0.7318	0.743
<i>Meta AI</i>	0.8890	0.6938	0.8351	0.7129	0.783
<i>Bing Chat</i>	0.8257	0.7149	0.8049	0.7599	0.776
<i>DeepSeek</i>	0.6796	0.5529	0.7827	0.7174	0.683

The trials conducted in this research help to demonstrate that, on average across multiple domains, the difference seems to range from 1.79% between the two highest scoring models (ChatGPT & Meta AI), to 16.69% between the highest and lowest scoring TBMs (ChatGPT & DeepSeek).

Evidently, much larger trials and many other subjects need to be chosen for a more comprehensive coverage and more confidence in the result.

The results from the four trials above did not deliver a conclusive result and did not identify one TBM as the best candidate. However, at the point of concluding the fourth trial, the direction of the research changed to focus on the role of TBMs in aid of Dyslexia and ADHD readability. Therefore, the conclusion from the trials was no longer relevant to the continuation of the survey.

8.2 ECONOMIC IMPETUS AND IMPACT OF TBMS

Pure, and even applied, academic research is not usually concerned with the economic aspects of the subject matter. However, in this case, it is difficult to overlook this as it is evident in daily life.

In academic terms, the development of large AI models such as GPT-style transformers is driven by a potent economic impetus rooted in both technological innovation and market demand. These models serve as foundational infrastructure for a wide array of commercial, governmental, and research applications. Among these are NLP, automation, customer service, content generation, education, and scientific discovery. The socioeconomic impact on the job industry and other aspects of social life, cannot be overlooked. There are many examples of that effect, found mainly online.

The economic drivers include:

- Scale economies – Large models benefit from economies of scale, where the marginal cost of additional use is low once the model is trained, making them cost-effective across many sectors.
- Competitive advantage – Firms investing in frontier models can gain significant strategic advantages, leading to winner-takes-most dynamics in sectors like search, advertising, and cloud computing.
- Labour substitution and augmentation – These models reduce costs and increase productivity by automating or supporting tasks previously requiring human labour, particularly in high-wage knowledge work.

The economic impact is multi-layered:

- Industry disruption – Large models reshape labour markets and business models in sectors ranging from legal services to journalism and software engineering.
- Resource concentration – Due to their high computational and financial demands, development is largely concentrated in a few well-capitalised firms or institutions, potentially exacerbating inequality and limiting open access.
- Global innovation spillovers – While high initial costs create barriers to entry, open models and APIs enable downstream innovation by smaller firms and educational institutions, thus expanding economic participation.

Overall, the rise of large AI models represents both an economic opportunity and a structural shift, with implications for productivity, inequality, and global technological sovereignty.

As mentioned in the literature survey of this thesis the introduction of DeepSeek demonstrates a startling effect of the economic factor of such development. The reaction of the technical and financial media to this event was examined and detailed below.

The launch of the DeepSeek AI model in January 2025 had a profound impact on global financial markets, particularly affecting the technology and semiconductor sectors (Batra, 2025). More widely, the market's impact resulted in stock market turmoil (Columbia Threadneedle Investments, n.d.) and investors' reassessment (City A.M., 2025).

On January 27, 2025, DeepSeek unveiled its cost-efficient AI model, leading to a significant sell-off in tech stocks. Nvidia's shares plummeted by nearly 18%, erasing approximately \$593 billion in market capitalisation, the largest single-day loss for a U.S. company. Other technological giants, like Microsoft, Alphabet, and Broadcom, also experienced notable declines.

The efficiency of DeepSeek model prompted investors to question the sustainability of high capital expenditures by major technology firms. Companies like

Microsoft and Meta, which had invested heavily in AI infrastructure, faced scrutiny over their spending strategies.

Wider economic impact affected other sectors of industry such as:

- Semiconductor Industry – DeepSeek’s ability to develop a competitive AI model using fewer and less advanced chips challenged the prevailing demand forecasts for high-end semiconductors. This raised concerns about the future growth prospects for chip manufacturers (Columbia Threadneedle Investments, n.d.).
- Energy Sector – The reduced computational requirements of DeepSeek suggested lower energy consumption for AI processes. This had a potential impact on the energy providers that had anticipated increased demand from data centres.
- Shift in Investment Focus –The success of a low-cost, open-source AI model like DeepSeek signalled a potential shift in investment from hardware-intensive AI solutions to more software-centric approaches, emphasising efficiency and accessibility (Ark Wealth Solutions, n.d.).

On the geopolitical scene, the DeepSeek launch affected the East-West technical dynamics as it highlighted China’s growing capabilities in AI. This has challenged the US dominance in the sector and underscores the ongoing technological competition between the two nations (Heikkilä, 2025).

In summary, DeepSeek’s launch not only disrupted financial markets but also prompted a re-evaluation of investment strategies, technological approaches, and geopolitical dynamics within the AI industry.

To illustrate this graphically, below is a Python code using information provided by ChatGPT about the effect of DeepSeek on market shares of other AI models with a graphic representation that follows (Fig. 24).

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
# Example financial data (in millions of dollars)
models = ['GPT-4', 'Claude', 'Gemini', 'Mistral', 'DeepSeek']
revenues_before = [180, 150, 140, 90, 0] # before DeepSeek entered
the market
```

```

revenues_after = [150, 120, 110, 70, 90] # after DeepSeek entered
x = range(len(models))
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
bar1 = plt.bar(x, revenues_before, width=0.4, label='Before DeepSeek',
align='center')
bar2 = plt.bar([i + 0.4 for i in x], revenues_after, width=0.4,
label='After DeepSeek', align='center')
plt.xticks([i + 0.2 for i in x], models)
plt.ylabel('Monthly Revenue (in millions USD)')
plt.title('Financial Impact of DeepSeek on Other Large AI Models')
plt.legend()
# Optional: Add labels on top of bars
for i in x:
    plt.text(i, revenues_before[i] + 2, f"{revenues_before[i]}",
ha='center')
    plt.text(i + 0.4, revenues_after[i] + 2, f"{revenues_after[i]}",
ha='center')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

The result was presented as a plot in figure 24 below.

FIGURE 24: ECONOMIC IMPACT OF DEEPSEEK

In this phase of the research, the same set of TBMs was evaluated in tasks specifically designed to simulate reading challenges commonly associated with Dyslexia and ADHD. These trials were informed by established neurocognitive theories on the origins of these conditions and aimed to assess the models' capabilities in supporting individuals with neurodivergence.

Drawing upon the Simple View of Reading (SVR) model, which conceptualises reading comprehension as a multiplicative function of decoding and language comprehension abilities (Gough & Tunmer, 1986), it was hypothesised that the advanced decoding and semantic understanding capacities inherent in TBMs would position them as promising tools for assisting individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD. Surprisingly, this hypothesis was not strongly supported by the empirical results.

While a range of software applications claim to leverage AI to support neurodivergent readers, there remains a notable absence of robust, openly available AI models or datasets specifically designed for this purpose. Many available tools primarily employ multimodal visual aids, such as colour coding, icons, or other superficial cues, rather than fully exploiting the capabilities of TBMs for semantic simplification, restructuring, and targeted linguistic adaptation.

Proprietary Dyslexia datasets do exist but remain inaccessible. Their restricted accessibility, due to commercial sensitivity or privacy concerns, hinders their utility for developing and finetuning large language models for this purpose. The reasons for that are either to protect their commercial value or prevent what could be privately held sensitive data, personal or commercial. Consequently, the full potential of TBMs to address the real linguistic challenges faced by individuals with Dyslexia and/or ADHD remains largely unexplored.

A large part of the problem with existing text from the point of view of a person with Dyslexia or ADHD, is, what is considered as the noise and distraction of the awkward structure and difficult vocabulary. This makes TBMs ideal for manipulating such texts by virtue of their excellent ability to simplify complex passages of texts, restructuring ability, and comprehension of the semantics of sentences.

Initial trials using simple text simplification prompts demonstrated that TBMs generally performed well when instructed to restructure complex sentences, employ simpler vocabulary, and organise content into more accessible formats such as bullet points. However, when tasked with more complex, multi-step transformations combining structural and phonetic manipulations, the models' performance deteriorated significantly. For instance, combining instructions such as syntactic restructuring alongside phonetic character substitutions led to frequent failure or incoherent outputs. This revealed a notable weakness in TBMs' ability to process and execute combined prompts, an area warranting deeper investigation.

This discovery of the weakness of these TBMs was revealing and needed further investigation. The full account of the failure to follow combined instructions evidenced in the trials of combining a request for simplification for an individual with Dyslexia or ADHD with another technique, namely Bionic Reading©, was reported in, Section 10 of Chapter 5 of this thesis.

While Bionic Reading© has been promoted as a potentially useful tool for enhancing reading efficiency, especially in digital contexts, its scientific efficacy remains contested within educational psychology literature (Paleshnikova, 2024; Snell, 2024). Importantly, Bionic Reading© alone does not address core distractibility issues frequently associated with ADHD, nor does it target the semantic and structural complexities that often impede readers with Dyslexia. Moreover, Bionic Reading©'s customisation options raise concerns regarding the degree of control placed in the hands of individual users. Allowing neurodivergent individuals to adjust the degree of visual emphasis without expert guidance could lead to suboptimal outcomes, much like allowing patients to self-regulate medication dosages without clinical supervision.

The initial reaction to Bionic Reading© in this research was positive. It represents a potential solution without the need to develop a sophisticated TBM and datasets to solve this issue. However, further survey of the literature, reveals multiple opposing schools and counter claims mainly from the education psychology cohort.

It is difficult to draw any conclusion on this method without extensive experimentation, but the other factors that affect ADHD readability cannot be

ignored. Noise and distraction are amongst these factors that this method does not address in the text seen by the person being helped.

Nevertheless, some TBMs in this trial were given prompts to simplify and apply some well-defined changes to the transformed text. Surprisingly those trials were not at all successful, which led to the idea of needing to do further investigation of the combined-prompt problem. That was also the motivation to build a proof-of-concept rule-based model to create a small dataset for Dyslexia. The model performed successfully on short sentences and a text of about 100 words.

To carry on with this topic, the researcher conducted the following exercise and came to a specific conclusion found in 8.3.2 below.

This exercise started with invoking ChatGPT to respond to the following prompt:

In the sentence "The big dog ate two meals" swap the location of the subject with the adjective and translate to French the rest of the sentence after the verb.

ChatGPT response:

Got it, Firas!

Let's go step by step again:

Original sentence:

"The big dog ate two meals."

- Subject: The dog

- Adjective: big (modifies "dog")

- Verb: ate

- Rest of the sentence after the verb: two meals

Step 1: Swap the location of the subject and the adjective

Instead of "The big dog", we place "big" first, then "the dog"

So, it becomes: "Big the dog ate..."

(This sounds odd in English but fits your request for swapping locations.)

Step 2: Translate the rest after the verb ("two meals") into French

"Two meals" → "deux repas"

✓ Final answer:

"Big the dog ate deux repas."

Then ChatGPT was tested with some phonetic elements by the prompt:

In the sentence "The big dog ate two meals" swap the location of the subject with the adjective and change every o to E.

ChatGPT response:

Alright Firas, let's break this down:

Original sentence:

"The big dog ate two meals."

- Subject: The dog

- Adjective: big

- You asked to swap the location of the subject with the adjective

- Then, change every "o" to "E"

Step 1: Swap the subject with the adjective

Instead of "The big dog", we move "big" to where "dog" was and "dog" to where "big" was.

So: "The dog big ate two meals."

Step 2: Change every "o" to "E"

Apply this to the whole sentence:

"The dEg big ate twE meals."

✓ Final result:

"The dEg big ate twE meals."

Want to try another transformation? These are great for language games or dyslexia exercises!

8.3.1 THE DYSLEXIA GAME

Inspired by observations during these trials, a novel pedagogical opportunity emerged. During interactive sessions with ChatGPT, the model's conversational responses suggested the potential for an educational language transformation game. This game concept involves presenting users with random sentences and instructing them to apply specific transformations, such as syntactic swaps or phonetic substitutions, followed by automated evaluation and feedback. Such exercises could offer a playful and interactive approach to enhancing linguistic awareness and processing flexibility for individuals with Dyslexia.

A prototype of this game was developed using ChatGPT, with the system generating dynamic challenges involving operations such as swapping the subject and adjective or replacing specific characters (e.g. converting "o" to "3"). In repeated trials, the model was able to generate, evaluate, and correct user responses, providing step-by-step feedback that reinforced learning.

As it is documented in the literature (Mayer, 2019), games can be very useful tools for education. The additional advantage of such a game concept is the design and creation which could be handled by AI models for expedience.

Therefore, the following instructions to build such a game were given:

Can you create a game if I give you a file of sentences to use with random questions to change one or two things within a sentence then check the answer and give the right answer if wrong?

ChatGPT response:

Yes, I'd love to help you build that game, Firas!

Here's what we can do together:

 How It Works:

1. You upload a file with your list of sentences (text or Word is fine).
2. I'll create a game engine that:
 - Picks a sentence at random

- Asks a fun transformation question (like “swap subject with adjective” or “change every O to E”)

- Checks your answer

- Tells you if it’s right or wrong

- Gives the correct version if needed

 Example Round:

Original: "The tall man climbed the ladder."

Question: Swap the verb with the object and replace every A with @

You answer: "The tall man the l@dder climbed."

System says: Incorrect. Correct version: "The tall man the l@dder climbed."

 Go ahead and upload your file

As soon as you send it, I’ll build the first version of your game using those sentences.

Ready when you are!

Prior to the first run, a file of the sentences to be used (a mini dataset) was uploaded and can be found in Appendix B of this thesis.

First run:

Nice try, Firas! Let’s check your answer step by step:

 Original Sentence:

"The ocean is beautiful."

 Challenge:

Swap the adjective and subject. Replace every "e" with "3".

- Subject: The ocean

- Adjective: beautiful

So swapping them gives:

"Beautiful the ocean is."

Now replace every “e” with “3”:

→ "B3autiful th3 oc3an is."

✓ Correct Answer:

"B3autiful th3 oc3an is."

✗ Your Answer:

"b3uatiful Th3 ocean is"

(You didn't fully swap, and missed a few e→3)

Want to try another one? I'll give you a new sentence + a random transformation!

Second run:

Nice try, Firas! Let's check how you did:

🔍 Original Sentence:

"The children played quietly."

- Adverb: quietly

✓ Step 1: Move the adverb to the beginning

→ "Quietly the children played."

✓ Step 2: Replace every "i" with "1"

→ "Qu1etly the ch1ldren played."

🎯 Correct Answer:

"Qu1etly the ch1ldren played."

✗ Your Answer:

"qu1etly The ch1ldren played"

Almost perfect! You:

- ✓ Moved the adverb

- ✓ Replaced all "i" with "1"

- ○ Just missed capitalizing "Quietly" at the start (no worries, that's tiny)

👤 Score: 9.5/10

Wanna go another round?

Third run (I must get this right 😊):

Nice work, Firas! Let's see how you did:

🔍 Original Sentence:

"She loves to eat ice cream."

- Verb: loves

- Object: ice cream

✅ Step 1: Swap the object with the verb

→ "Ice cream loves to eat she."

✅ Step 2: Replace every "e" with "3"

→ "Sh3 ic3 cr3am lov3s to 3at."

🎯 Correct Answer:

"Sh3 ic3 cr3am lov3s to 3at."

✅ Your Answer:

"Sh3 ic3 cr3am lov3s to 3at"

Perfect! You nailed both parts of the challenge. 🙌

Ready for the next round? 😊

This game can be stored permanently in the memory of ChatGPT (or other TBMs) and invoked by a chosen name. The dataset can be pre-created and uploaded on demand. The model can be instructed to pick a simple sentence from an unlimited resource on sites on the World Wide Web, such as Wikipedia, to make the game very exciting and always fresh. Alternatively, the dataset could be designed deliberately to implicitly educate using snippets of knowledge embedded in the original sentences, or ones that can inject some humour and amusement when it is changed. For example, changing "The mechanic fixed the car" to "The car fixed the mechanic" by swapping object for subject.

The implemented game engine was further developed into a Python-based prototype, capable of dynamically selecting sentence prompts, generating multi-

layered challenges, and providing automated feedback. The full codebase for this system is found below in Appendix C.

Not all models tried here were capable of creating such an interactive game. This is the response from Bing Chat for the same request:

I can't directly create an interactive game for you to play here, but I can help you design a concept for it or create code that you can run in a programming environment to implement it! For example, I could write a simple Python program that:

1. Randomly selects a sentence from your file.
2. Asks the user to modify one or two aspects of the sentence.
3. Checks the user's modification against the intended answer.
4. Provides feedback with the correct answer if the user is wrong.

If that sounds like something you'd like, let me know, and I'll craft some sample code for you!

Meta-AI proved more successful, but it took several attempts and changes of prompt before obtaining a similar result to ChatGPT. Since this is intended to be an educational tool, it is desirable to refer to words as “subject” and “adverb”, like in the ChatGPT’s version, to enhance the value of the exercise. In the Meta AI version, the instruction referred to the actual word that needed to change location and not its function in the sentence.

This extraneous prompt-engineering effort clearly supports the original argument that started this exercise as to the inability of some TBMs to handle combined instructions. Therefore, the case for further and deeper comparison study of TBMs from this perspective is indicated.

This observation reinforces a central finding of this research: despite their generalised language processing capabilities, TBMs vary considerably in their ability to handle combined instructions requiring complex transformations. These limitations have important implications for their deployment in educational interventions for neurodivergent populations.

The fifth prompt in the sequence of requesting Meta-AI to generate the desired game, was:

Can you create a game with same file of sentences to use with random questions to change one location of a word (verb, noun, etc.) and a character within a sentence then check the answer and give the right answer if wrong?

The variety of the answers obtained from Meta AI, reveals much more about either the architecture or the training or both. Here are some of the answers with prompts:

"The car fixed" becomes "The car foxed" and "mechanic" becomes "mechanoc" with the "i" to "o" change. Well done on that!

The full sentence with all "i"s changed to "o"s would be: "The car foxed the mechanoc."

Let's try another one:

Original sentence: "He brought a knife."

Question: Change the sentence to passive voice (so the focus is on "the knife") and change all the "e"s to "a"s in the sentence. What is the new sentence?

Tha knifa is brought

You're close! In passive voice, the sentence would be "A knife was brought by him" or more simply "A knife was brought". With the "e" to "a" change, it would be "A knifa was brought by him" isn't needed so "A knifa was brought".

Your attempt "Tha knifa is brought" is close, but the verb tense is slightly off.

8.3.2 DYSLEXIA AND ADHD CONCLUSION

While TBMs demonstrate promising capabilities for simplified transformations, their limitations in executing complex, multi-layered linguistic manipulations reveal the areas needing further development. To enable the full realisation of TBMs in supporting neurodivergent populations, two critical areas of future research are identified:

1. the development and open release of large-scale, high-quality Dyslexia and ADHD-specific datasets, and
2. the finetuning or development of TBMs specifically trained to handle the unique linguistic and attentional challenges faced by these individuals.

In conclusion, it was found extremely difficult to create a model to help Dyslexia and ADHD readability utilising TBMs. Most, if not all TBMs surveyed, faced difficulty processing combined instructions such as transforming part of a text to a different structure and translating the part after the verb to another language. An example of this was demanding the swap of location of the subject and its adjective as well as changing every “o” into “3” in the sentence “The large dog ate two meals” to produce “Large the d3g ate t3w meals”. When combined with aspects of Bionic Reading®, such as changing the font of some characters, the difficulty level increased further.

As additional conclusion, this clearly demonstrates and highlights the need for further investigation and research in the symptoms and aids for Dyslexia and ADHD. From the point of view of AI and data science in particular, the definite primary need is for good large Dyslexia (and possibly ADHD) datasets that are available for research, and subsequently, building new TBMs or/and training existing TBMs to enable them to perform this vital role for child education and countless adult sufferers.

Without extensive research and large-sized experiments, this claim cannot be substantiated. It is hoped that this research will serve as a foundation upon which future scholars can build more sophisticated, empirically validated tools for educational and cognitive support.

8.4 FUTURE RESEARCH

Throughout the course of this investigation into Transformer-Based Models (TBMs), several additional areas of inquiry and unresolved research questions have emerged. As this field remains relatively nascent, substantial opportunities exist for further advancement. Continued development may involve refining existing TBMs or constructing increasingly sophisticated models, particularly as advancements in

computational resources, including the prospective exploitation of quantum computing, expand the boundaries of what is technically feasible.

In the course of conducting these trials, this research has sought to present several foundational concepts and proofs of concept. Nevertheless, certain limitations were encountered, and multiple aspects of TBMs remain only partially explored and thus warrant further comprehensive investigation.

In this study, it has been difficult to find models that:

- Natively use YAM as an approach to simplifications
- Widely publicised or studied as powerful language error recovery tool
- Able to recognise the age parameter as an input and adjust their transformation accordingly

Therefore, the field of researching and improving TBMs remains wide open for further exploration and innovation.

In this section, the attention will be centred on only a few such potential applications of TBMs yet to be examined, and suggest future development for other research teams.

To expand the concept of domain-domain abilities of TBMs, similar trials can be conducted as detailed below.

It is important to emphasise a key outcome of this research before proceeding further. Although the study primarily examined six of the largest TBMs currently available, the research questions and limitations identified are equally relevant to the foundational models upon which many future models can be built. As previously discussed, it is essential to devote a greater attention to understanding the capabilities and limitations of these smaller core models. Through targeted training and finetuning, such models may be enhanced to perform more effectively, potentially reducing dependence on large-scale proprietary models accessible only through restricted API frameworks. This will also apply to all future trials and proposal listed below.

8.4.1 USER'S SUBJECT PROMPT

The objective of such approach is to train TBMs to recognise and react to the users' own speciality or familiarity of a particular domain of knowledge. The TBMs subsequently need to base their text transformation accordingly. For instance, a user can start a prompt as follows:

I am a musician, explain the concept of quantum entanglement to me.

The user in this case, does not have to ask for transformation in terms of music or by some metaphors. He/she neither needs to specify the source domain, in this case quantum physics, nor needs to know from which domain that term originates. They simply state their speciality and leave it to the trained TBM to decipher it.

FIGURE 25: USER'S SUBJECT TRIALS

This diagram demonstrates a similar trial to the ones in this thesis, where the input to various TBMs could be a number of similar prompts, and the output is measured every time using a similar AI metric model (Fig. 25).

The results of such trials can be tabulated as illustrated in Table 15 below:

TABLE 15: OUTPUT FROM USER'S SUBJECT TRIAL

Prompts	Outputs			
	Model A	Model B	Model C	Golden Standard (taken from earlier trial)
P1				
P2				
P3				
P4				

The initial test of this feature indicates that most TBMs are efficient at recognising prompters' speciality. They would respond accordingly using metaphors and concepts borrowed from the relevant subject of the prompter. However, a more thorough investigation of this feature may uncover other issues that need to be addressed.

8.4.2 PUBLICATION IDENTIFICATION

Another powerful avenue that can be tested and evaluated using current TBMs, is their recognition of well-known publications. The advantage of this is that when preparing a paper for publication, individual publications would have their particular requirements for formatting, including standards of references and quotations. These can easily be obtained from journals prior to publication. However, the most powerful feature that can be achieved by such TBMs is their ability to target the audience of the desired publication, while complying with the standards and formatting of the publication.

This means testing the ability of TBMs to:

- Identify well-known publications
- Recognise the audience, and the subjects that publication covers
- Transform the given materials in terms of the target publication

In the example given in the Introduction, a multidisciplinary text such as the one by Clayton (2023), could be modified for two kinds of audience, musical educators or neuroscientists. In that example, the researcher had to specify the type of audience and one TBM successfully transformed the text accordingly.

Below are the two outputs in full.

For neuroscience journal (transformed by ChatGPT):

Neuroscience Paper

Title: Implicit Sequence Learning in a Musical Sight-Reading Task: A Neuroscientific Perspective

Abstract Implicit learning is a fundamental cognitive mechanism facilitating skill acquisition in various domains, including music. This study investigates implicit sequence learning in the context of musical sight-reading, a skill requiring the rapid translation of visual notation into motor execution. Thirty-one musicians participated in an online experiment involving five sight-reading trials, with a repeated sequence embedded within randomized material. Performance was assessed using response time and accuracy measures. Results indicate that response times decreased, and accuracy improved for the repeated sequence, suggesting implicit learning effects. These findings support the role of implicit learning in musical skill development and highlight potential applications in cognitive neuroscience and music pedagogy.

Keywords: Implicit learning, sequence learning, sight-reading, music cognition, motor learning, neuroplasticity

Introduction Implicit learning, the unconscious acquisition of structured information, plays a crucial role in cognitive and motor skill development. It has been extensively studied in domains such as language acquisition, motor control, and visual perception. Music, with its structured yet complex temporal and spatial patterns, provides a unique framework for studying implicit learning. While research has demonstrated implicit acquisition of musical elements such as melody and harmony, little is known about its role in sight-reading—a skill that integrates visual processing, motor execution, and auditory feedback in real time.

Sight-reading requires musicians to decode visual symbols, anticipate auditory outcomes, and coordinate motor actions without conscious deliberation. It engages multiple cognitive faculties, including working memory, procedural learning, and motor control, all of which are associated with implicit learning mechanisms. Previous studies have shown that implicit learning enhances reaction time, decision-

making, and motor fluency in various domains, yet its specific impact on musical sight-reading remains underexplored. This study aims to investigate whether implicit sequence learning occurs in sight-reading and to assess its potential benefits for musical skill acquisition.

Methods

Participants Thirty-one musicians (15 professional, 10 advanced, 6 intermediate) participated in the study. Instruments represented included strings, woodwinds, brass, piano, and voice. Inclusion criteria required a minimum Grade 6 sight-reading proficiency (Associated Board of the Royal Schools of Music standard). Participants provided informed consent, and ethical approval was obtained from Royal Holloway, University of London.

Experimental Design A repeated-measures design was employed, with participants completing five sight-reading trials. Each trial consisted of three sequences: a unique first and third sequence and a repeated middle sequence. Performance was assessed by response time (time taken to complete each sequence) and accuracy (percentage of correctly performed notes).

Stimuli and Procedure Atonal musical sequences were generated using a serialist approach, ensuring the absence of tonal cues. Stimuli were displayed on participants' screens via PDF files. Participants performed each sequence on their instrument in real-time while audio was recorded for analysis. After completing the trials, participants underwent a post-experiment questionnaire assessing their awareness of sequence repetition.

Data Analysis Response times were extracted from audio recordings using GarageBand software. Accuracy was determined by independent raters comparing performances to the notated sequences. Statistical analyses included paired-sample t-tests and regression analysis to examine learning effects.

Results Analysis of response times revealed a significant reduction for the repeated sequence over trials ($t(30) = -3.95, p < .001$), indicating learning effects. Accuracy also improved significantly for the repeated sequence compared to non-repeated sequences ($t(30) = 9.54, p < .001$). Awareness assessments showed that 90% of

participants remained unaware of the repeated sequence, supporting the implicit nature of learning.

A correlation analysis identified cognitive load effects, with increased note density leading to longer response times ($r(13) = .49, p < .05$). However, implicit learning effects persisted despite higher cognitive demands, suggesting robustness of sequence learning under increased task complexity.

Discussion The findings confirm that implicit learning occurs in musical sight-reading, manifesting as improved response times and accuracy for repeated sequences. These results align with previous research on serial reaction time tasks and implicit motor learning, reinforcing the idea that musicians acquire procedural knowledge of musical structures through repeated exposure without conscious awareness.

This study also highlights the influence of cognitive load on sight-reading performance. Increased note density led to slower processing times, yet implicit learning effects remained significant. This suggests that implicit learning may enhance efficiency in high-demand musical tasks, offering potential applications in music training and rehabilitation for individuals with cognitive or motor impairments. Moreover, individual differences in learning rates and error patterns provide insights into the neurocognitive basis of music perception and performance. Future research should explore neural correlates of implicit learning in music using neuroimaging techniques to identify underlying brain mechanisms.

Conclusion This study demonstrates that implicit sequence learning enhances musical sight-reading performance by improving response times and accuracy. The findings contribute to the growing body of research on music cognition and suggest potential applications for implicit learning strategies in music education and cognitive neuroscience. Further research incorporating neurophysiological measures could provide deeper insights into the neural mechanisms supporting implicit musical learning.

References (Include formatted references in APA or a relevant journal-specific citation style.)

For music education journal (transformed by ChatGPT):

Implicit Sequence Learning in a Sight-Reading Task: Implications for Music Education

Abstract

Implicit learning plays a crucial role in music acquisition, yet its impact on sight-reading remains underexplored. This study investigates whether implicit sequence learning enhances sight-reading performance. Thirty-one musicians completed a sight-reading task with embedded repeated sequences, measuring response time and accuracy. Results showed significant improvements in the repeated sequences, suggesting that implicit learning accelerates visual processing and motor execution in sight-reading. Findings highlight the potential for integrating implicit learning strategies into music education to improve fluency and reduce cognitive load. These results align with research in language acquisition and motor learning, reinforcing the role of implicit learning in skill development. Implications for pedagogy include the design of instructional materials that leverage pattern recognition and repetition to enhance musical literacy. Future research should explore its application in diverse musical traditions and stress conditions.

Keywords: implicit learning, sight-reading, music education, cognitive load, performance fluency

Introduction

Sight-reading is a fundamental skill in classical music performance, yet it remains a challenging aspect of musicianship. While research has established the role of implicit learning in language acquisition, motor skills, and memory, its application to music education—specifically sight-reading—has not been fully explored. This study examines whether implicit sequence learning can enhance sight-reading proficiency by improving response times and accuracy.

Background and Theoretical Framework

Implicit learning occurs without conscious awareness and has been observed in various domains, including second-language acquisition (Choo, et al., 2012; Rashidi

& Ganbari, 2010), motor control (Raab, et al., 2009), and cognitive rehabilitation (Schuchard & Thompson, 2014). In music, previous studies have shown that implicit learning facilitates melodic and harmonic recognition (Rohrmeier & Rebuschat, 2012) and enhances the retention of unfamiliar musical structures (Dienes & Longuet-Higgins, 2004). This study builds on these findings to examine whether implicit sequence learning also benefits the technical skill of sight-reading.

Methodology

Thirty-one musicians (intermediate to professional level) participated in an online sight-reading experiment. Participants performed five sight-reading trials containing randomized atonal sequences, with the middle sequence in each trial repeated across all five trials. Performance was assessed through response times and accuracy. Participants were unaware of the repetition, ensuring that improvements resulted from implicit learning rather than conscious memorization.

Results

Analysis showed that response times significantly decreased for the repeated sequences compared to non-repeated ones. Accuracy also improved, suggesting that musicians acquired and applied implicit knowledge of the repeated sequence. Notably, the study found that implicit learning effects persisted despite increasing cognitive load, reinforcing its robustness in musical skill acquisition.

Discussion

These findings support the hypothesis that implicit learning can accelerate sight-reading proficiency. The ability to process notation more efficiently suggests that implicit learning reduces the cognitive burden of sight-reading, enabling smoother and more fluent performances. This aligns with research in visual context learning and motor adaptation, where repetition enhances efficiency and accuracy (Milazzo, et al., 2016).

Implications for Music Education

1. **Curriculum Design:** Incorporating implicit learning strategies, such as structured repetition and pattern recognition exercises, could enhance sight-reading pedagogy.

2. **Instructional Techniques:** Educators can design exercises that embed repeating motifs in reading exercises, allowing students to develop fluency without explicit memorization.
3. **Reducing Performance Anxiety:** Since implicit learning remains resilient under pressure (Lam, et al., 2009), integrating it into training could help students maintain accuracy and fluency in high-stakes performance settings.

Conclusion

Implicit learning significantly improves sight-reading proficiency by enhancing response times and accuracy. These findings suggest that incorporating implicit learning into music education could yield substantial benefits. Further research should examine its application across different musical traditions and its effectiveness in reducing performance anxiety.

References

(Formatted according to the Chicago Manual of Style, 18th edition, with footnotes or endnotes for MEJ submission)

This could be very helpful for assisting in the publication of existing documents for the benefit of differing reading audiences.

8.4.3 MORE ON DOMAIN-DOMAIN TRANSFORMATION

During conducting the experiment with ChatGPT and Meta-AI to ascertain if TBMs can handle complex instructions for transformation in conjunction with Bionic Reading®, the researcher theorised about the differing abilities of TBMs. From that experiment, it became evident that certain differences do exist as predicted.

This materialised upon prompting Meta-AI to instruct a player of an educational word game to change some characters within a text. By *character*, the prompt was referring to a letter or a digit in a text.

The prompt:

Can you create a game with same file of sentences to use with random questions to change one location of a word (verb, noun, etc.) and a character within a sentence then check the answer and give the right answer if wrong?

The response:

Let's play a game where I'll randomly select a sentence and ask a question to change one element (like a verb or noun) and also change the character or perspective within the sentence.

Here's your first challenge:

Original sentence: "He thought the ghost was real."

Question: Change the character to "She" and change the noun "ghost" to "monster". What is the new sentence?

Meta-AI wrongly assumed that the game is of a literary nature and there is a story to be edited to create another version of the same story. Even though there was no indication or reference in the prompt to anything literary, it interpreted the word *character* as a personality in a story or a play.

This indicates that some imperfection in the training of Meta-AI and how it processes meaning. Language models learn from massive amounts of text where words like *character* most often mean "a person in a story" unless the context makes it very clear.

Some of reasons why such confusion can happen are:

- Frequency bias – In literature and stories, the word *character* usually refers to a person, therefore this model associates that meaning more strongly with this word.
- Context sensitivity – Large language models look at surrounding words to figure out meaning. If there is not enough technical or computing context, it defaults to the more common usage.
- Polysemy – English has lots of words with multiple meanings (like *character*). If the model is not explicitly taught to disambiguate them well, it can make mistakes.

This places the responsibility on the user to disambiguate such words, which may reflect limitations in the model's training. However, this remains an open question requiring further investigation.

Future research could explore improved disambiguation strategies within TBMs, enhanced context-sensitive embeddings, integration of semantic knowledge bases, and specialised training on domain-specific or neurodivergent datasets.

Additionally, advancing multi-step reasoning capabilities and refining prompt engineering techniques may offer further avenues for improving model robustness and reduce the user's role in resolving ambiguities.

8.5 FUTURE CHALLENGES

While this study has demonstrated the potential of TBMs to support accessibility and cognitive adaptation, several challenges remain that warrant future attention.

A comprehensive user-oriented testing is essential to evaluate real-world effectiveness of future systems. The other challenge lies in refining and adapting these systems for diverse learner needs.

The cross-language support presents another significant frontier, as phonetic, syntactic, and orthographic differences pose unique challenges for multilingual adaptation.

Moreover, practical barriers to adoption, such as integration into existing educational platforms, user trust, and digital literacy, must be addressed to ensure a broad, equitable impact.

Tackling these issues will be key to translating the theoretical promise of this work into sustainable, inclusive solutions.

8.6 OVERALL CONCLUSION

This research has undertaken a systematic examination of the capabilities and limitations of contemporary Transformer-Based Models (TBMs) in addressing a range of complex language transformation tasks.

Particular emphasis was placed on exploring their potential applications in supporting individuals with Dyslexia and ADHD. To validate the theoretical findings, a small-scale, real-world experiment was conducted with school children, providing initial empirical support for the broader educational implications of the study.

While TBMs demonstrated competence in basic simplification and restructuring tasks, significant challenges emerged when models were tasked with processing multi-step or combined instructions, a scenario especially relevant for neurodivergent accessibility.

The development of a prototype educational app further highlighted both the potential and current limitations of these models in real-world pedagogical context. Importantly, this study underscores the urgent need for the creation of high-quality, openly accessible Dyslexia and ADHD-specific datasets, and suggests that meaningful progress will require not only larger models, but also more targeted finetuning and architectural refinements.

The findings presented here contribute both practical tools and theoretical insights, offering a foundation for future research aimed at developing AI systems capable of more nuanced, inclusive, and educationally valuable language support.

APPENDIX A: DYSLEXIA DATASET

Original	simplified	generated_simplified
The phone rang in the quiet room.	de fone rang in de kwiet rum.	The fone rang in the kwiet room.
She knew the knife was sharp.	she new de nife was sharp.	She new the nife was sharp.
He thought the ghost was real.	he dowt de ost was reel.	He thofft the ost was real.
Though he tried, he failed.	dow he tried, he failed.	Thoff he tried, he failed.
Please write your name on the paper.	pleese rite yowr name on de paper.	Please rite your name on the paper.
They laughed at the rough joke.	dey laued at de row joke.	They laued at the roff joke.
The children played quietly.	de kildren played kwietly.	The shildren played kwietly.
This station is always busy.	dis stashun is always busy.	This stashun is always busy.
I bought a book from the store.	i bowt a buk from de store.	I bofft a book from the store.
The character was brave.	de karakter was brave.	The sharakter was brave.
He fixed the box quickly.	he fiksed de boks kwikkly.	He fiksed the boks kwikly.
I can't see the city clearly.	i kan't see de sity kleeerly.	I kan't see the sity klearly.
The fancy dress was expensive.	de fany dress was ekspensive.	The fany dress was ekspensive.
She loves to eat ice cream.	she loves to eet is kreem.	She loves to eat ise krem.
He shouted out loud.	he showted owt lowd.	He shouted out loud.
The school is closed today.	de skul is klosed today.	The sshool is klosed today.
What do you think about this?	wat do yow dink abowt dis?	wat do you think about this?
They danced in the moonlight.	dey dansd in de munlit.	They dansed in the moonlit.
The ocean is beautiful.	de osan is beautiful.	The osean is botiful.
He broke the chair on accident.	he broke de kair on aksident.	He broke the shair on aksident.
I need to phone my mother.	i need to fone my moder.	I need to fone my mother.
We went through the tunnel.	we went drow de tunnel.	We went throff the tunnel.

The wind blew through the trees.	de wind blew drow de trees.	The wind blew throff the trees.
He writes with his right hand.	he rites wid his rit hand.	He rites with his rit hand.
The science teacher is nice.	de ssiens teeker is nis.	The ssiense teasher is nise.
The quick brown fox jumps.	de kwikk brown foks jumps.	The kwik brown foks jums.
The vacuum cleaner is broken.	de vakuum kleener is broken.	The vakuum kleaner is broken.
They will visit the museum.	dey will visit de museum.	They will visit the museum.
He studies architecture.	he studies arkitekture.	He studies arshitekture.
That machine is complicated.	dat makine is komplikated.	That mashine is komplikated.
The weather is bad today.	de weeder is bad today.	The weather is bad today.
This equation is difficult.	dis ekwashun is diffikult.	This ekwashun is diffikult.
The mechanic fixed the car.	de mekanik fiksed de kar.	The meshanik fiksed the kar.
Don't laugh at her.	don't lau at her.	Don't lau at her.
This story is interesting.	dis story is interesting.	This story is interesting.
We walked through the woods.	we walked drow de wuds.	We walked throff the woods.
The knight wore armor.	de nit wore armor.	The nit wore armor.
He brought a knife.	he browt a nife.	He brofft a nife.
The psychologist explained the theory.	de psykologist eksplained de deory.	The syshologist eksplained the theory.
What should we do now?	wat showld we do now?	wat should we do now?
Please knock before entering.	pleese nokk before entering.	Please nok before entering.
She coughed loudly.	she kowed loudly.	She koffed loudly.
The chemistry lab is dangerous.	de kemistry lab is dangerows.	The shemistry lab is dangerous.
A tsunami hit the coast.	a tsunami hit de koast.	A tsunami hit the koast.
I have enough food.	i have enow fud.	I have enoff food.
He wrapped the gift.	he rapped de gift.	He rapped the gift.
He caught the ball.	he kaut de ball.	He kaut the ball.

I wrote a poem.	i rote a poem.	I rote a pem.
They whistled a tune.	dey wistled a tune.	They wistled a tune.
The magician vanished quickly.	de magisian vanished kwikkly.	The magisian vanished kwikly.

APPENDIX B: GAME SENTENCES

Original	Original	Original
The phone rang in the quiet room.	He writes with his right hand.	The wind blew through the trees.
She knew the knife was sharp.	The science teacher is nice.	He wrapped the gift.
He thought the ghost was real.	The quick brown fox jumps.	He caught the ball.
Though he tried, he failed.	The vacuum cleaner is broken.	I wrote a poem.
Please write your name on the paper.	They will visit the museum.	They whistled a tune.
They laughed at the rough joke.	He studies architecture.	The magician vanished quickly.
The children played quietly.	That machine is complicated.	The wind blew through the trees.
This station is always busy.	The weather is bad today.	We went through the tunnel.
I bought a book from the store.	This equation is difficult.	I have enough food.
The character was brave.	The mechanic fixed the car.	He wrapped the gift.
He fixed the box quickly.	Don't laugh at her.	I need to phone my mother.
I can't see the city clearly.	This story is interesting.	A tsunami hit the coast.
The fancy dress was expensive.	We walked through the woods.	The chemistry lab is dangerous.
She loves to eat ice cream.	The knight wore armor.	He broke the chair by accident.
He shouted out loud.	He brought a knife.	She coughed loudly.
The school is closed today.	The psychologist explained the theory.	The ocean is beautiful.
What do you think about this?	What should we do now?	Please knock before entering.
They danced in the moonlight.		

APPENDIX C: PYTHON GAME CODE

```
import random
import re
# Define in-code sentence list
sentences = [
    "The phone rang in the quiet room.",
    "She knew the knife was sharp.",
    "He thought the ghost was real.",
    "Though he tried, he failed.",
    "Please write your name on the paper.",
    "They laughed at the rough joke.",
    "The children played quietly.",
    "This station is always busy.",
    "I bought a book from the store.",
    "The character was brave.",
    "He fixed the box quickly.",
    "I can't see the city clearly.",
    "The fancy dress was expensive.",
    "She loves to eat ice cream.",
    "He shouted out loud.",
    "The school is closed today.",
    "What do you think about this?",
    "They danced in the moonlight.",
    "The ocean is beautiful.",
    "He broke the chair on accident.",
    "I need to phone my mother.",
    "We went through the tunnel.",
    "The wind blew through the trees.",
    "He writes with his right hand.",
    "The science teacher is nice.",
    "The quick brown fox jumps.",
    "The vacuum cleaner is broken.",
    "They will visit the museum.",
    "He studies architecture.",
    "That machine is complicated.",
    "The weather is bad today.",
    "This equation is difficult.",
```

```

    "The mechanic fixed the car.",
    "Don't laugh at her.",
    "This story is interesting.",
    "We walked through the woods.",
    "The knight wore armor.",
    "He brought a knife."
]
# Define transformation challenges
def swap_adverb_start(sentence):
    words = sentence.split()
    for i, word in enumerate(words):
        if word.endswith("ly"):
            adverb = words.pop(i)
            words.insert(0, adverb)
            return ' '.join(words), f"Move the adverb to the start
of the sentence."
    return sentence, None
def change_e_to_3(sentence):
    return sentence.replace("e", "3"), "Change every 'e' to '3'."
def change_o_to_at(sentence):
    return sentence.replace("o", "@"), "Change every 'o' to '@'."
def change_i_to_1(sentence):
    return sentence.replace("i", "1"), "Change every 'i' to '1'."
def change_x_to_cks(sentence):
    return sentence.replace("x", "cks"), "Change every 'x' to
'cks'."
def swap_subject_and_adjective(sentence):
    words = sentence.split()
    adjectives = ["big", "small", "quiet", "loud", "brave", "nice",
"quick", "fancy"]
    for i in range(1, len(words)):
        if words[i].lower() in adjectives:
            words[i-1], words[i] = words[i], words[i-1]
            return ' '.join(words), "Swap the adjective with the
word before it."
    return sentence, None
def swap_subject_and_verb(sentence):
    words = sentence.split()
    for i, word in enumerate(words):

```

```

        if word.lower() in ["is", "are", "was", "were", "ate",
"wrote", "ran", "jumped", "fixed"]:
            if i > 0:
                words[i-1], words[i] = words[i], words[i-1]
            return ' '.join(words), "Swap the subject with the
verb."
    return sentence, None
def reverse_sentence_order(sentence):
    words = sentence.split()
    return ' '.join(words[::-1]), "Reverse the order of all words in
the sentence."
challenges = [
    swap_adverb_start,
    change_e_to_3,
    change_o_to_at,
    change_i_to_1,
    change_x_to_cks,
    swap_subject_and_adjective,
    swap_subject_and_verb,
    reverse_sentence_order
]
def play_game():
    sentence = random.choice(sentences)
    chosen_challenges = random.sample(challenges, 2)
    transformed = sentence
    instructions = []
    for challenge in chosen_challenges:
        result = challenge(transformed)
        if isinstance(result, tuple):
            transformed, instr = result
        else:
            transformed = result
            instr = challenge.__doc__ or ""
        if instr:
            instructions.append(instr)
    print("\nOriginal sentence:", sentence)
    print("Challenge:")
    for instr in instructions:
        print("-", instr)

```

```
user_input = input("\nYour answer: ")
print("\nCorrect answer:", transformed)
if user_input.strip().lower() == transformed.lower():
    print("✅ Well done!")
else:
    print("❌ Almost! Keep trying.")
# Run the game
if __name__ == '__main__':
    while True:
        play_game()
        if input("\nPlay again? (y/n): ").lower() != 'y':
            break
```

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